

Linear Variable Filter Fabrication and its Applications in Miniaturized Spectrometer

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the
West of Scotland for the award of **Doctor of Philosophy**,

01/09/2023.

Sijia Cai, M.Sc. Physics

Supervised by

Dr. Shigeng Song – Director of Studies

Professor Des Gibson – First Supervisor

Dr. Mojtaba Mirzaeian – Second Supervisor

Abstract

This thesis presents new designs for a linear variable filter (LVF) and discusses their manufacture using drum-based microwave plasma-assisted pulsed DC magnetron reactive sputtering. By using this deposition method, LVF samples for both the visible and near-infrared bands are manufactured, and spectroscopic measurements are used to characterize the LVF samples. It is demonstrated that deposition times can be reduced to a few days rather than the 6 weeks of alternative designs and methods described in the literature. The drum-based tool used here is shown to allow multiple copies of the filters to be manufactured in one run, increasing potential throughput by at least an order of magnitude over alternative deposition techniques.

An innovative miniaturized spectrometer design is proposed using the LVFs described in this thesis and several iterations are manufactured and tested. These miniaturized spectrometers are suitable for portable and real-time monitoring applications. Compared with traditional spectrometers, the manufacturing cost is relatively low, and the use of advanced microelectronic technologies opens up applications in chemical testing, food safety, material analysis, energy testing and other fields.

The design and analysis of the LVFs is achieved using thin film design software (TFCalc). The designs are based on narrow-bandpass filters and wide blocking filters, deposited on front and back surfaces of suitable substrates using the drum-based microwave plasma assisted DC magnetron sputtering thin film deposition system (Microdyn). Two particular LVFs are designed, one with a working range of 450 nm - 900 nm and linearity of 11.14 nm / mm for use in the visible light band and another with a working range of 1.5 μm - 2.5 μm and linearity of 42.68 nm / mm for use in the near-infrared band.

Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2 materials are selected as high and low refractive index materials respectively and their optical constants characterised by fitting to spectroscopic data for subsequent use in TFCalc.

To fabricate linear variable filters, the deposited film thickness must vary linearly along the length of the substrate. This is achieved by modelling the distribution of sputtered material arriving at the substrate during the sputtering process used in the MicroDyn tool. Optimal masking functions are designed using MathCad 15 scripts and successfully manufactured to

fit the target holders. With this mask in place, single thin film layers of the selected materials are shown to exhibit a linear trend in thickness over 44 mm lengths of glass and silicon substrates allowing the successful manufacture of the designed LVFs. Spectroscopic measurements at selected points along the lengths of the LVFs confirm the designed performance, with the central wavelength deviating from linearity by less than 1% over the 450 nm - 900 nm range and varying by a very satisfactory 10.8 nm/mm.

The continuous nature of LVFs means that different sizes of the illuminating spot produce different degrees of an averaging or blurring effect on spectral results and this effect is simulated, analysed and quantified for various spot sizes using square-wave and Pearson functions, with the Pearson VII function shown to give the best fit. This information can be used to improve the resolution of measurements. The full width at half maximum with an incident beam size of 0.4 mm is shown to be 11.2 nm.

Solidworks is used to design a miniaturized-spectrometer device incorporating the LVF as the core component, and 3D printing is used to manufacture practical spectrometers. An MCU control module is designed for the miniaturized spectrometer and an interface program is written to be used in a PC with the Windows operating system. Finally, optical thin film samples are measured using the manufactured spectrometers and compared with measurements obtained with an expensive conventional spectrometer equipment. Best results are obtained with the third iteration of spectrometer design, based on a threaded screw instead of 3D printed gears to scan the LVF past the single detector.

Suggestions for future work and potential improvements are discussed.

Declaration by candidate

I Sijia Cai hereby declare that the work presented in this thesis is my own work and has not been submitted in part or whole, for any other degrees at this or any other University or Institute. Where other sources of information have been used, they have been acknowledged in the appropriate format.

Signed:

Personal details withheld.

Date: 10/09/2023

Acknowledgement

In the blink of an eye, I have spent five years studying at UWS. It was a pleasant and enriching experience that will play a very important role in my future life.

This thesis was completed under the careful guidance of my director of studies Dr. Shigeng Song. Thank you very much for giving me the opportunity to participate in scientific research, providing a free and relaxed research environment. You have extensive knowledge, excellent humanistic qualities and moral qualities. He taught ideas, methods in scientific research and helped me for planning my future life, which benefited me a lot.

Special thanks to first supervisor Prof. Des Gibson, second supervisor Dr. Mojtaba Mirzaeian, assessor Dr Carlos Garcia Nunez and Dr. Lewis Fleming. Thanks to Prof. Des Gibson for helping coordinate the use of equipment and directing the completion of some critical tasks. Thanks also to Dr. Mojtaba Mirzaeian and Dr Carlos Garcia Nunez for supervisor. Thanks to Dr. Lewis Fleming for giving me great help in my doctoral experiment and thesis writing.

The completion of the thesis is also inseparable from the help of everyone in the ITFSI thin film laboratory. I would like to express my gratitude to Dr. David Hutson, Sam Ahmadzadeh, Daxing Han, Jian Song, Zhentao Wu and others for their help in scientific research or life.

In addition, I would also like to thank my parents. Without their support and encouragement, I might not have the opportunity and ability to get to where I am today. They will always be my strong backing.

Finally, I would like to express my most sincere thanks again to all the classmates and friends who cared about and helped the author during the process of dissertation. I wish you a successful career and a happy life. I would also like to express my sincere thanks to all the experts who participated in the defence and review of this thesis!

List of Symbols and Abbreviations

3D	-----	3-Dimensional
AC	-----	Alternating Current
A/D	-----	Analog to Digital
ADC	-----	A built-in Digital-to-Analogue Converter
AOTF	-----	Acousto-Optic Tunable Filters
ANN	-----	Artificial Neural Network
APD	-----	Avalanche Photodiode
BPF	-----	Band-Pass Filter
CCD	-----	Charge Coupled Device
CCS	-----	Code Composer Studio
CPC	-----	Compound Parabolic Concentrator
CVD	-----	Chemical Vapor Deposition
CVF	-----	Circular Variable Filter
CPU	-----	Central Processing Unit
DC	-----	Direct Current
DMD	-----	Digital Micromirror Device
DSI	-----	Deposition Sciences, INC
EO	-----	Earth-Orbiting Mission
FTIR	-----	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer
FPBP	-----	Fabry-Perot Band Pass
FWHM	-----	Full-Width at Half-Maximum
GR	-----	Growth Rate
GPIB	-----	General-Purpose Interface Bus
HWHM	-----	Half-Width at Half-Maximum
IBAD	-----	Ion Beam Assisted Deposition
IBS	-----	Ion Beam Sputtering

IBD	-----	Ion Beam Deposition
IDE	-----	Integrated Development
I/O	-----	Input/output
ISF	-----	Integrated Stepwise Filter
LCD	-----	Liquid Crystal Display
LED	-----	Light Emitting Diode
LVBF	-----	Linear Variable Bandpass Filter
LVE	-----	Linear Variable Etalon
LVF	-----	Liner Variable Filters
LVOF	-----	Linear-Variable Optical Filter
LWPF	-----	Long-wave Pass Filter
MCU	-----	Micro Controller Unit
MEMS	-----	Micro Electro-Mechanical System
MFC	-----	Microsoft Foundation Classes
MLR	-----	Multiple Linear Regression
MOEMS	-----	Micro Optical Electro-Mechanical System
MS	-----	Microscope Slides
MSM Detector	-----	Metal-Semiconductor-Metal Photodetector
NASA	-----	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NIR	-----	Near Infrared Filter
OGC	-----	Optical Gas Controller
PCA	-----	Principal Component Analysis
PIN	-----	Positive Intrinsic Negative
PLA	-----	Polylactic Acid
PLS	-----	Partial Least Squares
PVD	-----	Physical Vapor Deposition
RF	-----	Radio Frequency
RIBD	-----	Reactive Ion Beam Deposition

SNR	-----	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SWPF	-----	Short-Wave Pass Filter
UART	-----	Universal Asynchronous Receiver/Transmitter
USIC	-----	Universal Serial Communications Interface
UV	-----	Ultra-Violet
VISA	-----	Virtual Instrument Software Architecture
VOCs	-----	Volatile Organic Compounds
WBPB	-----	Wide Band Pass Blocking Filter

List of Figures

Figure 2. 1. The electromagnetic spectrum (Nikolov, 2016).	28
Figure 2. 2. Principle of reflection (Peatross and Michael, 2015).	31
Figure 2. 3. (a) Monolayer film (Macleod, 1986, p. 5) (b) Multilayer film.	32
Figure 2. 4. Structures of two beam splitters (Macleod, 1986).	36
Figure 2. 5. Reflectance curves of metal reflective films of different materials (Hass, 1955; Macleod, 1986).	37
Figure 2. 6. Principle of long-wave and short-wave pass filters: (a) long-wave pass filter, (b) short-wave pass filter (Jinfa et al., 2006).	38
Figure 2. 7. (a) Fabry-Perot standard device and its thin film device; (b) Spectral transmission characteristic diagram of Fabry-Perot type filter(Macleod, 1986, p. 180).	39
Figure 2. 8. Two basic types of all-dielectric Fabry-Perot filter structures.	40
Figure 2. 9. Schematic diagram of the spectral characteristics of an LVF.	41
Figure 2. 10. Illustration of generic dispersion in a prism (Goran_tek-en, 2023).	46
Figure 2. 11: Schematic diagram of grating principle.	47
Figure 2. 12. Schematic diagram of the principle of a Fourier transform spectrometer.	49
Figure 2. 13. Energy level scheme demonstrating the principle of Electron Spectrum Generation.	51
Figure 2. 14. Common spectrometer structure composition.	52
Figure 2. 15. Array LED-type miniature spectrometer (Yu, Lu and Gao, 2013). Figure (a) is the schematic diagram of the LED array, (b) Zeltex ZX-50 (ZELTEX Inc., 2023).	54
Figure 2. 16. Schematic diagram of a miniature near-infrared spectrometer using an LVF as the core. (a) LVF diffuse reflection mode and signal collection method; (b) Micro NIR 1700 (O'Brien et al., 2012a).	55
Figure 2. 17. Grating spectrometer schematic. In the figure on the right, 1 is the fibre coupler, 2 is the entrance slit, 3 is the collimating mirror, 4 is the diffraction grating, 5 is the focusing	

mirror, 6 is the array detector, and 7 is the thermoelectric cooler.....	56
Figure 2. 18. Illustration of Fourier transform spectrometer layout (Thermo Secentific, 2006).	56
Figure 2. 19. HiperScan's scanning grating spectrometer (SGS).....	57
Figure 3. 1. The Microdyn Sputtering Thin Film Deposition System.	58
Figure 3. 2. The internal structure of the Microdyn. (a) Image of the cavity structure, (b) Schematic diagram of the cavity structure.	59
Figure 3. 3. Side view of the Microdyn's chamber outline.	60
Figure 3. 4. The Microdyn's thin film deposition control system.	60
Figure 3. 5. Cathode voltage as a function of time traces for bipolar symmetrical and asymmetrical pulsed DC power (Westwood, Glocker; and Shah, 2018, p. 28).....	63
Figure 3. 6. Microwave plasma source and waveguide.	64
Figure 3. 7. The waveguide structure used in Microdyn.	65
Figure 3. 8. The relationship between the target voltage and the oxygen flux of the reactant gas (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012, p. 323).	67
Figure 3. 9. Thin film deposition rate as a function of oxygen flux of reactant gases (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012, p. 323).	68
Figure 3. 10. Wasa summarizes hysteresis characteristics in different modes of reactive sputtering (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012).	69
Figure 3. 11. Diagram of the Microdyn working steps. Schematic diagrams of (a) microwave plasma pre-cleaning stage, (b) metal film deposition and (c) dielectric film deposition.	71
Figure 3. 12. The Aquila NKD-8000 optical thin film characterization equipment.	73
Figure 3. 13. NKD-8000 internal structure diagram.	73
Figure 3. 14. Lambda 40 Dual Beam UV/Vis Spectrometer.	74
Figure 3. 15. Nicolet iS50 FTIR spectrometer.	75
Figure 4. 1. K9, JGS3 and microscope slide substrate transmittance spectrum curves.	79

Figure 4. 2. Spectral transmittance curves of Si, GaAs, Ge, and ZnSe uncoated substrates in the infrared band.80

Figure 4. 3. Optical transmittance measurements using the Perkin-Elmer Lambda 40 for (a) single layer Nb₂O₅ film H20I1409 (Nb₂O₅ thickness 860 nm) and (b) double layer film SiO₂ on Nb₂O₅ on JGS3 H20I1417 (SiO₂ thickness 840 nm). 85

Figure 4. 4. Refractive index n (left) and extinction coefficient κ (right) of (a) Nb₂O₅ and (b) SiO₂. 86

Figure 4. 5. TFCalc film design software fitting for (a) single-layer film Nb₂O₅ on JGS3 and (b) double-layer film SiO₂ on Nb₂O₅ on JGS3(those pictures obtained by screenshot). 86

Figure 4. 6. Optical transmittance of modelled Narrow Band Visible region FPBP LVF at 450, 675, 900 nm, designed by using TFCalc. 88

Figure 4. 7. Modelled Wide Band Blocking Bandpass filter of the visible band LVF at 450, 675, 900 nm, designed by using TFCalc. 89

Figure 4. 8. Modelled optical transmittance of the FPBP with WBPB filter in the visible band at 450, 675, 900 nm, designed using TFCalc. 90

Figure 4. 9. Modelled optical transmittance of the narrow band FPBP filter for the NIR LVF at 1500, 2000 and 2500nm, designed using TFCalc. 91

Figure 4. 10. Modelled optical transmittance of the WBPB filter for the NIR LVF at 1500, 2000 and 2500nm, designed using TFCalc. 92

Figure 4. 11. Modelled optical transmittance of the NIR LVF at 1500, 2000 and 2500nm, designed using TFCalc. 93

Figure 5. 1. Schematic of the Microdyn thin film deposition system. In the middle is a horizontal shaft, and sputtering targets are on both sides. A mechanical mask is between the target and the shaft, and the top microwave source facilitates an energetic reactive plasma for oxidation during the deposition process (Song et al., 2019). 94

Figure 5. 2. Conceptual diagram of thin film sputter deposition and sputter mask in the Microdyn (Li et al., 2017). 95

Figure 5. 3. Tracks left by the target after sputtering. 97

Figure 5. 4. Target erosion trajectory data measured using a depth gauge, shown as a quarter of the total size of the target. The upper part is the contour map, and the lower part is the depth map of the erosion track surface, in millimetres (Li et al., 2017). 97

Figure 5. 5. Mask on the chamber. 100

Figure 5. 6. Plot of equation 4.3 to obtain the simulation results for the thickness. $X_s=0$ mm is the middle position of the centreline of the drum plate. 101

Figure 5. 7. An example of the thickness averaging method, the film thickness is divided into several segments along the direction of the linear thickness gradient of the spot. 102

Figure 5. 8. Comparison of experimental and simulated results after thin film deposition using the mask. In this figure, the sample images are shown at the top, the thickness distribution graph measured by the experimental results of Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2 is in the middle position, and the thickness distribution results and experimental results comparison graph for SiO_2 are overlain at the bottom. 102

Figure 5. 9. The production flow chart of an LVF. 104

Figure 5. 10. 840.87 nm SiO_2 film on 858.31 nm Nb_2O_5 film on MS substrate. 104

Figure 5. 11. The LVF test data in the visible light band: (a) transmittance as a function of wavelength for different physical positions across the length of the LVF (b) Passband central wavelength as a function of physical position across the LVF. 105

Figure 5. 12. The LVF test data in the near infrared light band: (a) transmittance as a function of wavelength for different physical positions across the length of the LVF (b) Passband central wavelength as a function of physical position across the LVF. 105

Figure 6. 1. Internal view of NKD-8000 Aquila. 108

Figure 6. 2. Script program measurement flow for measuring LVF. 109

Figure 6. 3. Conceptual sample diagram (a) of BPF-type LVF and its theoretical spectral transmittance curve (b). 110

Figure 6. 4. When pbw is 0.75%, the design T_{max} value is 0.92, the simulated spectrum takes on the original square passband at each centre wavelength λ_c on the LVF (Zhou, Cai et al., 2021). 114

Figure 6. 5. When pbw is 0.75%, the design value of T_{max} is 0.92, and the result fits to the average effect of each central wavelength λ_c on the LVF using the Pearson VII distribution function (Zhou, Cai et al., 2021). 115

Figure 6. 6. When pbw is 0.835%, the LVF transmission spectrum using the Fabry-Perot cavity passband design, the simulation results of the average effect at each central wavelength λ_c (Zhou, Cai et al., 2021). 116

Figure 6. 7. Fitting of the LVF transmission data using Pearson VII function and modified Pearson VII function and comparing with actual measurement results (Zhou, Cai et al., 2021). 118

Figure 6. 8. When the incident light spot radius r is 0.4 mm, and the LVF sample is has a physical length of 44 mm, and the transmission measurement results are obtained at intervals of 4 mm. 119

Figure 6. 9. When the incident light spot radius r is 0.4 mm, the measured relationship between the centre wavelength of the transmission passband and the physical position of the LVF shows the linearity of the LVF (Zhou, Cai et al., 2021). 119

Figure 6. 10. The lateral uniformity data obtained when the measuring equipment's incident light spot radius r is 0.4 mm. (a) Transverse uniformity measurement at 2 mm intervals in the y-axis direction over a range of 20 mm, with a zoomed-in view of the top peak. (b) A plot of the central wavelength versus the physical position on the y-axis. 120

Figure 6. 11. Diagram of the steps in the method to start simulating the averaged results with a known peak profile. 121

Figure 6. 12. Results of the data used to validate the description of the LVF peak profile by mean effects (Zhou, Cai et al., 2021). 122

Figure 6. 13. Measured optical transmittance results for a 44 mm length LVF using a spot size of 1.5 mm, measured in increments of 4 mm along the length of the LVF. 123

Figure 6. 14. Extracted original profile of the measured passband at the centre of the LVF by using the modified Pearson VII function, Equation 4.6. (a) the extracted spectral profile using a beam spot size of 0.4 mm (b) the extracted spectral profile using a beam spot size of 1.5 mm (Zhou, Cai et al., 2021). 124

Figure 7. 1. The structure of a miniaturized spectrometer based on gear transmission.....	128
Figure 7. 2. Miniaturized spectrometer version 2, driven by a linear screw drive.	129
Figure 7. 3. Miniaturized spectrometer version 3, driven by a linear screw drive. A modular design was also introduced.	129
Figure 7. 4. Schematic diagram of the optical system structure.	130
Figure 7. 5. Building a CPC and its design principles (Tian et al., 2018).	131
Figure 7. 6. CPC (a) Image of a CPC (b) Design model mesh of the CPC optical surface. ...	131
Figure 7. 7. Thorlabs' F260SMA-A collimator.	132
Figure 7. 8. Photographs of (a) visible light (450 nm - 900 nm) LVF (b) near-infrared (1.5 μ m - 2.5 μ m) LVF.	132
Figure 7. 9. Image of the MSP430G2553 microcontroller development board.	133
Figure 7. 10. Nanotec's ST2018 stepper motor (a) Schematic diagram of ST2018 wiring diagram (b) Image of the ST2018.	134
Figure 7. 11. ST2018 stepper motor driver board DRV8835 (a) DRV8835 driver board schematic diagram (b) Image of DRV8835 driver development board.	135
Figure 7. 12. Flow chart of the working principle of the stepping motor and the driver board.	135
Figure 7. 13. Wave pattern of stepper motor operation (Carmine Fiore, 2022).	136
Figure 7. 14. Full-step mode of stepper motor operation (Carmine Fiore, 2022).	136
Figure 7. 15. Half-step mode of stepper motor operation (Carmine Fiore, 2022).	137
Figure 7. 16. Relationship between "High" and "Low" level signals and motor step angle.	137
Figure 7. 17 Rotation control signal of ST2018 stepper motor.	138
Figure 7. 18. 42 mm width stepping motor 17HS4401 physical picture.	138
Figure 7. 19. TB6600 stepper motor driver (a) TB6600 wiring diagram (b) Image of the TB6600 driver module.	139
Figure 7. 20. Image of BPW21R Silicon Photodiode detector in through-hole TO can package.	

.....	140
Figure 7. 21. Image of uncooled PB25S10104S type PbS detector in through-hole TO can package.	140
Figure 7. 22. MSP430G2553 MCU development board produced by TI.	141
Figure 7. 23. MFC program for controlling a miniaturized spectrometer.	146
Figure 7. 24. Using C++ programming, the main PC sends instructions to the lower computer to control the stepper motor to rotate a unit length.	147
Figure 7. 25. Some functions in the VISA library.	148
Figure 7. 26. The program connects the main PC and the multimeter.	148
Figure 8. 1. Image of the Anet A8 3D printer used to manufacture spectrometer chassis in this work.	150
Figure 8. 2. Miniaturized spectrometer model based on LVF (a) with the low torque ST2018 stepping motor gear transmission (b) with the low torque ST2018 stepping motor screw drive (c) with the high torque 17HS4401 stepping motor wire Lever transmission.	152
Figure 8. 3. Spectrometer version gear-driven LVF micro-spectrometer (a) The stepping motor moves from right to left (b) The stepping motor moves from left to right.	153
Figure 8. 4. Spectrometer version 2, lead screw drive type LVF micro-spectrometer (a) The stepper motor moves from left to the right, (b) moves from right to left.	154
Figure 8. 5. Image of the manufactured LVF miniaturised spectrometer, driven by gears... ..	157
Figure 8. 6. The data(10 layers Nb ₂ O ₅ and SiO ₂) measured by the gear-driven spectrometer version 1 LVF micro-spectrometer, the x-axis is the number of steps of the stepping motor, and the y-axis is the spectral transmittance.	158
Figure 8. 7. Comparison of data after measuring the same sample(10 layers Nb ₂ O ₅ and SiO ₂) using a geared LVF model and a Scalar spectrometer.	158
Figure 8. 8. LVF miniaturized spectrometer with screw drive (a) Small motor spectrometer version 2 and (b) Large motor spectrometer version 3.	159

Figure 8. 9. The data comparison of Nb₂O₅ single-layer film measured by the LVF miniaturized spectrometer driven by the lead screw and the Lambda 40 standard benchtop spectrometer. 160

Figure 8. 10. The test data (10 layers Nb₂O₅ and SiO₂) of the LVF miniaturized spectrometer driven by the gear transmission and the lead screw are compared with the Scalar measurement data. 160

List of Tables

Table 1.1. Design indicators of system performance parameters of LVF spectrometer in the visible light band.....	23
Table 1.2. Design indicators of system performance parameters of near-infrared band LVF spectrometer.....	23
Table 6. 1. Specific characteristic parameters of the visible LVF produced in this work. ...	125
Table 8. 1.. Gearing moves from motor left to right.....	153
Table 8. 2 . Gearing moves from right to left of motor.....	154
Table 8. 3. The screw drive moves from the right to the left of the motor.....	155
Table 8. 4. Screw drive moves from motor left to right.....	155

Table of Contents

Abstract	1
Declaration by candidate	3
Acknowledgement	4
List of Symbols and Abbreviations	5
List of Figures	8
List of Tables	16
Table of Contents	17
Chapter 1 Introduction	22
1.1 Motivation & Background	22
1.2 Thesis Innovations	24
1.3 Outline of Thesis	25
Chapter 2 Literature Review	27
2.1 Optical Filter	28
2.1.1 The principle of the optical filter	28
2.1.2 Classification of Optical Filters	33
2.1.3 Optical Filter-Linear Variable Bandpass Filter (LVF)	41
2.2 Classic Spectrometer	44
2.2.1 Classical Dispersive Spectrometer	45
2.2.2 Modulation Conversion Spectrometer	48
2.3 Miniaturized Near Infrared Spectrometer	50
2.3.1 The Principle of Near Infrared Spectrometer	51
2.3.2 The History of Infrared Spectrometers and Their Miniaturization	53
2.3.3 Classification of Near Infrared Miniature Spectrometers	53

Chapter 3 Experiment.....	58
3.1 Equipment of Thin Film Deposition for my research: Microdyn	58
3.2 Introduction to the Microdyn components and their principles of operation	61
3.2.1 Pumping System	61
3.2.2 The Polycold Cryochiller	61
3.2.3 MDX Power Supply	62
3.2.4 Sparc-le V Pulsing Unit	62
3.2.5 IC/5 (A Thin Film Deposition Controller)	63
3.2.6 Microwave Magnetron Power Supply	64
3.2.7 Vacuum Gauge Measurement and Control System	65
3.2.8 MKS-Mass Flow Controllers	66
3.2.9 OGC-1 Partial Pressure Controller	66
3.3 Process Flow for the Microdyn Thin Film Deposition	69
3.4 Sample Measurement and Sample Calibration for Spectrometer	72
3.4.1 Aquila NKD-8000	73
3.4.2 Perkin Elmer Lambda 40	74
3.4.3 Nicolet iS50 FTIR	75
3.5 Summary	76
Chapter 4 Design of Linear Variable Filter (LVF).....	77
4.1 Introduction.....	77
4.2 Material Selection for Linear Variable Filter Fabrication	78
4.2.1 Selection of LVF substrate material	78
4.2.2 Selection of LVF film materials	81
4.3 Design of Linear Variable Filter	82

4.3.1 The basic design concept of LVF	82
4.3.2 Design Process of an LVF	84
4.3.3 Design of Visible and Near Infrared LVFs	86
4.4 Summary	93
Chapter 5 Fabrication of Linear Variable Filters	94
5.1 Introduction	94
5.2 LVF Thickness Uniformity Distribution Modelling and Mask Template Design	95
5.2.1 Target sputtering yield and sputtering angle	96
5.2.2 Film Thickness Simulation of Magnetron Sputtering with Mask	99
5.2.3 Experimental results of Mask design	100
5.3 LVF production and results	103
5.4 Summary	106
Chapter 6 Characterization of Linear Variable Filter	107
6.1 Introduction	107
6.2 Equipment for measuring LVFs and Script Automated Measurement Program	107
6.2.1 Equipment for measuring LVFs	107
6.2.2 Script Automated Measurement Program	109
6.3 Parameters for evaluating and characterizing LVF properties	110
6.3.1 Spatial gradient of LVF	110
6.3.2 Linearity of LVF spatial gradient	111
6.3.3 Passband bandwidth of LVF	111
6.3.4 Transverse Uniformity of LVF	112
6.4 Simulation of the effect of beam spot sizes on the optical transmittance	112
6.5 Actual measurement results and analysis	117
6.5.1 Measurement of an LVF under relatively small incident spot size	117

6.5.2 Fitting the peak profile of the LVF using the averaging effect	121
6.6 Summary	124
Chapter 7 The Fabrication of a Miniature Spectrometer	127
7.1 Structure and principle of Miniature spectrometer	127
7.1.1 System structure of micro spectrometer	127
7.1.2 Optical System Module	130
7.1.3 Core device linear variable filter	132
7.1.4 Control Systems and Detectors	132
7.2 Control system design and interface program	141
7.2.1 MSP430 MCU and IDE Introduction	141
7.2.2 Programming of MCU	142
7.2.3 The interface control system on Windows	145
7.3 Summary	148
Chapter 8 Experimental Process and results analysis	150
8.1 Miniature spectrometer model manufacturing	150
8.2 System connection and debugging	151
8.3 Experimental test results	156
8.3.1 Measurement results of a gear-driven miniaturized spectrometer	156
8.3.2 Measurement results of miniaturized spectrometer driven by lead screw	159
8.4 Summary	161
Chapter 9 Summary and Suggestions for Future Work	163
9.1 Summary of the work and results	163
9.1.1 Summary of Results	163
9.1.2 Summary of Innovation	164
9.2 Prospects for Future Work	165

Appendix 1: History of thin film manufacturing technology and processes	168
Appendix 2: Summary of Thin film deposition technology	177
Appendix 3: Software	199
List of publications	203
References	204

Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation & Background

Most traditional spectrometers use large-volume diffraction gratings as the dispersive component (Siesler et al., 2008). While such a structure makes the traditional spectrometer highly accurate in measurement and provides good stability, it also limits the size of the spectrometer, making it difficult to create portable or mobile devices. In addition, the complicated internal design uses additional mirrors and lenses, making them expensive.

To promote innovation and advancement in spectrometer technology the miniaturization of spectrometers is technologically important. The ideal requirements for such a device include being small in size, lightweight, easy to carry and operate, capable of remote control and real-time monitoring, and applicable to agricultural production, chemical analysis, environmental monitoring, industrial testing, biomedicine, and optical communication (Emadi, Wu, de Graaf and Wolffenbuttel, 2012b; O'Brien et al., 2012a; Wiesent, Dorigo and Koch, 2013; Song et al., 2020).

The following are some common application scenarios of miniaturized spectrometers:

In chemical analysis, miniaturized spectrometers can be used to analyse the composition and structure of substances, such as identifying different chemicals, drugs, foods, etc. High precision and fast response makes the miniaturized spectrometer an important tool for chemical analysis.

In the field of biomedicine, miniaturized spectrometers can also be used for the analysis of body fluids and the detection of cell components.

In environmental monitoring, miniaturized spectrometers can monitor environmental parameters such as air, water quality and soil. Those correspond to atmospheric pollutants, nutrients and harmful substances in water, etc. Its portability and real-time performance are important for environmental monitoring.

In industrial testing, miniaturized spectrometers can be used to test the composition and quality of steel, plastic, rubber and other materials. Miniaturized spectrometers can be implemented on the production line in real-time, improving production efficiency and quality.

In the field of biological spectroscopy, miniaturized spectrometers can be used in protein structure research, DNA sequencing, etc. High sensitivity, and high resolution make the miniaturized spectrometer an important tool for biological spectroscopy research.

In the field of optical communication, miniaturized spectrometers can be used in signal detection and demodulation in optical fibre communication. High speed and high precision make the miniaturized spectrometer an important tool for optical communication.

The main purpose of this work is to research, develop and manufacture new miniaturized spectrometer based on a so-called linear variable filter (LVF) replacing the diffraction grating. Based on extensive research into the impact on spectrometer application conditions of the spectral characteristics of the LVF, a miniaturized spectrometer design utilizing LVFs for detecting material spectra has been developed. The spectral ranges of the designed LVFs were selected to span the desirable visible light (450 nm - 900 nm) and near-infrared light (1.5 μm - 2.5 μm) wavelength ranges.

The performance parameter design indicators of the spectrometer systems designed in this research are shown in the following tables 1.1 and 1.2:

Table 1.1. Design indicators of system performance parameters of LVF spectrometer in the visible light band.

Working Spectrum Wavelength Range	450 nm - 900 nm
Spectral Resolution	≤ 5 nm
Spectrometer Volume after Integrating	$\leq 230 \times 90 \times 70$ mm
Signal-to-noise Ratio	1000:1
Integration Time	< 100 ms

Table 1.2. Design indicators of system performance parameters of near-infrared band LVF spectrometer.

Working Spectrum Wavelength Range	1.5 μm - 2.5 μm
Spectral Resolution	≤ 5 nm
Spectrometer Volume after Integrating	$\leq 230 \times 90 \times 70$ mm
Signal-to-noise Ratio	1000:1
Integration Time	< 100 ms

1.2 Thesis Innovations

This thesis describes the development of a miniaturized spectrometer based on a novel LVF approach for the visible and near-infrared bands. The main content includes the verification of the principle of the micro-spectrometer and the construction of the spectrometer system structure based on the LVF core. The principle part includes the description of the LVF manufacturing process, the introduction of the working principle of an LVF, the introduction of the new micro-spectrometer based on an LVF, and the introduction of the signal processing principle.

The innovations of this research are:

1) A new method of LVF manufacturing, based on a unique drum-based microwave- assisted magnetron sputtering system using metal targets to form highly transparent metal oxide films. The advantages of this drum-based sputtering are firstly the deposited film thickness is normally uniform along the entire circumference of the drum, and a scissors-like mask can be used to form the necessary gradient in the coating thickness. Secondly, the regions of sputtering and microwave-assisted oxidation are separated which avoids poisoning of the targets and increases the deposition rate. The new method used in this paper is faster, simpler, and is suitable for a large batch of production. The deposition time for LVF using drum-based sputter is much shorter than previously reported methods, such as the ion beam sputtering method used by Lemarquis et al (Lemarquis, Abel-Tiberini and Koc, 2010).

2) A different approach to optical filter design. Lemarquis et al used a combination of short and long wavelength pass filter to form a linear variable band pass filter. In contrast, in our design we used a narrow band pass filter and wide band pass filter approach deposited on opposite sides of glass substrates.

3) The development of a miniaturized spectrometer system with a single-chip microcontroller unit (MCU), processing the circuit signal, and compiling the interface control software. The main innovation here is the control of the stepper motor with the MCU such that the spatial position of the core component LVF varies uniformly along one direction. Combined with a previously designed optical system, the light beam is collimated through the optical path, then passes through the sample and the LVF. Finally, a photodetector detects the light that passes

through the LVF to complete the data measurement.

1.3 Outline of Thesis

Chapter 1 is an introduction to this dissertation. In this chapter, the author primarily introduces the motivation, background, and innovative points of this article, and provides an overview of the contents.

Chapter 2 is a review of the scientific background to this dissertation. In this chapter, the classification of optical filters and their principles are introduced, the principles and history of linear variable filters (LVF) are highlighted, and the development of miniature spectrometers is introduced. Historical and existing taxonomy relating to the research background and significance of this work is discussed .

Chapter 3 introduces the technical principles and components of the Microdyn, the thin film deposition equipment used in this thesis, and introduces several kinds of thin film characterization equipment that were used to analyse the experimental results.

Chapter 4 introduces the principle and design process of the LVF. Firstly, the substrate and film materials required for LVF production are selected, and then the design process of the LVF is explained. Finally, the software (TFCalc) design results of an LVF for the visible and near-infrared bands are introduced.

Chapter 5 discusses in detail the film manufacturing process of the LVF. First, the film thickness uniformity distribution model of LVF is introduced. Then, the mask design process needed for thin film deposition is introduced. Finally, the products and measurement results of the LVF are presented.

Chapter 6 introduces the detailed testing and characterization process of the LVF. Firstly, the Aquila NKD-8000 measurement equipment is introduced. The measurement process involves characterizing the optical performance of the LVF, as well as conducting a simulation to demonstrate how the spot size of the test beam affects the measurement results. Finally, the measurement results are analysed, and the data analysis takes into account the average effect.

Chapter 7 introduces the fabrication of the opto-mechanical components of the miniature spectrometer. Firstly, the overall structural design of the miniature spectrometer is introduced. Next, the optical path and circuit design of the spectrometer are introduced. Finally, the

design and compilation of the graphical user interface are introduced.

Chapter 8 builds on the findings of the previous chapters and demonstrates the practical use of the finalised miniaturized spectrometer to measure some fabricated optical thin film samples. The experimental results are compared with those from a commercial lab-scale spectrometer.

Chapter 9 is an overall summary of the work in this thesis, including the design approach for the LVF samples made in this work and the miniaturized spectrometer prototypes constructed with the LVFs manufactured with our Microdyn deposition system. The advantages and disadvantages of LVF based spectrometers are analysed and future prospects and a plan for future work is formulated.

Appendix 1 provides a detailed history of thin film manufacturing technology and processes.

Appendix 2 is a detailed summary of thin film deposition technology.

Appendix 3 provides details of the software and control system design.

Chapter 2 Literature Review

A spectrometer is a scientific instrument that can measure the spectral absorption features of chemical substances and facilitate their identification. It can separate light of different wavelengths and measure its intensity and energy at different wavelengths. Different substances' chemical and physical properties are studied by analysing the spectral information obtained from the measurement. Therefore, the spectrum can be described as the "fingerprint" of different substances. Spectrometers are widely used and have important applications in agriculture, biology, chemistry, optics, optoelectronics, material science, medicine, the thin film industry, the semiconductor industry, component detection and other fields.

Traditional spectrometers are usually large, require large optical elements and mechanical structures, and require a long optical path length when dispersing light. In addition, they have high resolution and precision. Traditional spectrometers are expensive, often requiring sophisticated optics and electronic control systems. The maintenance cost of traditional spectrometers is also relatively high. Due to the complex optical and mechanical structures, professionals require regular upkeep and maintenance. Therefore, the miniaturization and cost reduction of spectrometers has become an important development direction.

The miniaturized spectrometer described here is centred around a linear variable filter. Linear variable filter (LVF) spectral imaging technology has the advantages of a compact system and simple structure compared with traditional grating, prism spectroscopic and interference spectroscopic techniques. The production of the core component LVF is inseparable from the manufacturing technology of the film.

In this chapter, the core component of the miniaturized spectrometer in this paper is firstly introduced. The development history of the thin film deposition technology used to manufacture the LVF is introduced in Appendix 1, and a summary of thin film deposition technology is presented in Appendix 2. Then the principle of an optical filter and several classic optical filters are introduced and the main principle and development history of the core component LVF is discussed. Finally, the principle of visible and near-infrared spectroscopy, its historical development process and classification after miniaturization are introduced.

2.1 Optical Filter

This section briefly introduces the history and classification of optical filters and mainly introduces the LVF that is the focus of this work.

2.1.1 The principle of the optical filter

An optical filter is a device that selectively transmits or blocks light of a certain wavelength or range (Choudhury, 2014). Optical filters are commonly used in microscopy, spectroscopy, chemical analysis, and machine vision (Macleod, 1986).

The essence of light as an electromagnetic wave was introduced by James Clerk Maxwell (Maxwell, 1873). Electromagnetic waves are arranged in the order of wavelength and frequency to form the electromagnetic spectrum, as shown in Figure 2.1 (Nikolov, 2016). The range of light waves is about 1 mm -10 nm, and electromagnetic waves with wavelengths between 380 nm and 760 nm can be seen by people and constitute the visible light band. Light with a wavelength greater than 760 nm is called infrared light, while light with a wavelength less than 400 nm is called ultraviolet light. The speed of light waves propagating in a vacuum is about $c \approx 2.99792458 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}$, and the speed of propagation in medium is smaller than that in vacuum, and is generally a function of wavelength (Macleod, 1986; Peatross and Michael, 2015).

Figure 2. 1. The electromagnetic spectrum (Nikolov, 2016).

Visible light with different wavelengths appears as different colours to human eyes (Peatross and Michael, 2015). Generally, light with a single wavelength is called monochromatic light,

and light containing multiple wavelengths is called polychromatic light. One of the simplest applications of optical filters is to filter polychromatic light, passing only the light of the required wavelengths (Macleod, 1986).

Sunlight is composed of a continuum of monochromatic light. In the visible light, the decomposition of sunlight can be recognised in the rainbow's seven colours: red, orange, yellow, green, blue, indigo and violet (Macleod, 1986; Peatross and Michael, 2015).

Optical filters can be distinguished according to the band of the spectrum, which can be divided into ultraviolet (180 nm - 400 nm), visible light (400 nm - 700 nm), near-infrared (700 nm - 3000 nm), infrared (3000 nm - 10 μm) and far infrared filters (above 10 μm).

Optical thin films are solid thin film materials that can produce light interference phenomena on optical components or independent substrates (Macleod, 1986). Light propagation in a medium is based on the classical theory of electromagnetic wave propagation (Madsen and Zhao, 1999, p. 19). The theoretical and technical basis for thin-film design is based on Maxwell's equations (Maxwell, 1873), as shown in Equation 2.1. For isotropic media, Maxwell's equations (Maxwell, 1873) are:

$$\begin{cases} \nabla \cdot \vec{D} = \rho \\ \nabla \times \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \\ \nabla \times \vec{H} = \vec{j} + \vec{j}_D \\ \nabla \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

In the above formula 2.1, \vec{D} is the electric displacement vector, \vec{E} is the electric field intensity vector, \vec{H} is the magnetic field intensity vector, \vec{B} is the magnetic induction intensity vector, \vec{j} and \vec{j}_D are conduction current density vector and displacement current density vector ($j_D = \frac{\partial D}{\partial t}$), and ρ is the bulk charge density.

In addition, since the electromagnetic field is excited by moving charges, the influence of the medium on the electromagnetic fields also needs to be considered. The set of equations in 2.2, describe the influence of the medium,

$$\begin{cases} \vec{D} = \varepsilon \vec{E} \\ \vec{B} = \mu \vec{H} \\ \vec{j} = \sigma \vec{E} \end{cases} \quad (2.2)$$

where ε is the absolute dielectric constant of the medium, μ is the absolute magnetic

permeability of the medium, and σ is the electrical conductivity of the medium.

Bringing the density vector j_D of the displacement current into the above formula 2.1 and combining it with 2.2, and assuming a space without net charge ($\nabla \cdot \vec{E} = 0$), the following formula 2.3 can be obtained, which means that the electromagnetic disturbance propagates in the medium following a wave equation;

$$\nabla^2 \vec{E} = \mu \varepsilon \frac{\partial^2 \vec{E}}{\partial t^2} + \mu \sigma \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} \quad (2.3)$$

For a plane wave propagating in the positive x-direction (Cartesian coordinate system), a solution such as Equation 2.4 can be obtained, where ω is the angular frequency of the plane wave, v is the propagation velocity in the medium, and \vec{E} is the amplitude of the electric field;

$$\vec{E} = \vec{E}_0 \exp \left[i \omega \left(t - \frac{x}{v} \right) \right] \quad (2.4)$$

Substituting Equation 2.4 into Equation 2.3, solutions of the form (2.5) can be obtained.

$$\vec{E} = \vec{E}_0 \exp \left[i \left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi N x}{\lambda} \right) \right] \quad (2.5)$$

Provided

$$N^2 = \frac{(\varepsilon \mu - i \frac{\sigma \mu}{\omega})}{\varepsilon_0 \mu_0} \quad (2.6)$$

Where $N^2 = n^2 - k^2 = \varepsilon_r \mu_r$, ε_r is the relative permittivity of the medium, μ_r is the magnetic permeability of general optical materials, ε_0 is the magnetic permeability in vacuum and μ_0 is the permittivity in vacuum, c is the speed of electromagnetic waves in vacuum, v is the speed of electromagnetic waves in non-conductive media and λ is the wavelength of a monochromatic plane wave propagating along the positive x direction.

$N = \frac{c}{v} = n - ik$, is identified as the complex refractive index, where n is the real part of the refractive index of the medium, and κ is the extinction coefficient.

Substituting the complex refractive index into equation 2.5 yields equation 2.7,

$$\vec{E} = \vec{E}_0 \exp \left(-\frac{2\pi \kappa x}{\lambda} \right) \exp \left[i \left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi n x}{\lambda} \right) \right] \quad (2.7)$$

Equation 2.7 shows that the electromagnetic wave in a conductive medium (the conductivity σ is not zero, so the extinction coefficient κ is not zero) is a wave that decays gradually. The

extinction coefficient κ measures the absorption of electromagnetic energy by a medium. After propagating through $x = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi\kappa}$, the amplitude of the wave will decay to the initial $\frac{1}{e}$. The quantity $n\lambda$ in Equation 2.7 is known as the optical thickness in the film design.

The study of optical thin film filters involves the propagation characteristics of light travelling through multiple layers. Figure 2.2. shows a wave travelling along the z axis and incident on a single boundary between two media. Here, n_i is the refractive index of the medium containing the incident wave-front, and n_t is the refractive index of the second medium. The incident wave is divided into two parts at the interface, one part is a reflected wave, and the other part is a transmitted wave and refracted wave.

Figure 2. 2. Principle of reflection (Peatross and Michael, 2015).

When light waves propagate from one medium to another, reflection and refraction occur at the interface between the two media, and the laws of reflection and refraction hold (Peatross and Michael, 2015). The amplitude-energy relationship between the incident reflected and refracted light can be expressed by Fresnel's formula (Macleod, 1986, pp. 15–30) derived from Maxwell's equations:

When $J_s = 0$; $u_r = 1$ (Assuming that there is no conduction current on the interface, the magnetic permeability of the optical material is approximately equal to 1),

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

$$\begin{aligned}
r_s &= \frac{n_1 \cos(\theta_i) - n_2 \cos(\theta_t)}{n_1 \cos(\theta_i) + n_2 \cos(\theta_t)} \\
t_s &= \frac{2n_1 \cos(\theta_i)}{n_1 \cos(\theta_i) + n_2 \cos(\theta_t)} \\
r_p &= \frac{n_2 \cos(\theta_i) - n_1 \cos(\theta_t)}{n_2 \cos(\theta_i) + n_1 \cos(\theta_t)} \\
t_p &= \frac{2n_1 \cos(\theta_i)}{n_2 \cos(\theta_i) + n_1 \cos(\theta_t)}
\end{aligned}
\tag{2.8}$$

in this set of equations (equation 2.8), r is the amplitude reflection coefficient (Fresnel reflection coefficient), t is the amplitude transmission coefficient (Fresnel transmission coefficient), the subscripts s and p represent the s-polarized wave and p - polarized wave, and θ_i is the incident angle, θ_t is the refraction angle. Through equation 2.8, the basic relationship between the amplitude of incident light waves, reflected light waves, and refracted light waves can be calculated.

Figure 2. 3. (a) Monolayer film (Macleod, 1986, p. 5) (b) Multilayer film.

In Figure 2.3, 2.3(a) is a schematic diagram of a single-layer film structure, and 2.3(b) is a schematic diagram of a multilayer film system with k layers. In Figure 2.3(b), θ_0 is the incident angle, θ_{k+1} is the outgoing angle, and θ_r is angle of incidence at the r^{th} layer of the of the film. n_0 is the refractive index of the incident medium, and n_{sub} is the refractive index of the substrate, that is the outgoing medium. d_1, d_2, \dots, d_k respectively correspond to the film thickness of the layers.

For a thin-film system with multiple layers, the method of choice in thin film design software is the so-called matrix method, allowing very rapid calculations due to the advancement of computer technology.

In the thin-film system in Figure 2.3(b), with light incident at a non zero angle in the y - z

plane it is convenient to introduce an effective admittance η , using η_r instead of n_r to characterise the media at the oblique incidence. It is only necessary to consider two cases:-

(1) When the incident electric field intensity E is within (parallel to) the y-z plane, this wave is called a *TM* wave (transverse magnetic wave) or a *p* - polarized wave;

(2) When the incident electric field intensity E is perpendicular to the y-z plane, this wave is called a *TE* wave (transverse electric wave) or an *s* - polarized wave.

The optical characteristics of the combined k-layer thin-film system can then be expressed by the multiplication of the characteristics of each layer, and a resultant characteristic matrix obtained as follows: 2.9:

$$M_k = \prod_{r=1}^k \begin{bmatrix} \cos \delta_r & \frac{j \sin \delta_r}{n_r} \\ j\eta_r \sin \delta_r & \cos \delta_r \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_k & jB_k \\ jC_k & D_k \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.9)$$

In formula 2.10, where ϑ_r is the phase thickness of the rth layer, n_r is the refractive index of the rth layer. For both p-polarized and s-polarized waves, the phase thickness of the film is as follows:

$$\delta_r = \frac{2\pi n_r d_r \cos \vartheta_r}{\lambda_r} \quad (2.10)$$

The angle of refraction θ_r is determined by Snell's law of refraction and η_r is given by:

$$\eta_r = \begin{cases} n_r / \cos \theta_r & p - \text{polarized} \\ n_r \cos \theta_r & s - \text{polarized} \end{cases}$$

η_0 is the admittance of the incident medium, η_{sub} is the admittance of the exiting medium. If the substrate is itself semi-infinite (i.e. there is no returning reflected wave) the reflectivity R of the complete multilayer can be expressed by the following formula 2.11:

$$R = \frac{(\eta_0 A_k - \eta_{sub} D_k)^2 + (\eta_0 \eta_{sub} B_k - C_k)^2}{(\eta_0 A_k + \eta_{sub} D_k)^2 + (\eta_0 \eta_{sub} B_k + C_k)^2} \quad (2.11)$$

The transmittance T can be expressed as the following formula 2.12:

$$T = \frac{4\eta_0 \eta_{sub}}{(\eta_0 A_k + \eta_{sub} D_k)^2 + (\eta_0 \eta_{sub} B_k + C_k)^2} \quad (2.12)$$

2.1.2 Classification of Optical Filters

Macleod divides optical filters into antireflection coating filter, neutral mirrors, beam splitters, highly reflective coating filter, edge filter, and bandpass filter in his classic book "*Thin Film*

Optical Filters” (Macleod, 1986). Among them, the edge cut-off filter and band-pass filter are key for this work, and the detailed designs will be introduced in Chapter 4.

Anti-Reflection Coatings Filter

The first anti-reflection film was discovered by Lord Rayleigh (Poitras and Dobrowolski, 2004) in 1880, but that was just due to the etching of the surface over time in the environment. Interference-based thin film deposition was invented in 1935 by Smakula (Smakula, 1935), who worked for the optical company Carl Zeiss. The invention of this technology greatly promoted the early development of thin film optics, and antireflection films still play a vital role in all-optical thin films today.

When a ray of light passes from a medium with a refractive index of n_i to another medium with a refractive index of n_t , and there is no absorption in the medium, the surface is an optical surface, and the light is at normal incidence, then the reflectivity R is simply:

$$R = \left(\frac{n_i - n_t}{n_i + n_t} \right)^2 \quad (2.13)$$

The transmittance is $T=1-R$ in the case of no optical absorption.

On the surface of uncoated crown glass, such as the commonly used BK7 glass material, the refractive index at 550 nm is about 1.52, which means that about 4.26% of the incident light in the entire visible spectrum will be reflected, with additional reflectance at the rear surface (Macleod, 1986). Multiple reflections in a camera or imaging lens will lead to a loss of light energy and the reduction of intensity at the film/sensor; it will also cause image ghosting, affecting the contrast quality of the imaging system. In particular, complex systems such as televisions and movie cameras, which contain multiple lens surfaces, cannot be used without anti-reflection coatings (Macleod, 1986; Jinfa *et al.*, 2006).

In order to reduce the situation of surface reflection, the simplest method is to coat a layer of film on the glass surface with a lower refractive index than the glass. Ideally, the film thickness of this single-layer anti-reflection coating has an optical thickness of $\lambda/4$, where lambda is the wavelength of the incident light, and its refractive index is the square root of the product of the incident medium and the substrate refractive index. Ideally for an air/glass interface this requires a film with index 1.22, which is not realisable. In practice, a magnesium fluoride film with a refractive index of 1.38 is deposited on crown glass with a

refractive index of 1.52. After coating, the reflectance of the central wavelength is reduced from 4.2% to about 1.3%, and the average reflectance over the entire visible light region is about 1.5% (Macleod, 1986).

The production of single-layer anti-reflection films was a major progress in history. But it still has some flaws. Firstly, the residual reflection is still too high for most applications. Secondly, the light reflected by the anti-reflection coating destroys part of the colour balance. These defects were overcome with the emergence of double-layer or even multi-layer anti-reflection film technology. Although the design is more complicated, the reflection effect is more suitable for the required use (Macleod, 1986).

At present, many different types of special anti-reflection films have been developed to meet the needs of different situations. However, complex optical systems and laser optics have even higher requirements for anti-reflection performance. Therefore, the development of anti-reflection coating designs is ongoing.

Neutral Beam Splitters

A beam splitter is a device that splits a beam of light into two parts. The beam splitter is usually used at an oblique angle, which can more conveniently separate the incident light into reflected light and transmitted light. If the reflected light and transmitted light after splitting have different spectral components or have different colours, this kind of beam splitter is called a dichroic mirror, which will be introduced in the cut filter. This section mainly considers the neutral beam splitter. Neutral means that the two beams to be split have the same spectral composition. The most used is the neutral beam splitter with a transmission and reflectance ratio of 1:1 (Macleod, 1986).

Commonly used beam splitters have two structures, as shown in Figure 2.4. One of the structures (a) is depositing the film layer on a transparent flat plate called a flat beam splitter. Another structure (b) is to deposit the film layer on the slope of a 45° right-angle prism and then glue a similar prism, and the final cubic structure is called a glued cube beam splitter (Macleod, 1986). Plate beam splitters are commonly used for simple optical setups, while cemented cube beam splitters are commonly used for more demanding optical systems. In contrast, the glued cube beam splitter is easier to store and use because the film layer is not exposed to the air, but its polarization effect is larger (Macleod, 1986).

Figure 2. 4. Structures of two beam splitters (Macleod, 1986).

Beam splitters are further divided into metal film beam splitters, dielectric film beam splitters and polarizing beam splitters. The disadvantage of the metal film beam splitter is that the absorption loss is large, and the light splitting efficiency is low. For the metal film beam splitter, due to the absorption in the film layer, the light's incident angle will greatly influence the beam splitter's reflectivity. Just because the absorption loss of the beam splitter has a great relationship with the environmental medium around the beam-splitting film, the dielectric film beam splitter came into being by changing the surrounding medium to reduce the absorption loss. Compared with the metal film beam splitter, the dielectric film beam splitter has negligible absorption and higher light-splitting efficiency. However, it is more sensitive to wavelength, it is more difficult to split the beam neutrally, and the polarization effect of the dielectric film is also greater. The polarizing beam splitter that appears due to the polarization effect uses the polarization of light to achieve 1:1 neutral light splitting. Its principle is that the interface n_1/n_2 of two media with different refractive indices, when the incident angle satisfies the Brewster angle condition, $\tan \theta_1 = n_1/n_2$. P-polarized light has zero reflectivity, while s-polarized light is partially reflected and transmitted (Macleod, 1986). For general dielectric film beam splitters, the p-polarised component's reflectivity is generally lower than that of the s-polarized component. This polarization effect is more pronounced in cube beam splitters, so in some cases, only metal-coated beam splitters can be used.

Highly Reflective Coating

As the name suggests, the function of the high-reflective film is to increase the reflectivity of the main part of the incident light. Higher reflectivity is required in many applications, and a

small number of applications require high reflectivity and lower absorptivity simultaneously. Highly reflective films can be divided into metal reflective films, multi-layer dielectric high reflective films and non-equal thickness periodic film systems by different film designs and materials (Macleod, 1986).

Metal reflective films generally appear in the form of mirrors. Commonly used metal film materials include Al, Ag, Au, etc. Their spectral reflectance curves are shown in Figure 2.5 (Macleod, 1986). Since most metal films are soft and easily damaged, a protective film is often coated on the outer layer of the metal film. That can increase the strength and protect the metal film from being corrupted by the atmosphere. However, after the protective film is coated, the reflectivity of the mirror will decrease, and the higher the refractive index of the protective film, the more the reflectivity will decrease.

Figure 2. 5. Reflectance curves of metal reflective films of different materials (Hass, 1955; Macleod, 1986).

Metallic reflective films have large absorption losses, and in some applications, higher reflectivity and as little absorption as possible are required. The multi-layer dielectric high-reflection film can obtain higher reflectance by using alternating high and low refractive index films, with an optical thickness of $\lambda_0/4$ per layer. That is because the light beam reflected from the structure of the thin film system has the same phase when it returns to the front surface, resulting in constructive interference, and the reflectivity is very close to 100% in theory. Generally, a reflective film structure in which the outermost layer is a high refractive index film layer is used to obtain high reflectivity and low loss (Macleod, 1986).

A feature of periodic thin film systems with alternate high and low indices, n_h and n_l of thicknesses d_h and d_l are high reflection and low transmission bands. The necessary conditions for a high reflection band to appear are:

$$n_h d_h + n_l d_l = q \frac{\lambda_0}{2} \quad (2.14)$$

Meaning that the sum of the optical thicknesses of the layers in the fundamental period is an integer multiple, q , of $1/2$ of the central wavelength, λ_0 . However, when the optical thickness of each individual layer happens to be an integer multiple of $1/2$ of λ_0 , each layer of film will act as a ‘dummy’ (non-existent) layer, and the result will be high transmittance. Therefore, the centre wavelength of each reflection band can be determined by using Equation 1.14 and ignoring those wavelengths that make each layer a dummy layer (Macleod, 1986).

Edge Filter

Edge filters pass wavelengths above or below a cut-off wavelength. Edge filters are generally divided into two categories, long-pass and short-pass. A filter that suppresses the short-wave region and transmits the long-wave region is called a long-wave pass filter. On the contrary, the filter that suppresses the long-wave region and transmits the short-wave region is called a short-wave pass filter. The principle is shown in Figure 2.6, which shows the typical characteristics of long-pass and short-pass filters (Jinfa *et al.*, 2006).

Figure 2. 6. Principle of long-wave and short-wave pass filters: (a) long-wave pass filter, (b) short-wave pass filter (Jinfa et al., 2006).

The cut-off wavelength and the slope of the curve are important characteristic parameters of the filter. In addition, there is the spectral width, average transmission, and minimum transmission within the transmission band in the high transmission region, the spectral width

in the reflection region and the maximum transmission in this range.

Bandpass Filter

A bandpass filter is a device that only transmits a specific range or band of wavelengths and suppresses other wavelength ranges. The bandwidth of a band-pass filter is characterised by the wavelength range it allows to pass. Generally, a band-pass filter is a combination of a low pass filter and a high pass filter (Macleod, 1986). However, for filters with narrow bandpass requirements, combining long and short passes is unsuitable. Generally, a film with both pass and suppression band functions is used. The simplest and most commonly used is the Fabry-Perot band pass (FPBP) type thin-film filter, which is a peripheral product of the Fabry-Perot type optical resonant cavity first invented by Charles Fabry and Alfred Perot in 1897 (Vaughan, 2017).

Figure 2. 7. (a) Fabry-Perot standard device and its thin film device; (b) Spectral transmission characteristic diagram of Fabry-Perot type filter(Macleod, 1986, p. 180).

The simplest thin-film narrow-bandpass filter is based on the Fabry-Perot multi-beam interferometer. The structure of the Fabry-Perot type beam interferometer originally designed by Fabry and Perot in 1899 (Vaughan, 2017) comprises two identical parallel high reflectors separated by an air gap of d . The parallelism requirement is very high, as shown in Figure 2.7(a) (Macleod, 1986, p. 180). In this structure, when parallel light is incident, only a series of narrow transmission bands separated by equal wavenumber intervals can transmit light, and the rest of the transmittance is very low. Afterwards, with the development of technology, this structure was replaced by a thin-film combination of a dielectric layer sandwiched

between two metal layers, with the dielectric ‘spacer’ layer replacing the air gap. The characteristic analysis of this thin film filter is basically the same as the commonly used Fabry-Perot type structure, only the spacer layer has a refractive index greater than 1. Figure 2.7(b) shows the characteristics of the Fabry-Perot type filter. Among them, the parameters generally used to characterize the filter include the central wavelength λ_0 , the transmittance T_{MAX} of the central wavelength, the wavelength width $2\Delta\lambda$ of half the peak transmittance, and the relative half-width $2\Delta\lambda/\lambda_0$.

When designing and manufacturing Fabry-Perot type optical filters, asymmetry in the reflectance of the two metal film layers will produce errors and affect the performance. Any asymmetry error will affect the peak transmittance of the Fabry-Perot filter, but the impact is not serious. Even when the residual transmittance of the reflective films differs by a factor of two, a peak transmittance of 75% can still be obtained. The half-width passband of the Fabry-Perot filter depends on the interference order and the reflectivity of the reflective film. In general, the lower the reflectivity of the reflective film, the better the monochromaticity of the light transmitted by the filter, the higher the reflectivity, and the higher the interference order.

Due to the large absorption loss of metal films, they can only be used in simple systems, and the subsequent development of multi-layer all-dielectric reflectors enabled the Fabry-Perot filter to obtain significantly better performance (Macleod, 1986, p. 158). There are two basic Fabry-Perot filter structures:

Figure 2. 8. Two basic types of all-dielectric Fabry-Perot filter structures.

Generally, for Fabry-Perot filters, the optical thickness of the dielectric spacer layer needs to be a dummy layer and therefore an integer multiple of half the design wavelength. The high reflectance layers replacing the metal mirrors can each be quarter wave optical thickness. Also, the reflectivity of the mirrors on both sides of the spacer layer should be as close as possible, with the ratio of high and low refractive indices as large as possible and of high

interference order (not exceeding 4th order).

2.1.3 Optical Filter-Linear Variable Bandpass Filter (LVF)

Introduction

The commonly used optical filter types and principles are introduced in the previous section. This section will introduce LVFs as highly specialised optical filters. The LVF is a type of interference filter whose design wavelength changes with the physical location in a specific direction across its physical length (Krasilnikova *et al.*, 2005). It can divide an incident light beam into spectral components corresponding to the changing design wavelength across the physical position of the filter, thereby acting as a single optical component variable filter, spanning a wide wavelength range. The types of LVF optical filters can be divided into band-pass, high-pass, low-pass, etc. Of these, the LVF bandpass filter can be used in spectrometers. A high performance spectrometer will require a narrow-bandpass LVF. The spectral shape of the transmission curve of this filter in each position is the same as that of the usual planar narrow-band filter. However, its central wavelength will continue to change linearly with a given thickness gradient, as shown in Figure 2.9. In this way, one linear variable filter can span a wide wavelength range and can replace multiple dedicated filter components, greatly simplifying the system structure and minimizing the device's weight.

Figure 2. 9. Schematic diagram of the spectral characteristics of an LVF.

In the scientific literature, LVFs also have many other names. Emadi et al. called it Linear-Variable Optical Filter (LVOF) (Emadi, Wu, de Graaf and Wolffenbuttel, 2012a), Kirby et al. called it Variable Interference Filter (Kirby *et al.*, 2006), Klein et al. called it Linear Variable

Interference Filter (Klein *et al.*, 2008), Jhabvala *et al.* called it Linear Variable Etalon (LVE) (Jhabvala *et al.*, 2003), Loesel *et al.* called it Wedge Filter (Loesel and Laubier, 2008). The transmittance of the filter may not change continuously with the movement of the physical position. If it changes in steps, it is called Integrated Stepwise Filter (ISF) or multi-channel filter (Tack *et al.*, 2012). Similar to LVFs, there are Circular Variable Filters (CVF) (Cabib, Lavi and Orr, 2010). The bandpass wavelength of CVF changes linearly with angular position of the circular substrate, and a spectral scan is generally completed by rotation.

LVFs can be used in a spectrometer or imaging system. Compared with traditional grating spectrometers, the instrument's volume can be reduced by making the optical path more compact. At the same time, because there are fewer optical components, the instrument's sensitivity to vibration is relatively low, which is better suited to the needs of miniaturization or handheld devices. In the near-infrared band, LVFs are very suitable for spectral analysis because near-infrared spectroscopy does not require very high-resolution and medium resolution is relatively easy to obtain with LVFs.

History of Linear Variable Filter

The concept of an LVF can be traced back to around 1950. Dufour discussed the production method of LVFs and also proposed the concept of circular variable filters (Dufour, 1950). In 1965, Thelen and Apfel of OCLI introduced the theoretical and experimental steps of an optical film they called a circular wedge, which is actually a circular variable filter (Thelen and Apfel, 1965). But unfortunately, because array detectors such as charge-coupled devices (CCD) have not yet been invented, there were only a handful of LVF applications in that era. However, circular variable filters were used in simple spectrometers for colour measurement for example, because they can be scanned by rotation (Hovis, Kley and Strange, 1967).

Until the appearance of array detectors, LVF really comes in handy and shines in the field of spectral imaging. Among them, there are abundant applications in the field of aerospace. Santa Barbara Research Center, a subsidiary of Houston Aviation, published two articles on spectral imaging systems based on linear variable filters in 1990 and 1999 (Mika, 1990; Jeter and Blasius, 1999). These two articles respectively introduce two different types of aviation spectrometers, both based on linear variable filters.

In 1996, the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) also carried an imaging spectrometer using an LVF as the core on a satellite named EO-1 as the first Earth-orbiting

mission of the new millennium (Seery, Cramer and Stevens, 1996). Since then, spectral imaging systems with an LVF as the core have appeared in many United States aerospace projects (Rosenberg *et al.*, 1994; Jeffrey *et al.*, 1995; Reuter *et al.*, 1997). These spectral imaging systems use LVFs as the core spectroscopic element, and most of their system structures are very compact, which illustrates the advantages of LVF-based devices in terms of space and volume.

Before the 21st century, there were fewer applications of LVFs in the field of spectrometers, and only a few documents recorded it (Pavri *et al.*, 1999; Zhang *et al.*, 1999). Around 1999 OCLI corporation, the LVF supplier of NASA and other institutions, launched the commercialized Micropac series spectrometer, which may be the first spectrometer that used linear gradient filters as spectroscopic components (Zhang *et al.*, 1999). The entire instrument adopted a compact design and needed to be connected to a computer for use, and its resolution was less than 2.5% of the central wavelength. The detection window of this instrument was relatively long and narrow, close to the shape of the filter, so it was not easy to ensure the same intensity of light at different positions.

In the 21st century, LVFs began to be applied in civilian spectrometers, and it was used more frequently in imaging spectrometers. Around 2007, a Russian company launched a new product, a liquid sample spectrometer called InfraSpec VFA-IR, to detect explosives. This spectrometer uses an LVF in the mid-infrared band as the core spectroscopic element and uses the principle of Attenuated Total Reflection to detect samples (Boreysho *et al.*, 2007). In 2012, the German JDSU company launched the MicroNIR1700 near-infrared spectrometer. The entire spectrometer has a compact structure and weighs only 60g, but because of the use of expensive InGaAs detectors, the instrument's price is high (O'Brien *et al.*, 2012b). In 2013, German scholar Wiesent designed an LVF-based Mid-IR micro-spectrometer for monitoring oil conditions (Wiesent, Dorigo and Koch, 2013).

In more recent years, LVFs are still mainly used in hyperspectral imaging systems and spectrometers. In 2016, the Danish company Delta Optical Thin Film A/S launched an LVF-based hyperspectral imaging system for medium and full-frame CCD/CMOS sensors (Delta Optical Thin Film A/S, 2016). In 2017, the American company Omega developed a linear variable filter with a gradient of up to 100 nm/mm (Omega Optical, 2021). In 2020, Shigeng Song at UWS introduced an LVF-based hyperspectral imaging system for large-scale crop

monitoring in agriculture (Song *et al.*, 2020). In 2021, we explained the effect of spot averaging on the LVF measurement by modelling and comparing the actual results (Zhou, Cai *et al.*, 2021). In 2022, we introduced the LVFs made by high throughput microwave plasma-assisted sputter deposition at the Optical Interference Coating Conference, which are used in visible light and near-infrared spectrometers (Fleming, Cai *et al.*, 2022).

Overall, there have been many near-infrared spectroscopic analysis instruments using LVFs as spectroscopic elements and related scientific research in recent years, and most of the research related to LVFs is again applied to spectral imaging. Although there have been some research results related to the development of LVF spectrometers, most of these documents focus on the development of the actual LVF itself, and there is a lack of systematic research on the development of this type of the full instrument. LVFs have broad application prospects in visible light and infrared spectrometers, but are still in the initial stages of development with great potential for future development.

2.2 Classic Spectrometer

The essence of a spectroscopic instrument is an instrument that realizes dispersion and collection of polychromatic light. There are many ways to classify them. According to the spectral range covered by the spectrometer, they can be divided into: extreme ultraviolet spectrometer (6 nm - 200 nm), ultraviolet spectrometer (185 nm - 400 nm), visible spectrometer (380 nm - 780 nm), near-infrared spectrometer (780 nm - 2500 nm), infrared and far-infrared spectrometer (2.5 μm - 50 μm). In the actual development of spectroscopic instruments, there is no strict classification according to the above method. The spectral range of commercial spectroscopic instruments may cover multiple bands, and spectrometers' application fields and analysis capabilities are varied. The working spectral range of the spectrometer is limited by the response band range of the detector, the dispersion capability of the spectrometer's optical system, and the system's spectral transmission capability. The spectrometer systems studied in this paper are designed to work in the visible and near-infrared bands.

According to the specific working principle of the spectrometer, it can be divided into two categories: classical dispersion spectrometer and modulation conversion spectrometer. The classical dispersive spectrometer is based on a slit incident aperture and uses a prism or a grating as a spatial dispersive element to collect the dispersed light intensity signal. This type

of spectrometer is divided into two types according to the different sampling components: one type contains a mechanical scanning mechanism inside. It uses a photomultiplier tube to receive a light intensity signal of one wavelength in a single scan, usually called a monochromator. The other type has no scanning mechanism inside. It uses a photoelectric array detector to receive light intensity signals of a certain wavelength range simultaneously, usually called a spectrograph. The modulation transformation spectrometer is a non-spatial dispersion instrument based on a circular incident aperture, and the incident light is first subjected to systematic modulation transformation (interferometric modulation or Hadamard transformation, etc). The modulated light intensity signal is collected at one time, and then the actual measured spectrum is obtained through calculation and demodulation. Classical dispersive spectrometers have a simple optical-mechanical structure and are relatively mature in development. They are the most widely used, but the incident slit, and dispersion capabilities restrict their resolution and signal-to-noise ratio. The optical-mechanical structure of the modulation conversion spectrometer is complex, including many physical motion mechanisms, and the entrance aperture does limit its resolution and signal-to-noise ratio. High signal-to-noise ratio and high-resolution spectral signals can be obtained by expanding the aperture and modulation method, and it is more used in the detection field of long-distance weak light intensity.

Several of these typical spectrometer systems are briefly introduced below.

2.2.1 Classical Dispersive Spectrometer

Classical dispersive spectrometers can be divided into two categories according to their spatial dispersive elements: prism dispersive spectrometers and grating dispersive spectrometers.

Prism Dispersion Spectrometer

Prisms can be divided into reflective and beam-splitting prisms according to their working principles. As the spatial dispersion element of a spectrometer, a beam-splitting prism needs to be selected. Its working principle is shown in figure 2.10:

Figure 2. 10. Illustration of generic dispersion in a prism (Goran_tek-en, 2023).

The polychromatic parallel light beam is incident on the working end surface of the prism at the incident angle i_1 , refracted by the two surfaces of the prism, and emerges at the exit angle i_2 ; assuming that the apex angle of the prism is α , the deflection angle of the light is δ , and the refractive index of the prism material is n . The prism dispersion equation can be obtained:

$$\delta = i_1 + \sin^{-1} \left\{ n \sin \left[\alpha - \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\sin i_1}{n} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (2.15)$$

According to the formula 2.15, it can be seen that the different refractive index for each light wavelength component in the polychromatic light, changes the deflection angle of the outgoing light is realized, and the dispersion of the light can be realized. The dispersion capability of the prism spectrometer is related to the effective aperture width and angular dispersion of the system. It has nothing to do with the vertex angle α of the prism. The prism's angular dispersion depends on its material's refractive index N . The dispersive prism spectrometer is a transmissive optical system, and the working spectral range is limited by the material's transmittance and the prism's size. At the same time, the subsequent transmissive system will also introduce chromatic aberration, which will affect the imaging quality. The dispersive prism spectrometer has a simple structure, and most importantly has no high-order diffracted light, and is the easiest optical system to realize miniaturization. However, the dispersion ability of a single prism is limited, and it is often necessary to use multiple prisms to implement the spectrometer optical system. Currently, mainstream commercial spectrometers seldom use prisms as dispersion elements and are usually only used as pre-dispersion elements in instruments to cooperate with other dispersion elements.

Grating Dispersion Spectrometer

The grating dispersive spectrometer is currently a relatively mainstream dispersive

spectroscopic instrument, and its core component, the grating, is an optical element made by drawing periodic lines on a precision optical surface. According to its manufacturing process, gratings can be divided into mechanically carved gratings, replica gratings, and holographic gratings; according to their working methods, they can be divided into transmissive gratings and reflective gratings. Transmission gratings are rarely used in commercial spectroscopic instruments due to the limitation of the transmittance of their materials, but they still have their advantages in astronomy and other fields. Spectroscopic instruments based on reflective gratings can be divided into planar and concave grating spectrometers according to their working surface types. Planar gratings work in parallel beams, so the optical system needs to add a collimation system and an imaging system in addition to the slit aperture; concave gratings work in divergent beams, and the optical system aberration is corrected through optimized design, and the optical structure is simpler. The optical structure based on grating dispersion is the fastest and most mature micro-spectrometer, such as the Ebert-Fastie structure, Czerny-Turner structure, Littrow structure, etc.

The grating achieves dispersion through diffraction. Taking planar gratings as an example, planar diffraction gratings work under parallel light beams, and its essence is to add a periodic modulation to the incident light. The diffraction process of the grating is equivalent to the joint action of single-slit diffraction and multi-slit interference, and the modulation effect of the grating on the light intensity is the product of the incident light intensity, the single-slit diffraction factor and the multi-slit interference factor. For the modulation of the grating, the effect of the interference factor on the amplitude and phase is mainly investigated.

Figure 2. 11: Schematic diagram of grating principle.

Figure 2.11 is a schematic diagram of the principle of a reflective planar blazed grating, and the grating equation is

$$\Lambda(\sin \theta_i \pm \sin \theta_d) = m\lambda, (m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots) \quad (2.16)$$

In the formula, θ_i and θ_d are the incident angle and diffraction angle of the grating, respectively. Λ is the grating constant, that is, the distance between the ruled line pairs, and m is the diffraction order. The dispersion power of the grating is related to the grating density and the diffraction order. For a planar grating with a given area, the higher the grating density, the stronger the dispersion power of the grating. According to the grating's principle of diffraction and spectroscopy, the incident light intensity is divided into several parts, and the spectrometer needs to receive more light energy to improve the signal-to-noise ratio. The main energy of ordinary gratings is concentrated in the maximum zero-order spectrum, and the zero-order spectrum is non-dispersive light. Therefore, as shown in Figure 2.11, the groove surface of the grating is designed to have a certain angle with the bottom surface of the grating, and the main energy of the grating is concentrated on a certain diffraction order. The most commonly used blazed grating concentrates the main energy of the diffraction spectrum on the first-order spectrum. It can achieve better spectral resolution with the imaging system, according to the formula 2.16. It can be seen that there is a phenomenon of overlapping diffraction orders in the grating dispersion. That is to say, the light of different diffraction orders will exit at the same diffraction angle.

2.2.2 Modulation Conversion Spectrometer

Modulation transform spectrometers can be divided into two types according to different modulation methods: Fourier transform spectrometers using interference debugging and Hadamard transform spectrometers using encoding and decoding modulation.

Fourier transform spectrometer

Fourier transform spectrometers are spectroscopic instruments that use fast Fourier transform technology to reconstruct the interference fringe pattern into the original measurement spectrum. Currently its development is relatively mature. Figure 2.12 is a working diagram of the Fourier transform spectrometer interference system. The point (line) light source S is incident on the beam splitter G_1 through the aperture stop and the collimating objective lens C_1 , and a part of the light is incident on the fixed plane mirror M_1 . Another part of the light is incident on the movable plane mirror M_2 , and the optical path compensation plate G_2 is placed between the beam splitter G_1 and the mirror M_1 . The beams reflected by the two mirrors

undergo double-beam interference on G_1 , and the interfered light is imaged on the image plane of the detector through the objective imaging lens C_2 .

Figure 2. 12. Schematic diagram of the principle of a Fourier transform spectrometer.

Based on the relationship between the interference fringes and the change of the optical path difference, the power distribution of the measured light spectrum is calculated by the Fourier transform. The resolution of the Fourier spectrometer is proportional to the length of the imaged interferogram. That is the more sampled data, the higher the resolution of the spectrometer and the longer the scan time and calculation time. The Fourier spectrometer can be illuminated by an extended light source, which improves the signal-to-noise ratio without affecting the resolution of the system; the double-beam structure can also effectively suppress light source fluctuations and random noise. The calculation speed limited the early Fourier spectrometers, but with the development of modern computers, the excellent performance of this kind of spectrometer has become apparent. Fourier spectrometers are widely used in infrared, remote sensing, spectral imaging and other fields. Static Fourier spectrometers and micro Fourier spectrometers also appear in commercial spectrometer products.

Hadamard Transform Spectrometer

Hadamard transform is a generalized Fourier transform, which is widely used in video coding as a coding method, and its characteristic is that it can analyse the frequency spectrum quickly. The Hadamard transform spectrometer uses a multi-slit incident aperture called a coded aperture. The coded aperture is used as the code plate in the Hadamard transform, and the actual spectral data is obtained by decoding the measured spectral signal. The Hadamard spectrometer modulates the optical signal in the spatial domain. Compared with the Fourier transform, which is based on the mathematical model of the plane wave function, the

calculation speed is fast. Due to the multi-channel lighting method, the system's signal-to-noise ratio is effectively improved, and the system structure can also be adapted to the miniaturized system requirements. The application of the Hadamard transform spectrometer is not yet popular, and its advantages of high signal-to-noise ratio and high resolution are gradually applied in Raman spectroscopy detection, biomedicine, imaging spectroscopy and other fields. Recently, on the basis of the Hadamard transformation spectrometer, a spectrometer system based on DMD (Digital Micromirror Device) devices has also been developed. It adopts a double grating system and does not need to adjust the optical path. Replacing the detector can extend the working spectral range from ultraviolet to middle and far infrared.

2.3 Miniaturized Near Infrared Spectrometer

Near-infrared spectroscopy is one of the world's most widely used analytical techniques. Because of its advantages of being non-destructive and fast, it is widely used in agriculture (Song *et al.*, 2020), the chemical industry (Balabin, Safieva and Lomakina, 2007), medical treatment, environmental monitoring (O'Brien *et al.*, 2013; Wiesent, Dorigo and Koch, 2013) and other fields.

In recent years, with the in-depth research of more and more scientists and the combination of chemometric software, spectrometers and application models, near-infrared spectrometers have developed rapidly, and commercial near-infrared spectrometers are also very mature. However, almost all high-end spectrometers are designed for benchtop use, with bulky optics and moving parts. Although they can provide high-precision measurement data and spectral bandwidth, they contribute greatly to rigorous scientific research work. However, most industries and production facilities often require miniaturized spectrometers that are small in size, light in weight, easy to move and used for rapid on-site analysis. In order to meet this demand, scientific research institutions and enterprises have developed a variety of compact and portable micro-spectrometers based on different technologies.

Based on different measurement principles, many types of micro-spectrometers exist, and new technologies are constantly emerging. At present, according to the measurement method of the spectrometer, they can be roughly divided into the following categories: filter type, grating type, Fourier transform type, acousto-optic tunable filter type, and MEMS technology (Yu, Lu and Gao, 2013). This section will introduce the principle, history and types of

miniature infrared spectrometers.

2.3.1 The Principle of Near Infrared Spectrometer

Near-infrared spectroscopy is a modern analysis method that judges the chemical composition of substances and measures the relative content of each component based on the spectrum. Molecular vibration energy levels are characteristic of the atoms involved. When a molecule absorbs a photon of a certain energy, it is excited from a lower energy level to a higher energy level. The energy of the photon must be exactly equal to the energy difference between the higher and lower energy levels. Otherwise, it will not be absorbed, as shown in the following formula 2.17 (Siesler *et al.*, 2008, pp. 13–15):

$$\Delta E = E_2 - E_1 = \frac{hc}{\lambda} \quad (2.17)$$

where E_2 is the excited state energy level, E_1 is the ground state energy level, ΔE is the incident photon energy, h is Planck's constant, c is the speed of light in vacuum, and λ is the wavelength of incident light. According to this principle, when infrared rays of a certain frequency are focused and irradiated on the sample to be analysed, if the vibration frequency of a certain group in the sample molecule is equal to the frequency of the irradiated infrared rays, resonance will occur (Siesler *et al.*, 2008). While resonating, the group absorbs infrared rays of a certain frequency. At this time, the absorption of infrared rays by the molecules is recorded, and the characteristic spectrum reflecting the components of the sample to be measured can be obtained (Beć, Grabska and Huck, 2020). After comparison or calculation with the standard data, the type and structure of the compound can be deduced.

Figure 2. 13. Energy level scheme demonstrating the principle of Electron Spectrum Generation.

The near-infrared spectral region is usually defined as 800 nm - 2500 nm, and only overtones and combinations of molecules can be observed in this range (Beć, Grabska and Huck, 2020). In near-infrared spectroscopy, the main measurement and analyses are C-H, N-H, and O-H chemical groups (Xu, Zhang and Chen, 2017). Generally, after the near-infrared spectrum is measured, it will be analysed and compared with the sample structure calculated by the chemometric method. NIR spectra are usually complex in comparison with mid-IR spectra. This may be overcome by the use of multivariate calibration.

At present, there are many methods for correction, such as partial least squares (PLS), multiple linear regression (MLR), principal component analysis (PCA), artificial neural network (ANN) and Topological, which are widely used (Blanco *et al.*, 2000; Xu, Zhang and Chen, 2017).

Although there are many types of spectrometers, their main structures are similar, and near-infrared spectrometers are no exception. The structure of a common spectrometer includes the following parts: a spectrum generator or system light source for generating accurate spectra, a beam collimation system, a dispersion system, a focusing system and a detection system, as shown in Figure 2.14. In addition, there are optional accessories mentioned above, which are used to increase the functionality of the spectrometer and provide convenient data processing capabilities.

Figure 2. 14. Common spectrometer structure composition.

2.3.2 The History of Infrared Spectrometers and Their Miniaturization

The beginning of spectroscopy is from people's exploration of beautiful unknown things. After a rain shower, the rainbow phenomenon has been marvelled at for thousands of years. In 1666, Sir Isaac Newton discovered the phenomenon of the dispersion of light, which marked the beginning of the science of spectroscopy (Thomas, 1991).

Around the beginning of the 19th century, German optician Joseph von Fraunhofer connected the convex lens between the slit and the prism to the telescope and developed the earliest spectral mirror (J. von Fraunhofer, 1817; Thomas, 1991). In the early 20th century, J.J. Thomson built the predecessor of the mass spectrometer (Thomson, 1913). Herschel was the first to discover the infrared spectrum, which was discovered from the electromagnetic spectrum in 1800 but was not studied in depth (Herschel, 1800). It was not until 1882 that scholars paid attention to infrared spectroscopy again. Abney and Festing discovered that compounds and certain organic groups in molecules have infrared absorption bands (Abney and Festing, 1883). However, the first infrared spectrometer was not developed until nearly a century later. Perkin-Elmer Incorporated developed the first infrared spectrometer Model 12, in 1944. The mode is a single beam, point-to-point measurement (PerkinElmer Life And Analytical Sciences, 2005). So far, the history of infrared spectrometer technology has begun.

The rapid development of near-infrared spectroscopy came after the 1980s, thanks to the rapid development of chemometrics and computer technology. After the rapid development of near-infrared spectroscopy, technology gradually became independent of the mid-infrared analysis technology centre and became an important analysis and detection technology. The concept of the micro-spectrometer was first invented in 1992 when Ocean Optics of the United States invented the world's first micro-fibre spectrometer, which marked the beginning of the commercialization of the world's first micro-spectrometer (Ocean Insight., 2023).

2.3.3 Classification of Near Infrared Miniature Spectrometers

The difference between micro-spectrometers is mainly in the use of different optical path structures, which can be roughly divided into different types such as filter type, grating type, and Fourier transform type (Yu, Lu and Gao, 2013).

Filter Type Miniature Spectrometer

Filter-type spectrometers are the earliest near-infrared spectrometers, and a few micro-

spectrometers also use filters as spectroscopic components. At present, there are two types of products sold by companies on the market, one is a narrow-band filter that uses an LED array as the light source corresponding to 12 different wavelengths, and the other uses LVFs as the core component (introduced in the previous article).

Filter-type spectrometers using LED arrays are represented by Zeltex's ZX-50 series near-infrared grain analysers (ZELTEX Inc., 2023). The device uses 12 LEDs as the light source, corresponding to 12 narrow-band filters with different wavelengths, corresponding to 893 nm - 1045 nm. As shown in Figure 2.15, each LED is controlled to emit light in sequence. Then the transmitted light signal is received by a single-point detector behind a narrow-band filter and finally summarized and displayed on the LCD screen after data processing (Yu, Lu and Gao, 2013). The advantage of the miniature spectrometer with this structure is that the power consumption of the LED light source is low, and a battery can power it; the structure of the device is simple, and there are no moving parts, so it has high stability and low cost and is relatively easy to accept in the agricultural field.

Figure 2. 15. Array LED-type miniature spectrometer (Yu, Lu and Gao, 2013). Figure (a) is the schematic diagram of the LED array, (b) Zeltex ZX-50 (ZELTEX Inc., 2023).

The near-infrared spectrometer using an LVF as the core is represented by the MicroNIR 1700 series of Viavi solutions. LVF is an optical thin-film device whose spectral characteristics change linearly with the filter's position. The film thickness changes linearly with the direction of the substrate length, and different physical positions correspond to different band-pass centre wavelengths (Song *et al.*, 2020). MicroNIR 1700 uses an LVF as the core filter device, corresponding to the wavelength of 950 nm -1650 nm, uses two low-power tungsten lamps as the light source, and the diffusely reflected light is transmitted by the LVF and then received by the InGaAs linear array detector, as shown in Figure 2.16 (O'Brien

et al., 2012a; VIAVI Solutions Inc., 2023). The miniature near-infrared spectrometer with this structure simplifies the optical path structure, which is smaller and lighter and the stability is also good. The weight is less than 60 g, and it has high stability when fixed.

Figure 2. 16. Schematic diagram of a miniature near-infrared spectrometer using an LVF as the core. (a) LVF diffuse reflection mode and signal collection method; (b) Micro NIR 1700

Grating-type miniature spectrometer

The grating spectrometer is a relatively traditional and common spectrometer structure. Most of the large-scale spectrometer test equipment used in the laboratory uses a grating structure. Grating spectrometers use prisms or gratings as the core spectroscopic components, so grating spectrometers are also called dispersive spectrometers. Gratings, also known as diffraction gratings, are generally made of flat glass or metal (Pügner, Knobbe and Grüger, 2016). Many parallel, equal-width and equidistant slits are engraved on this flat plate. Diffraction occurs when the monochromatic parallel light passes through the grating and then is focused onto the array detector by a concave lens.

Miniature near-infrared spectrometers using this grating structure are also relatively common, and there are many manufacturers. Companies such as Ocean Optics, B&W Tek., and FOSS have such products. The miniaturized instruments mostly use the Czerny-Turner optical path, as shown in Figure 2.17. This structure folds the optical paths to reduce the instrument's volume effectively. The representative product is B&W Tek. TE Cooled InGaAs Array Spectrometer (B&W Tek., 2023). In terms of detectors, low-cost silicon detectors can detect spectra below 1100 nm, InGaAs detectors can detect 1000 nm -2600 nm, and a few use other detectors.

Figure 2. 17. Grating spectrometer schematic. In the figure on the right, 1 is the fibre coupler, 2 is the entrance slit, 3 is the collimating mirror, 4 is the diffraction grating, 5 is the focusing mirror, 6 is the array detector, and 7 is the thermoelectric cooler.

Fourier Transform Miniature Spectrometer

Fourier transform spectrometers have fewer miniature instruments in the near-infrared band, and most manufacturers provide mid-infrared bands. The Fourier transform spectrometer has a large luminous flux, and the test results have a high resolution. At the same time, micro-equipment in the near-infrared band generally does not require high resolution. Moreover, because there are moving parts in the structure of the Fourier transform spectrometer, it is more sensitive to vibration, and it isn't easy to obtain good anti-seismic performance after miniaturization. The representative instrument is Antaris MX from Thermo Company, and the structure diagram is shown in 2.18(Thermo Secentific, 2006).

Figure 2. 18. Illustration of Fourier transform spectrometer layout (Thermo Secentific, 2006).

Acousto-optic Tunable Filter (AOTF) Miniature Spectrometer

Acousto-optic Tunable filter spectrometer is an instrument that uses the acousto-optic effect to analyse the spectrum of a sample. The phenomenon that the crystal's refractive index changes periodically with ultrasonic waves' action is called the acousto-optic effect. This effect produces an effect similar to that of a transmission grating in a spectrometer. By changing the frequency of ultrasonic waves applied to the crystal, the wavelength of the

coloured light can be precisely controlled (Korpel, 1981). Therefore, AOTF-type spectrometers are suitable for near-infrared spectroscopy. At the same time, because there are no moving parts, the stability is high, and the optical path is completely static. It can be designed as an integrated, fully sealed instrument to minimise the volume. The representative product is the Luminar 5030 AOTF-NIR Spectrometer of Brimrose Company, which concentrates all optical paths on the hand-held gun probe, with battery and display screen (Brimrose Corp, 2021). However, due to the high price of AOTF crystals, there may be difficulties in promotion.

New Spectrometer using Micro Electro-Mechanical-System (MEMS) Technology

The emergence of Microelectro - mechanical - system (MEMS) technology has given a new definition to miniaturized spectrometers. MEMS can realize the movement of optical components on a microscopic scale, which greatly simplifies the optical path and makes miniaturization and microchips possible. In recent years, many institutions have successfully proposed various types of micro near-infrared spectrometers based on MEMS structures, and many have been commercialized.

The German Fraunhofer laboratory integrated the grating and scanning rotation device on a chip to replace the scanning grating in the traditional grating scanning spectrometer. The representative product is the SGS series product of Hiperscan, as shown in Figure 2.19 (Schenk *et al.*, 2000; Alexander, 2023).

Figure 2. 19. HiperScan's scanning grating spectrometer (SGS).

The micro-spectrometer based on the Fabry-Perot filter of MEMS uses the principle of multi-beam interference so that only specific wavelengths can pass through, and other wavelength ranges are blocked. The representative product is the IntegraSpec series near-infrared spectrometer of Axsun Company, which uses a high-precision F-P filter to make the wavelength accuracy of the instrument reach 0.25 nm (Miller *et al.*, 2001; Jianfei *et al.*, 2012).

Chapter 3 Experiment

This chapter introduces the thin film deposition equipment and thin film characterization measurement equipment used in this paper. The main film deposition equipment used is the Microdyn, a microwave plasma-assisted pulsed DC magnetron sputtering system. Next, several thin film characterization instruments used in the experiments are introduced.

3.1 Equipment of Thin Film Deposition for my research: Microdyn

The film deposition system mainly used in this work is called the Microdyn, a microwave plasma-assisted pulsed DC magnetron sputtering system from DSI Company in the United States. The full name of DSI is Deposition Sciences, INC., which is a wholly-owned subsidiary of Lockheed Martin. The Microdyn equipment was developed in 1990 to help Philips' light bulb products with multi-layer thin film coating (C. LUECK, 2022). This section will give an overview of the UWS Microdyn system, which is the only such instrument in a university laboratory.

The basis of the Microdyn system is pulsed DC magnetron reactive sputtering, utilising a microwave plasma to assist reactive deposition and is presented in detail in Appendix 1. To have better understanding, a long name of this technique can be “pulsed-DC, microwave plasma assisted, reactive magnetron sputtering”. The following sections outline the physical structure, sub-units and the brief discussions of the advantages of Microdyn system.

Figure 3. 1. The Microdyn Sputtering Thin Film Deposition System.

From the appearance point of view, the Microdyn thin film deposition equipment is a horizontal axis rotary drum type thin film deposition device. The appearance is shown in Figure 3.1. The metal device on the left in Figure 3.1 is a chamber for thin film deposition, and the internal environment of the chamber is kept in a high vacuum state during thin film deposition. In the chamber of the Microdyn, there is a circular drum consisting of 16 flat metal plates that are tangent to the drum. An image is shown in Figure 3.2 (a), and the schematic diagram is shown in Figure 3.2 (b).

Figure 3. 2. The internal structure of the Microdyn. (a) Image of the cavity structure, (b) Schematic diagram of the cavity structure.

During film deposition, the substrate is fixed on a flat plate, and the sample moves in a uniform circular motion with the rotation of the drum. On both sides of the Microdyn's chamber and on the sides obliquely upwards, four metal boxes (#1, #2, #3, #4) can be seen. The target positions are inside the boxes, as shown in Figure 3.3. Thin film deposition can be carried out only by fixing the target on the position in the chamber and applying voltage. The Microdyn is designed to install up to four targets at the same time. Generally, targets of different materials (#1, #2) are symmetrically placed on both sides of the chamber so that two-material multilayer thin film deposition can be performed as needed. At the top of the chamber is a microwave source, used for pre-cleaning/etching of the substrate prior to deposition, activation of the reaction before reactive sputtering, and assisting in the thin film deposition process reactive gas plasma generation. Finally, space is left at the bottom for the high vacuum pump to create the vacuum environment.

Figure 3. 3. Side view of the Microdyn's chamber outline.

The cabinet on the right in Figure 3.1 is the control system for controlling the film deposition, as detailed in Figure 3.4. This control system consists of two Advanced Energy MDX power supplies, two Sparc-Le V pulsing units connected to the MDX power sources for controlling output power pulsing parameters (for arc suppression), Inficon IC5 deposition controller to control film deposition rate, microwave controller for controlling the microwave power, vacuum measurement and control system, MKS multi-gas controller for controlling MKS mass flow controllers (MFCs) that control the gas flow, and Inficon optical gas controller (OGC) for controlling the reactive gas flow partial pressure.

Figure 3. 4. The Microdyn's thin film deposition control system.

In addition, not shown in the figure, a Polycold cryosystem, is employed to reduce the effect of water vapour on the film deposition and there are external roughing/backing pumps. The functions of each component will be described in section 3.2.

3.2 Introduction to the Microdyn components and their principles of operation

3.2.1 Pumping System

As mentioned above, modern thin film processes are generally carried out under vacuum conditions, and attainment of vacuum is an indispensable condition for coating. The vacuum system of the Microdyn thin film deposition equipment is composed of three vacuum pumps, which are; a roughing pump, a backing pump and a turbomolecular pump. The functions of these three pumps are different, but they are inseparable.

The roughing pump is the first step in achieving a high vacuum. After the roughing pump evacuates the chamber to 4.0×10^{-2} Torr, control switches to a turbomolecular pump with a blade rotation speed of 1300 rev/s. The turbomolecular pump will increase the vacuum in the chamber to a high vacuum. This process generally lasts anywhere from 30 to 60 minutes, depending on how long the inner walls of the chamber are exposed to the atmosphere. Whenever the vacuum system is exposed to air, the surfaces inside the chamber are covered with layers of water molecules (Schoonover Inc., 2018). The Polycold cryosystem reduces this effect by trapping water vapour on a cold finger. The role of the backing pump is to remove air from the high vacuum to atmosphere, since the turbomolecular pump cannot be directly connected to the atmospheric environment. The backing and roughing pumps are two separate rotary vane pumps.

The vacuum controller and the gauges to measure the vacuum environment level in the chamber will be introduced later. This system also controls the vent's exhaust and valve opening and closing sequence.

3.2.2 The Polycold Cryochiller

The Polycold cryochiller is a type of cold trap, that captures and collects water molecules in the vacuum chamber to accelerate the formation of a high vacuum state and reduce the base pressure to enhance film purity during vacuum coating (Schoonover Inc., 2018). A special refrigerant flows in the stainless steel or copper tubes that meander through the chamber.

Through cold and heat exchange, water vapour is adsorbed and trapped on the surface of stainless steel or copper tubes, reducing the influence of water vapour on pumping and thereby accelerating the formation of a vacuum environment.

3.2.3 MDX Power Supply

An MDX DC power supply is used to supply the current and voltage for target sputtering. Two MDXs power the left and right targets. The DC output power of the MDX can reach up to 10 kW, and three working modes can be selected: constant current, constant voltage and constant power. The MDX is fan cooled and is connected to a good external ground/earth point to keep the power supply running safely.

3.2.4 Sparc-le V Pulsing Unit

An Advanced Energy Sparc-le V is installed in series between the power output of the Advanced Energy MDX power supply and the target/magnetron assembly to provide pulsed output power to the target on the chamber. There are three modes of Sparc-leV, active control, passive control and automatic control. It can change the pulse frequency (20 kHz - 100 kHz), set the duration of the reverse pulse, and therefore the device's duty cycle (Advanced Energy Industries Inc., 2015).

The Sparc-le V works by monitoring the inputs and outputs of its associated MDX and also acts to reduce arcing at the target caused by localised oxidation of the target. When the output voltage is lower than 50% of the input voltage, the arc energy from the chamber is diverted through the Sparc-le V, which can extinguish the arc before current damage occurs (Advanced Energy Industries Inc., 2015).

The pulses provided by Sparc-le V are bi-directional pulses. In a pulse cycle, the bidirectional pulse has two phases: positive and negative. In the negative voltage stage, the power supply supplies power to the target to generate sputtering by accelerating positively charged argon ions into the target. In the positive voltage stage, electrons built up on locally oxidised areas are removed. That aims to clean the target surface and expose the material on the target surface.

Currently, the frequency of commercial pulsed DC power supplies on the market can reach 200 kHz and generate double-click symmetrical or asymmetrical pulse waveforms, as shown in Figure 3.5. In the mode of DC pulse symmetry, the height of the positive and negative

pulses is equal. Still, the duration of the positive pulse is shorter than that of the negative pulse, and there is a short off-time when the positive and negative pulses switch. (Westwood, Glocker; and Shah, 2018, p. 28).

Figure 3. 5. Cathode voltage as a function of time traces for bipolar symmetrical and asymmetrical pulsed DC power (Westwood, Glocker; and Shah, 2018, p. 28).

For an asymmetric pulsed DC power supply, the size of the negative pulse can be four times the size of the positive pulse. The pulse has no off time and changes directly from the positive pulse to the negative pulse. Similar to symmetrical bipolar pulses, positive pulses are smaller in width than negative pulses. In this case, the average energy of the high-energy particles in the DC pulse discharge is much larger than that in the DC discharge, and due to the larger peak current, the plasma density will increase after the DC pulse discharge (Westwood, Glocker; and Shah, 2018, p. 29).

Bidirectional pulses are often used in unbalanced magnetron sputtering systems with two targets, such as the Microdyn. In this system, the two magnetron devices will be connected to the same pulsed power supply, and two identical targets will be alternately used as cathode and anode. The advantage of this is that when the cathode target is sputtered, the anode target will be cleaned. The polarity of such circulating magnetic flux is the self-cleaning function of the equipment.

3.2.5 IC/5 (A Thin Film Deposition Controller)

The IC/5 is a closed-loop process controller specifically designed for the physical vapour deposition of thin films. The main function is to detect or control the film deposition rate and record the film's deposited thickness. The deposition rate and thickness of the film are inferred by calibrating the frequency change caused by the increase in mass of a quartz crystal

placed in the chamber as thin film coating material is deposited on it.

This technique places the sensor between the target and the target substrate. In the Microdyn, the sensor contains a quartz crystal positioned, as shown in Figure 2.3 above. Three quartz crystals are placed in the sensor on each side, and the data is more accurate by averaging the feedback signals of the three quartz crystals. The drum in the Microdyn system is composed of 16 metal plates, 8 of which have holes, and the other 8 have no holes. A perforated metal plate permits the sputtered material onto the exposed quartz crystal inside the drum. After calibration for each deposited material, the IC/5 will automatically control the thin film deposition process in a precise and repeatable manner according to the deposition time provided by the user, the set deposition thickness, the required deposition rate, and the properties of the materials used (INFICON Inc., 2001).

3.2.6 Microwave Magnetron Power Supply

The microwave magnetron head provides energy for the generation of microwaves. Generally, the maximum power of the microwave plasma source is set to 3 kW, and the reflected microwave power must not exceed 0.05 kW. Microwaves pass through the waveguide at a frequency of 2.5 GHz, and then transmit into the chamber through the pure silica window. The microwave source and waveguide are shown in Figure 3.6.

Figure 3. 6. Microwave plasma source and waveguide.

The internal structure of the waveguide is shown in Figure 3.7. It is shaped like a cuboid box, and the connection between the end and the chamber is a silica window. To ionise the desired gas, the microwave source has a tuner: a recirculation and a detector for detecting the state of microwave generation. When the device runs, the microwave source generates microwaves that enter the waveguide and propagate into the chamber. The plasma is ignited near the quartz window if the power reaches the required value. The waveguide adopts a double-layer vacuum sealing method, one layer is between the silica window and the waveguide, and the other layer is in the chamber inside the silica window.

Figure 3. 7. The waveguide structure used in Microdyn.

3.2.7 Vacuum Gauge Measurement and Control System

In the Microdyn, there are four vacuum measurement gauges for measuring different degrees of vacuum environments. Generally, these four vacuum measurement gauges are used sequentially when creating a vacuum environment for accurate measurement in different degrees of vacuum environments.

A Convection gauge installed on the chamber is used to detect a rough vacuum environment. When the vacuum reaches 4.0×10^{-2} Torr, the vacuum gauge will be switched to the Convection gauge installed between the backing pump and the chamber. When the vacuum environment reaches a high vacuum, with the work of the turbomolecular pump, the pressure will become lower and lower, and this process generally lasts for two hours. Before the film deposition starts, the hot cathode ion gauge is used to measure the vacuum in the chamber, which is generally lower than 10^{-5} Torr. Currently, the vacuum is already lower than the range of the convection gauge ($< 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$ Torr), and it is impossible to measure with this gauge. The hot cathode ion gauge is relatively sensitive, measuring between 10^{-3} and 10^{-10} Torr.

Generally, it is only measured before deposition and will not be turned on all the time, which can protect the service life of the gauge. Lastly, a Baratron capacitance manometer is used to detect the pressure in the chamber during film deposition.

3.2.8 MKS-Mass Flow Controllers

MKS's mass flow controllers (MFCs) can detect and control the gas flow through the mass flow controller. In the Microdyn's setup, four commonly used gases; argon, oxygen, nitrogen and hydrogen are fed in through pipelines. In the Microdyn, in order to allow the gas to be evenly distributed in the desired position in the chamber, it is further refined into eight branch pipelines to form the gas distribution in the chamber. MFCs control the rate of the gas introduction, and the unit, standard cubic centimetres per minute (sccm^{-1}) is generally used.

3.2.9 OGC-1 Partial Pressure Controller

The optical gas controller (OGC) is manufactured by INFICON, and its function is mainly used to control the partial pressure of the gas in the chamber. Its working principle is to maintain the pressure of different gases in the chamber at a constant value by measuring and controlling a luminescence peak in the reaction gas. It uses a built-in filament that emits electrons to enable electron ionisation of the reactive gas and measures the pressure of different gases through the spectral selection of luminescence generated by the reactive gas species activated by the filament and returning to the ground state. Each gas emits its own characteristic wavelength upon electronic relaxation, which is detected by selective optical filters and sensitive photomultipliers.

In Pulsed DC Magnetron Reactive Sputtering, it is generally necessary to control the reaction process. That is because the quality and performance of the final film deposition will be greatly related to the sputtering flux and active gas concentration in sputtering. For example, in Song et al. LVF production, the partial pressure control is used to ensure the maximum deposition rate of SiO_2 film and ensure the quality of the film after formation (Song *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, it can be seen that Pulsed DC Magnetron Reactive Sputtering can maximize the deposition rate of the film and can also adjust the stoichiometry, microstructure and properties of the film formation by adjusting other control parameters (Westwood, Glocker; and Shah, 2018, p. 30).

The Microdyn is a reactive sputtering thin film deposition device. During reactive sputtering, target poisoning can occur after long-term contact with reactive gases. If simple gas flow

control is used to control the amount of reactive gas introduced, a dielectric (oxide or nitride) reactant layer on the surface of the target can become thicker, and the sputtering phenomenon will stop. Using the partial pressure of the gas to control the amount of reactive gas fed in, when the material sputtered from the target reacts highly with the reactive gas, more reactive gas is fed to maintain a constant partial pressure. But when reactive substances accumulate on the surface of the target, the partial pressure controller will reduce the introduction of the reactive gas and keep the reaction rate normal so that the sputtering can proceed normally.

Figure 3. 8. The relationship between the target voltage and the oxygen flux of the reactant gas (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012, p. 323).

Figure 3.8 illustrates the relationship between the discharge voltage and oxygen flow rate during reactive sputtering of oxides from metal targets in Wasa et al. (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012). When the pressure in the chamber reaches 1 mTorr, hysteresis occurs. The solid and hollow circles in the figure represent increasing the oxygen flow rate from 0% to 11% and decreasing from 11% to 0%, respectively. In the stage of increasing oxygen flux, the discharge voltage at point B drops from 530 V to 390 V due to the formation of an oxide layer on the surface of the target due to too much oxygen. When the oxygen flux dropped to 4%, the oxide layer was not formed as fast as it was consumed, and the oxide layer was removed. Because in Wasa's experiment, the power was constant, a decrease in voltage represented an increase in current (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012).

Figure 3. 9. Thin film deposition rate as a function of oxygen flux of reactant gases (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012, p. 323).

This phenomenon is because, in reactive sputtering, the yield of secondary electrons participating in the reaction is higher than the number of metal atoms on the target surface. Wasa (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012) called the phase with an oxide covering the target surface "Oxide Mode" and the phase without oxide covering the target surface "Metallic Mode". He also observed in the experiment that due to the sudden drop and sharp rise of the voltage applied to the target, the deposition rate of reactive sputtering is also affected, as shown in Figure 3.9, the relationship between the deposition rate and the oxygen flow rate of the reactive gas.

Figure 3.9 shows that with the increase of O₂ input from 0% to 9%, the film deposition rate has been stable at 40 nm/min. From point A to point B in the figure, almost all metal films are obtained at this time. However, when the amount of O₂ introduced is greater than 10%, the surface of the target is completely covered by oxides, and the film deposition rate drops rapidly to 4 nm/min. At this time, oxide films are deposited. After reducing the O₂ flux from C to A, the deposition rate returns to the original metallic mode at point E. Wasa summarizes this specific hysteresis as shown in Figure 3.10.

Figure 3. 10. Wasa summarizes hysteresis characteristics in different modes of reactive sputtering (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012).

In reactive sputtering the reaction process basically occurs at solid surfaces, and the gas phase reaction is almost negligible. The Microdyn aims to deposit metal on the substrate, which is oxidised preferentially at the microwave position. However, the reaction at the target material surface cannot be ignored when sputtering because the ion bombardment makes the metal atoms on the target material surface become very active, coupled with increase in surface temperature of the target, which makes the reaction speed on the target material surface accelerate. At this time, the surface of the target is undergoing both sputtering and reaction to form compounds simultaneously. If the sputtering rate is greater than the rate of compound formation, the target may be in a metallic mode; conversely, the sputtering of the target may be stalled because the rate of compound formation that occurs exceeds the rate of sputter removal.

In the Microdyn, the reaction gas generally controlled by OGC is oxygen or nitrogen.

3.3 Process Flow for the Microdyn Thin Film Deposition

As previously mentioned, the Microdyn is a microwave plasma-assisted DC magnetron reactive sputtering film deposition equipment. Its deposition steps can be divided into the following stages: 1) preparation stage; 2) vacuum environment formation stage; 3) microwave pre-treatment stage; 4) film deposition stage; 5) cooling treatment.

Preparation stage: The substrate is pre-cleaned using an ultrasonic bath prior to loading into

the chamber. The substrates are then loaded onto the 16-plate drum and loaded into the chamber.

Film deposition environment stage: The chamber is then sealed, and the roughing pump is turned on. When the vacuum reaches 4.0×10^{-2} Torr, the valve port of the roughing pump is closed and switched to the turbomolecular pump, which takes about 15 minutes. Under the turbomolecular pump, the vacuum will drop rapidly and form a high vacuum environment. When the environment inside the chamber reaches a high vacuum, the Polycold can be turned on to accelerate the formation of an improved vacuum. Reaching the high vacuum environment required for thin film deposition takes about two hours.

Microwave treatment stage: After two hours of turbomolecular pump work, the vacuum inside the chamber can reach 10^{-6} Torr. At this time, the hot cathode ion gauge is switched on to check whether the chamber environment meets the requirements for film deposition. If it meets the standard, the hot cathode ion gauge is turned off and the motor to spin the drum is turned on and is set to about 60 rpm. Before film deposition begins, the substrate is cleaned by microwave plasma in an argon and oxygen atmosphere. The advantage of this cleaning step is that any residual microscopic organic pollutants on the surface of the substrate are removed by microwave plasma, which can improve the film's adhesion on the substrate's surface and make the film grow more uniformly with greater density. In the microwave treatment stage, the microwave power is generally set between 2 kW and 3 kW, and the pre-treatment time is judged depending upon the selection of film materials, the choice of substrates and the environment in the chamber. The schematic diagram of the Microdyn microwave pre-cleaning stage is shown in Figure 3.11(a), and the purple part is the microwave plasma working area.

If the film to be deposited is metal, the steps are as follows. First, the microwave used for pre-cleaning in the previous step is turned off, because otherwise the microwave will produce a very large reflected energy when the metal film is deposited. If this is allowed to last, it will reduce the microwave magnetron lifetime. After the microwave is turned off, the sputtering gas is introduced. Argon gas is generally used in the Microdyn. After introducing the argon gas, the pressure in the chamber reaches a stable value. At this time, the thin film deposition detection is started through the IC5, and the MDX supplies power to the target. The schematic diagram of the working state is shown in Figure 3.11(b). The time required for the general

film deposition phase depends on the desired thickness of the film design.

Figure 3. 11. Diagram of the Microdyn working steps. Schematic diagrams of (a) microwave plasma pre-cleaning stage, (b) metal film deposition and (c) dielectric film deposition.

If a dielectric film is to be deposited, the microwave remains on. Under microwave plasma treatment, the reactive substances will be ionised and can react at a lower temperature. Generally, when depositing metal oxides, O_2 is introduced to make the sputtered metal react in O_2 to form corresponding metal oxides; when depositing nitrides, N_2 or NH_3 is introduced; when depositing nitrogen oxides, a mixed gas of O_2 and N_2 is fed; when depositing carbides, feed C_2H_2 or CH_4 ; when depositing fluorides, feed HF or CF_4 . The reaction process and area in Microdyn are shown in Figure 3.11(c), and the pure target, for example Si, is placed on the right side of the figure. The mixed gas of Ar and O_2 is passed into the chamber, and with energy provided by the DC power supply, the Ar is ionised and positive Ar ions bombard the target, so the Si material is sputtered and deposited on the surface of the substrate placed on the drum. The substrate rotates in a circle with the drum and contacts with partially ionised oxygen when it passes through the microwave area directly above. At this time, an oxidation reaction forms a dense SiO_2 dielectric film. The advantage of this is that the sputtering deposition and oxidation reaction are separated in the chamber to form a sputtering area and an oxidation area, which reduces the probability of target poisoning and makes the film deposition process more stable. At the same time, under microwave plasma treatment, the sample's surface is denser, the formed film has fewer defects, and the strength and corrosion

resistance of the film is guaranteed.

Finally, the film deposition will enter the cooling stage when it is over. After a long time of thin film deposition, it is generally necessary to have a cooling process to reduce the temperature in the chamber. After the cooling, the chamber is vented in order to increase the pressure in the chamber to atmospheric pressure, and the chamber door will automatically open once atmospheric pressure is reached.

Generally, a control program is written to control the film deposition process through a computer during the deposition process. Because in the deposition process of multi-layer thin films, deposition processes can take a long time, computer control of the IC5 can switch targets eliminating any delay caused by manual switching of materials. All experimental parameters need to be entered manually in the program. The data, such as magnetron power, voltage, current, microwave power, argon gas flow rate, reaction gas flow rate required for deposition are recorded in material files. An operation file (run file) records the number of film layers that need to be deposited, the thickness of the film (or time) for each layer, the time required for microwave treatment before film deposition, and the time required for cooling after deposition.

3.4 Sample Measurement and Sample Calibration for Spectrometer

A main focus of this thesis is the study of the optical properties of thin films after deposition. Routine optical thin film measurement of completed optical filters focuses on the transmittance and reflectance of single and multi-layer thin films on optical substrates.

However, for thin film filter design to be possible, it is first necessary to determine the optical constants and optical characteristics of the materials to be used in the deposition process. This data can be calculated from the measured transmittance and reflectance of deposited films. Similarly, completed filters are measured and then compared with the design, with the quality of the sample determined based on agreement with the design. Therefore, thin film samples' characterization methods are as important as the thin film deposition process itself.

The next section will introduce the thin film characterization equipment that were commonly used throughout this work.

3.4.1 Aquila NKD-8000

Figure 3. 12. The Aquila NKD-8000 optical thin film characterization equipment.

The thin film measurement system model, NKD-8000 from Aquila Instruments Ltd, is shown in Figure 3.12. Its measurement range is between 350 nm - 1700 nm, and it can measure the optical transmittance and reflectance of the sample at the same time at variable angle of incidence. The device also provides software that can calculate the film thickness and can model the refractive index and extinction coefficient of films on substrates. This sample measurement process does not cause damage to the sample.

Figure 3. 13. NKD-8000 internal structure diagram.

A special feature of this device is to measure the spectral data of the sample by continuously changing the angle of incidence of the light, while using polarized (S and P) or unpolarized light. Its internal structure is shown in Figure 3.13. The main test structure consists of an incident light source installed on the arm, a detector for receiving transmitted light installed on the lower arm, and a reflected light detector installed on the upper arm. The incident light source is a 100 W quartz tungsten halogen lamp, and the diameter of the spot can be changed between 0.5 mm - 3 mm by adding a lens. The reflected light receiving detectors are variable, with one for the visible light band and one for the near-infrared light band. S-polarized, P-polarised, or unpolarized light can be selected by use of a polariser.

The measurement steps of the equipment are divided into the following steps. First, the sample is placed on the sample stage, the door is closed, and the measurement is started through software control. At this time, the device will move the sample stage and first take the calibrated reference sample in the upper right corner of the sample stage as a standard sample for measurement and save the data as a reference. Then detector dark values are obtained and saved. Finally, the sample stage is moved to the sample position back to the centre spot alignment position. This process typically takes around 15 minutes, depending on the spectral resolution of the selected spectral data. The beam's incident angle is variable, and the range is between 10° - 70°.

3.4.2 Perkin Elmer Lambda 40

The UV/visible wavelength range spectrometer model Lambda 40 is one of the products of Perkin Elmer, as shown in Figure 3.14.

Figure 3. 14. Lambda 40 Dual Beam UV/Vis Spectrometer.

The device consists of a keyboard, a display screen, a power switch, a light source, a connection panel and a sample placement platform. It is a laboratory-grade double-beam ultraviolet and visible spectrometer with a working wavelength range of 190 nm - 1100 nm, and the highest resolution can reach 0.1 nm wavelength. It has the characteristics of fast measurement, high accuracy, high resolution, low stray light, and various operating modes (PerkinElmer Ltd, 2000).

3.4.3 Nicolet iS50 FTIR

The Nicolet iS50 is a Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectrometer from Thermo Scientific, as shown in Figure 3.15. This spectrometer has built-in dual light sources, which can be selected from the tungsten-halogen white and long-life infrared light sources. The measurable spectral range in wavenumbers is 400 cm^{-1} - 12004 cm^{-1} , and the converted wavelength is 833 nm - $25\text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The device has three detectors in the main sample chamber. The data obtained after the test have high resolution, the spectral resolution in the mid-infrared band is less than 0.09 cm^{-1} , and the spectral resolution in the near-infrared band is less than 2 nm.

Figure 3. 15. Nicolet iS50 FTIR spectrometer.

The principle of this device is based on a Michelson interferometer. The light source is directed into the light path and split into two vertical beams using a beam splitter inclined at 45 degrees. Then, split beams are each incident on a mirror and then reflected into the receiver, where they interfere to generate an interference pattern. Different interference conditions occur in each wavelength range depending on the optical properties of different samples. Finally, data in units of wavenumbers or wavelengths can be displayed by transforming the time-domain signal into a frequency-domain signal through Fourier transformation (Boyle, Sukumaran and Chen, 2017).

3.5 Summary

This chapter mainly introduces the thin film deposition technology and equipment, the Microdyn used in this work. Then introduces the components of the Microdyn, the vacuum process, the formation of microwave plasma and the film deposition process (deposition method of the optical film) are introduced in detail. Additionally, the three pieces of equipment used for measuring manufactured samples optical properties are introduced. Aquila NKD8000 and Lambda 40 are used to test sample data in the visible light band, and iS50 FTIR is used to test sample data in the infrared band.

Chapter 4 Design of Linear Variable Filter (LVF)

4.1 Introduction

In the literature review in the first chapter, the concept of a Linear Variable Filter (LVF) and its historical development have been briefly introduced. An LVF is an optical device whose spectral transmittance or reflectance changes uniformly and linearly across its length while its optical properties remain uniform in the direction perpendicular to the gradient change. LVFs have undergone years of research and development and are typically divided into short-wave pass filters (SWPF), long-wave pass filters (LWPF), and band-pass filters (BPF), among which band-pass filters can be divided into ultraviolet, visible light and infrared bands.

The LVF is very versatile and has many applications in multispectral and hyperspectral imaging. These applications are mostly used in remote control systems such as environmental monitoring, drug analysis, and agricultural product quality monitoring.

In environmental monitoring, LVFs can be used for remote measurement, imaging transmission and other functions. A Fabry-Perot LVF-based micro-spectrometer in the ultraviolet band (310 nm – 400 nm) was developed by Emadi et al. It mainly provides functions for measuring the transmission of atmospheric gases, measuring and analysing medicines, etc. In this spectrometer, by using an LVF to replace complex grating components, the volume of the device is reduced, and the cost is reduced at the same time (Emadi, Wu, de Graaf and Wolffenbuttel, 2012a). An Infrared LVF (5.5 μm – 11 μm) was used in an oil condition monitoring system for offshore wind turbines by Wiesent et al. The device developed was a scanning cell LVF spectrometer using static multi-element detectors and using no moving parts (Wiesent *et al.*, 2011; Wiesent, Dorigo and Koch, 2013).

In biomedicine, an LVF has been combined with micro-spectral and microscopic imaging to form a hyperspectral imaging system. The system allows invasive analysis of samples without destroying them (Balas, Pappas and Epitropou, 2016). Compared with traditional machine vision systems, hyperspectral imaging technology has a stronger spectral and spatial resolution and has a better ability to convey details and nuances to users. The spectral width of hyperspectral imaging technology can be extended to the ultraviolet and infrared spectrum, providing details such as chemical and structural components of food that cannot be observed in the visible spectrum. Hyperspectral cameras do this by generating "data cubes". The

spectral information is divided into two dimensions, and the two-dimensional spatial information of the measured target is combined with the one-dimensional spectral information to form a combined set called a data cube. The spectral information related to the frequency or wavelength of light can be considered the third-dimensional information of the detected target.

In the quality inspection of agricultural products, LVFs can show good spectral performance and non-destructive detection ability of crop diseases based on spectral response. A miniature LVF based spectrometer operating in the visible light band (450 nm – 900 nm) was developed by Song et al. (Song *et al.*, 2019). Its main function is to detect the health of agricultural products. A moving part is used in this spectrometer, and the detector receives the light transmitted by the LVF as it moves horizontally to complete the measurement.

This chapter introduces the full manufacturing technology of an LVF for two wavelength bands, one in the visible and one in the near infrared, from the selection of materials and the method of design, to the experimental production. The aim is to develop a relatively low-cost LVF and use it as a core component in a miniaturized spectrometer.

4.2 Material Selection for Linear Variable Filter Fabrication

An LVF is an optical component used to measure spectral properties such as the optical transmittance as a function of wavelength of the tested sample. The measured transmission spectrum varies linearly with the incident or transmitted signal, in which case the spectrum provides information such as absorption and scattering properties.

In this thesis, LVFs in the visible and near-infrared bands are designed, manufactured and used. Therefore, their optical properties are prioritised in the selection of thin film materials and deposition substrates. When the optical characteristics meet the requirements, factors such as heat resistance, corrosion resistance, material strength and manufacturing cost of the thin film substrate should also be considered.

4.2.1 Selection of LVF substrate material

Visible light band substrate selection

Optical glass or plastic can be used as the substrate for thin film deposition in the visible light band. Commonly used visible light substrate materials include K9 glass, microscope slides (MS) and fused silica JGS3. The transmission data of these substrates are shown in Figure 4.1,

measured using the Perkin-Elmer Lambda 40 described in the proceeding chapter.

K9 glass is a borosilicate optical glass mainly composed of silicon dioxide and boron trioxide.

K9 glass has excellent transparency throughout the visible light region and beyond 1100 nm.

Figure 4. 1. K9, JGS3 and microscope slide substrate transmittance spectrum curves.

Fisher Scientific are a supplier of high-quality microscope slides made from Swiss extra-white soda-lime glass. By reducing the iron content in the material, the autofluorescence effect is weakened, and it has better transparency in the visible light region.

Optical quartz glass can be divided into three categories by spectral characteristics; JGS1 in the far ultraviolet band (185 nm – 2500 nm), JGS2 in the ultraviolet band (220 nm – 2500 nm) and JGS3 in the infrared band (260 nm – 3500 nm). In this experiment, JGS3 is used, and its transmittance in the visible and infrared bands is excellent.

According to the above, the spectral transmittance in the visible light band and the parameters of the material itself means all three kinds of substrates could be used. However, since the JGS3 substrate is a circle with a diameter of 15 mm, it is unsuitable for making LVFs and is only used for calibration during production. The K9 glass substrate is a square of 50 mm × 50 mm, and the MS substrate is a rectangle of 76 mm × 26 mm. These two substrates are more suitable for producing LVF in the visible light band.

Selection of Infrared Light Band Substrates

In the infrared band, commonly used optical glass or plastics will produce large absorption, and fewer materials are suitable as substrates. Therefore, it is necessary to carefully study the selection of substrate and thin film materials according to the operational wavelength band. After the substrate and thin film materials are determined, the subsequent thin film design, deposition and detection work must be carried out with the parameters of the level and substrate materials. Commonly used infrared substrate materials include Si, GaAs, Ge, ZnSe, etc. The transmission data are shown in Figure 4.2, measured using the FTIR described above.

Figure 4. 2. Spectral transmittance curves of Si, GaAs, Ge, and ZnSe uncoated substrates in the infrared band.

Silicon (Si) belongs to the Group IV class of semiconductor materials and has high hardness and is insoluble in water. Si wafer substrates are used as substrate materials in this work. In the infrared band, Si is optically transparent in the range of 1.5 μm - 2.5 μm.

Gallium arsenide (GaAs) is a semiconductor material with the advantages of a large band gap, high mobility, high frequency, low noise, and high conversion rate for semiconductor devices. From an optical perspective, GaAs is a useful infrared material with properties similar to Si. GaAs is optically transparent over the 1.5 μm - 2.5 μm range, however it is typically more expensive than Si.

Germanium (Ge) has a cubic diamond structure, and the transparent region ranges from 1.7

μm - 23 μm . Ge has the advantage of high hardness, corrosion resistance, and good mechanical properties and is widely used in mid-to-far infrared detection systems and infrared imaging systems.

ZnSe is a light-yellow transparent crystal and is insoluble in water, relatively soft, with average moisture resistance partial transmittance in the visible wavelength band, and ~71% optical transparency throughout the IR waveband. It can be used in infrared dual-band optical systems.

According to the above optical transmittance and the parameters of the material itself, considering the transparent spectral range, refractive index, mechanical properties and cost performance, Si wafer was finally selected as the substrate material for near-infrared LVF.

4.2.2 Selection of LVF film materials

There are many types of optical films, and the main factor to be considered for selection is their optical performance and spectral range of choice. Optical properties mainly include thin film materials' transparency, refractive index and extinction coefficient. In addition, it is necessary to consider its application requirements, including mechanical firmness, chemical stability, durability after film formation, and corrosion resistance. If the designed film system has a working wavelength range in the visible and near infrared wavebands, for example, 450 nm – 900 nm, then the selected coating materials should be dielectric with as high transparency as possible throughout that region. At the same time, the material's refractive index is also a very important parameter, which is mainly restricted by several factors such as the type of material, the wavelength of action, the crystal structure, the density and the composition of the film layer. The wavelength dependent refractive index of each coating material must remain stable after deposition.

In preparing LVFs and multilayer optical interference coatings in general, combining a high refractive index material and a low refractive index material to achieve the target spectral characteristic is generally necessary. The film materials used can be distinguished according to the spectral bands used in the LVF. A. Emadi et al. used HfO_2 and SiO_2 as high and low refractive index film materials in the preparation of an LVF in the 320 nm - 400 nm ultraviolet band (Emadi, Wu, de Graaf, Enoksson, *et al.*, 2012). A. Emadi et al. used a combination of high refractive index TiO_2 and low refractive index SiO_2 as thin film materials in the preparation of 470 nm – 720 nm for a visible light band LVF (Emadi, Wu, de Graaf and

Wolffenbuttel, 2012a). Song et al. used Nb₂O₅ and SiO₂ as high/low refractive index film materials to prepare 450 nm - 900 nm for a visible light band LVF (Song *et al.*, 2020). A. Emadi et al. used SiO₂ as a low refractive index and Si as a high refractive index material combination in preparing 1500 nm – 2000 nm, 3000 nm – 5500 nm infrared band LVFs (Emadi, Wu, de Graaf and Wolffenbuttel, 2012b).

For the LVFs introduced in this paper, the visible light band LVF and the near-infrared band LVF were deposited using Nb₂O₅ and SiO₂ as a combination of high refractive index material and low refractive index material, respectively. The sputter target materials used to produce LVFs are high-purity niobium (Nb) and Si (purity approx. 99.99%). The sputtered Nb and Si atoms will form the required Nb₂O₅ and SiO₂ films by oxidation in the Microdyn thin film reactive sputtering system (Song *et al.*, 2017). The commonly used Nb₂O₅ film has a refractive index between about 2.1 - 2.3, a high refractive index material between that of TiO₂ and Ta₂O₅. The Nb₂O₅ film is transparent in the range from near ultraviolet to infrared, and the bulk density of the film obtained after deposition is close to 1. The refractive index of SiO₂ film is between 1.3 - 1.4, which is a commonly used low refractive index material.

4.3 Design of Linear Variable Filter

4.3.1 The basic design concept of LVF

The function of optical thin film filters is based on the interference effect of light. While keeping the original volume and weight of optical components largely unchanged, they can redistribute spectral energy by modifying optical properties, such as transmittance, reflectivity, and phase. The same is true for the design of an LVF, and the important parameter to measure the quality of an LVF is the linear dispersion coefficient. The linear dispersion coefficient of an LVF, can be defined as:

$$LVF_{Dispersion} = \frac{\lambda_{End} - \lambda_{Start}}{d_{End} - d_{Start}} \quad (4.1)$$

d_{Start} and d_{End} are the respective start position and end position of the LVF working range, λ_{Start} and λ_{End} are the respective start wavelength and end wavelength of the LVF working range.

There are generally three ways to design linear gradient bandpass filters: long-wave pass plus short-wave pass filter, Fabry-Perot multi-cavity band-pass filter (FPBP) and induced transmission band-pass filter (Piegari and Bulir, 2006; H. A Macleod, 2018).

Long pass plus short pass bandpass filter

When the relative bandwidth of the LVF needs to be designed to be above 3%, it is more convenient to use the long-wave pass plus short-wave pass design because its passband bandwidth can be adjusted freely, and such design and preparation are relatively easy. During preparation, the long-wave pass and the short-wave pass can be deposited on the substrate's front and back sides. The film system combining long, and short wave passes uses different film thickness correction versions, which can effectively eliminate the influence of dispersion on the passband bandwidth and is more conducive to making the passband bandwidth of the fabricated LVF consistent throughout the entire working bandwidth range. The disadvantage of this type of filter is that the required bandwidth of the bandpass filter cannot be too narrow. The too-narrow design will make the slope of the LVF too small, and the form factor is not good enough.

Fabry-Perot type multi-cavity bandpass filter

When the relative bandwidth of the LVF needs to be designed below 3%, the Fabry-Perot multi-cavity bandpass filter (FPBP) design is a good choice. Compared with the design of long and short wave passes, this method can be used to obtain narrower bandwidth and passband form factor. However, the disadvantage is that the choice of materials is relatively limited. The bandpass bandwidth of the filter is dependent on the refractive index ratio of high and low refractive index materials, and the designed passband bandwidth cannot be changed arbitrarily. In addition, for the Fabry-Perot type bandpass filter with a fixed thin film system structure, its bandpass will change with the central wavelength. The shorter the wavelength, the narrower the absolute bandwidth, and the weaker the system's stability.

Induced Transmission Bandpass Filter Mode

When the system to be designed does not have strict requirements on the passband transmittance and form factor, the induced transmission bandpass filter mode can be used to design and manufacture. The advantage of the induced transmission bandpass filter design mode is that the number of film layers designed is less than the former two, and the time and difficulty required for the filter to be prepared are relatively low. That is because the filter designed this way is easily affected by the metal layer at the long wavelength end. Its long-wave dielectric bandwidth is very wide, and there is no need to add more layers to cut off the

long-wave secondary peak. However, the peak transmittance of the LVF designed by this design method is low, the form factor is not obvious, and its peak transmittance and bandpass bandwidth will vary with the position of the working wavelength.

4.3.2 Design Process of an LVF

The thin film design software used in this work employs the characteristic matrix method. Even if hundreds of thin film layers are designed, with the help of thin film design software, it only takes a short time to display the transmission and reflection characteristic curves of the designed thin film system on a computer. The thin film design software used in this paper is TFCalc, which is easy to use and powerful (Hulinks, 2023). However, the design needs to be combined with the actual material parameters used in the experiment. Even different production batches of the same material will have subtle differences in optical properties.

Therefore, in order to carry out the thin film design of the LVF, it is first necessary to test the selected thin film materials to obtain the optical constants of the thin film coating materials required for thin film design. The optical constants are generally the refractive index n , and the extinction coefficient κ of the material. The material's refractive index and extinction coefficient are generally calculated using the OJL model (O'Leary, Johnson and Lim, 1997). The OJL model is a basic empirical model for the electronic state distribution of amorphous semiconductors jointly proposed by O'Leary-Johnson-Lim. The derived optical absorption results of the characterized thin films are empirically measured to derive the complex refractive index of the material. The formula (equation 4.2) is given by

$$\tilde{n} = n \pm i\kappa \quad (4.2)$$

where the real part in the formula is the refractive index n of the material, which reflects the change of the electric field phase, and the imaginary part is the extinction coefficient κ , which reflects the change of the electric field amplitude.

The relationship between the absorbance of the material and κ is as follows,

$$\alpha = \frac{4\pi\kappa}{\lambda} \quad (4.3)$$

where λ is the corresponding beam wavelength. The larger the extinction coefficient κ , the stronger the absorbance of the material.

The film materials used in this experiment are fabricated from Nb and Si sputtering targets.

Nb_2O_5 is formed by oxidation of Nb and is a high refractive index material, and SiO_2 is formed by oxidation of Si and is a low refractive index material. The material's refractive index n and extinction coefficient κ are calculated using transmission measurements. Using the JGS3 circular substrate mentioned above, two thin film depositions were performed respectively. First, a layer of Nb_2O_5 film on JGS3 is deposited. The sample is then measured using the Perkin-Elmer Lambda 40 to measure the optical transmittance. The data is shown in Figure 4.3 (a). The JGS3 sample deposited with a single layer of Nb_2O_5 film is put into the equipment. The SiO_2 film is deposited and measured again using Lambda 40. The data is shown in Figure 4.3 (b).

Figure 4. 3. Optical transmittance measurements using the Perkin-Elmer Lambda 40 for (a) single layer Nb_2O_5 film H20I1409 (Nb_2O_5 thickness 860 nm) and (b) double layer film SiO_2 on Nb_2O_5 on JGS3 H20I1417 (SiO_2 thickness 840 nm).

The refractive index n and extinction coefficient κ of the material obtained by fitting of the optical transmittance data are shown in Figure 4.4.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. 4. Refractive index n (left) and extinction coefficient κ (right) of (a) Nb_2O_5 and (b) SiO_2 .

The obtained n and κ of Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2 thin film materials are imported into TFCalc film design software, and the fitted data is shown in Figure 4.5.

Figure 4. 5. TFCalc film design software fitting for (a) single-layer film Nb_2O_5 on JGS3 and (b) double-layer film SiO_2 on Nb_2O_5 on JGS3(those pictures obtained by screenshot).

So far, the optical parameters of the materials required for the early LVF design have been collected.

4.3.3 Design of Visible and Near Infrared LVFs

From the perspective of the application, the larger the linear dispersion coefficient of the LVF, the denser the working wavelength is compressed, and the higher the degree of miniaturization of LVF integration. But from the perspective of thin film deposition, a large dispersion coefficient means a large change in deposition rate, and the difficulty of making such an LVF is also higher. Therefore, to ensure production accuracy in this work, an LVF with a linear dispersion coefficient in the visible region of 10.3 nm/mm was designed, so that

a linear gradient area spanning 450 nm – 900 nm can be obtained within a physical length of 44 mm. The LVF linear dispersion coefficient in the near-infrared band is designed to be 31.25 nm/mm, so a linear gradient area of 1.5 μm – 2.5 μm can be obtained within a substrate range of 32 mm. From the thin film system design perspective, an LVF is the same as ordinary optical filters and is also designed based on the principle of interference of light waves in multilayer optical films.

Design of visible light LVF (450 nm -900 nm band)

For the visible light band LVF design, an optical interference filter on both sides of the substrate must be deposited. The front face is a three-cavity Fabry-Perot type narrow band bandpass filter (FPBP), and the opposite face is a Wide Band Pass Blocking filter (WBPB).

1) Front face film system design

A narrow-band filter thin film system realizes the front surface of the filter, and its film layer structure is formed of four reflective layers and three spacer layers, that is, *reflector | spacer | reflector | spacer | reflector | spacer | reflector*. The frontal FPBP design is according to the following formula 4.4:

$$Sub/L(HL)^24H(LH)^5L4H(LH)^5L4H(LH)^2/Air \quad (4.4)$$

In this formula, Sub represents the MS substrate used in for the visible light band. Designed using a reference wavelength of $\lambda_0 = 675$ nm, H represents a film layer with $\frac{1}{4} \lambda_0$ optical thickness of high refractive material Nb_2O_5 , L represents a layer with the $\frac{1}{4} \lambda_0$ optical thickness film layer of low refractive index material SiO_2 , and Air represents the medium exit air. This formula was imported into the TFCalc thin film system design software, and as the resultant spectra are shown in Figure 4.6 for designs of the reference wavelength at 450, 675 and 900 nm.

Figure 4. 6. Optical transmittance of modelled Narrow Band Visible region FPBP LVF at 450, 675, 900 nm, designed by using TFCalc.

2) Design of rear surface film system

The WBPB filter on the rear face must transmit the central FPBP peak and simultaneously block the unwanted sidebands across the entire length of the LVF. Therefore, a broadband bandpass filter is designed to block the light passing through except for the light at expected narrow band transmission.

By using 34 layers long pass Edge filter as an initial design. Edge filter formula design is according to the following formula 4.5:

$$Sub/(0.2H0.2L)^3 (0.5H0.5L)^4 (0.7H0.7L)^4 (HL)^3 (HL)^3/Air \quad (4.5)$$

It is perfect design for edge filter, only for an initial trial structure for design. Then use 'target continuous' function in TFCalc, used to optimize the wavelength range for sequential target.

Then set target for TFCalc for optimization, obtained final design with 115 layers for wide band pass filter, as shown in Figure 4.7.

Figure 4. 7. Modelled Wide Band Blocking Bandpass filter of the visible band LVF at 450, 675, 900 nm, designed by using TFCalc.

3) Double-sided design result

The front surface and back surface film system designs are then combined and modelled onto opposite faces of a substrate in TFCalc. The theoretical transmission spectrum curve of the FPBP filter film is shown in Figure 4.8, and the transmittance at 675 nm is 85%. The unwanted sideband peaks that reside outside the central wavelength region of the FPBP filter deposited on the front side, are suppressed by using the WBPB filter deposited on the reverse side.

Figure 4. 8. Modelled optical transmittance of the FPBP with WBPB filter in the visible band at 450, 675, 900 nm, designed using TFCalc.

Design of near-infrared LVF (1.5 μm - 2.5 μm band)

The LVF design in the near-infrared band is similar to the LVF design in the visible light band above, and an optical interference filter is deposited on both sides of the substrate. The front side is a three-cavity FPBP designed based on the bandpass filter film system, and the opposite side is a WBPB.

1) Front surface film system design

A similar approach is used for the near infrared, and the formula 4.6 used in the design is as follows:

$$Sub/0.25L0.25HL(HL)^24H(LH)^5L4H(LH)^5L4H(LH)^20.5L0.5H/Air \quad (4.6)$$

In this formula, Sub represents the Si substrate used in the near infrared band. Designed using a $\lambda_0 = 2000$ nm, H and L have the same meaning as previously stated for the visible LVF and Air represents the exit medium. The design spectra are shown in Figure 4.9.

Figure 4. 9. Modelled optical transmittance of the narrow band FPBP filter for the NIR LVF at 1500, 2000 and 2500nm, designed using TFCalc.

2) Design of rear surface film system

Similar to the design of the visible light band above, the allowable wavelength range is changed to 1500 nm – 2500 nm. A broadband bandpass filter is designed to block the light passing through except for the light at expected narrow band transmission, and the spectral obtained by using TFCalc are shown in Figure 4.10.

Figure 4. 10. Modelled optical transmittance of the WBPB filter for the NIR LVF at 1500, 2000 and 2500nm, designed using TFCalc.

3) Double-sided design result

Combining the near infrared FPBP and WBPB designs, the theoretical transmission spectrum curves of this near-infrared narrow-band filter film are shown in Figure 4.11, and the transmittance at 2000 nm is 82%. The impurity peaks outside the central wavelength region of the narrow bandpass filter deposited on the front side are suppressed by using the wide band blocking filter deposited on the reverse side.

Figure 4. 11. Modelled optical transmittance of the NIR LVF at 1500, 2000 and 2500nm, designed using TFCalc.

4.4 Summary

In this chapter, a discussion of LVFs in the published literature is covered. A discussion of suitable substrate materials for LVFs operational in the visible (450 nm – 900 nm) and NIR (1500 nm – 2500 nm) range is then explored. It was decided that microscope slide glass was the best choice for the visible region and Si wafer was the best choice for the near infrared. This is followed by a discussion of suitable thin film coating materials. Thin film coating materials for the LVFs were selected to be Nb_2O_5 as a high index material and SiO_2 as a low index material for both the visible and near infrared LVFs. Next, the LVF design process is discussed, including extraction of the optical constants of the individual thin film coating materials, FPBP and WBPB filter design and combining the two for a finalized double side coated LVF design.

Chapter 5 Fabrication of Linear Variable Filters

5.1 Introduction

The thin film deposition equipment, the Microdyn, used throughout this work has been introduced in the second chapter. The LVFs are fabricated by using a microwave plasma-assisted DC reactive sputtering process with a mechanical mask system, and the mask is used to control the spatial variation of the bandpass centre wavelength on the substrate surface. The Microdyn uses a horizontally rotating drum for thin film deposition using a rectangular planar shaped DC magnetron and microwave plasma-assisted deposition. When the drum rotates, the substrate placed on the drum will pass through the deposition area several times to complete the thin film deposition, as shown in Figure 5.1. The drum spins at 60 rpm, depositing one or two monolayer films on the substrate each time it passes through the magnetron sputtering zone. When the substrate passes through the microwave plasma oxidation area on the top, the sputtered thin film material will be fully oxidized, thereby depositing the required oxidized material.

Figure 5. 1. Schematic of the Microdyn thin film deposition system. In the middle is a horizontal shaft, and sputtering targets are on both sides. A mechanical mask is between the target and the shaft, and the top microwave source facilitates an energetic reactive plasma for oxidation during the deposition process (Song et al., 2019).

In the process, the real-time control of the film thickness is performed by the IC5 quartz crystal oscillator method. The critical deposition rate of this method was studied by Song et al. in 2011 (Song and Placido, 2011). Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2 were used as high and low refractive index materials and pulsed DC-controlled sputtering was used to suppress the arc discharge

phenomenon during SiO₂ thin film deposition. The thickness of the film obtained by rotating the substrate through the drum is relatively uniform, which is an essential aspect of LVF production. The advantage of this is that the linear thickness gradient along one direction and the transverse thickness are relatively uniform. In order to achieve better uniformity of the LVF deposition, this section introduces the modelling of LVF thickness uniformity and the design of sputter mask plates. Since the thickness of the film is not guaranteed to be uniform over a wide range of space, the average thickness within the device is modelled by measuring a single layer of film using transmittance.

5.2 LVF Thickness Uniformity Distribution Modelling and Mask Template Design

Collecting data for modelling the coating thickness uniformity distribution after multiple thin film depositions is time-consuming, labour-intensive, and wastes material. There will also be large errors in thickness uniformity modelling through this method of data collection. In order to more effectively design the LVF mask plate required to achieve a desired LVF linear dispersion coefficient, the thin film deposition model is established by using mathematical design software and a program is written to simulate the thin film deposition process. In this model, the part that needs to be considered is how to design a mask to cover part of the film material during deposition through its shape so that the film material is more uniform when deposited on the film substrate coated on the drum. The schematic diagram is shown in Figure 5.2.

Figure 5. 2. Conceptual diagram of thin film sputter deposition and sputter mask in the Microdyn (Li et al., 2017).

In Figure 5.2, the substrate is mounted onto the rotating drum plate. The point (x_t, y_t, z_t) on the rightmost target is the spatial position of the sputtered atomic material, and β is the

movement of high-energy particles sputtered from the target to the substrate. The angle of the surface, γ is the incident angle of the thin film material sputtered onto the substrate surface. A is the path that the atomic material can reach the substrate surface, and B is the path that the mask blocks the atom, (x_s, y_s, z_s) designate the spatial position of atoms on the substrate surface (Li *et al.*, 2017).

5.2.1 Target sputtering yield and sputtering angle

The material sputtered from the target is called the sputter yield in thin film sputter deposition. The sputtering yield is generally related to the particles bombarding the target, the strength of the magnetic field, the cathode voltage applied to the target and the gas pressure in the equipment chamber. During film deposition, in order to stabilize the deposition process, the gas pressure in the chamber will be controlled to a constant value, and the voltage applied to the cathode during sputtering will also be kept constant. Therefore, the target sputtering yield during film deposition is not a function of gas pressure in the chamber or the cathode voltage. Also, because the drum moves in a uniform circular motion inside the chamber, it can be assumed that the deposition is uniform over the entire target surface. Therefore, these parameters do not need to be considered in the modelling. In the device, the magnetic field is tangential to the target surface at the cathode, which helps confine the electrons' trajectories, accelerates plasma generation, and is highly inhomogeneous across the target surface. According to the method introduced in the article by Goeckner *et al.* in 1991, by using the Monto Carlo simulation, an equilibrium state exists when the magnetic field is below a value, and the ionization state is about to saturate (Goeckner, Goree and Sheridan, 1991). Between these two magnetic field values, there is almost a linear relationship between the ionization efficiency and the dimensionless magnetic field, as in Equation 5.1.

$$\beta = \sqrt{e/2m} \left(a / V_{dis}^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) B_{tan} \quad (5.1)$$

In this formula, β is the dimensionless magnetic field, e and m are the charge and mass of the electron respectively, a is the radius of the magnetic field tangent to the target surface, V_{dis} is the cathode bias voltage loaded on the target, B_{tan} is the magnetic field strength tangent to the cathode target.

Therefore, the sputtering yield on the target surface is not uniform, which is physically

reflected by the track profile generated on the target surface after sputtering, as shown in Figure 5.3.

Figure 5. 3. Tracks left by the target after sputtering.

According to the above, the probability distribution of the relative yield on the target surface can be obtained by measuring the tangential magnetic field B_{tan} . In addition, there is another way to obtain the relative yield of the target surface by directly measuring the erosion track profile left by the target after sputtering, as shown in Figure 5.3. This method can directly give the result of the material consumption rate related to the magnetic field B_{tan} , which is more suitable for thickness distribution simulation. Figure 5.4 shows a measured erosion trajectory model for the target. The post-sputtering trajectory data obtained by the measurement will be used to generate a two-dimensional data array related to the relative sputtering yield on the target surface, and this surface sputtering yield data set is defined as the "Trackyield" function (Li *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 5. 4. Target erosion trajectory data measured using a depth gauge, shown as a quarter of the total size of the target. The upper part is the contour map, and the lower part is the depth map of the erosion track surface, in millimetres (Li *et al.*, 2017).

In addition to the simulation of the yield distribution by sputtering presented above, the distribution of sputtering angles of the atoms sputtered from the substrate needs to be considered as a function of the angle of incidence of the atoms bombarding the target. In this study, polycrystalline Nb and crystalline Si materials were used. For polycrystalline materials, the sputtered yield is proportional to the offset of the normal direction until it increases to a maximum value and then gradually decreases as the value of the incident angle approaches the grazing incidence angle. The factors to be considered for crystalline materials are more complicated, and the sputtering yield will have some obvious minimum and maximum values under different crystal structures. Sigmund introduced this in his book. The minimum is observed when energetic particles bombard the target in a dense direction in which ions may be redirected into open channels (Peter Sigmund, 1993). In this case, there will not be enough impact energy delivered to the target to excite atoms or molecules from the target surface. Therefore, the sputtering yield will be minimal.

However, the sputtering mode of the device used in the experiments in this paper is pulsed DC magnetron sputtering. When high-energy particles bombard the target, the incident angle will mostly be at a normal angle to the target surface (Shon and Lee, 2002). Considering particle collisions and turbulent electric fields, the average incident angle to the surface normal is calculated to be 7.95° using Monte Carlo simulation (Goekner, Goree and Sheridan, 1991). Therefore, this model will not consider changes in the angle of incidence of the bombarding particles. However, in magnetron sputtering, a general function of the angular distribution of the excited particles needs to be derived. For targets of crystalline materials, the angular distribution of the sputtered particles will be related to the crystal structure of the target. Sigmund tested this idea by bombarding a (100 orientation) silver material crystal target with mercury ions at 100 eV (Peter Sigmund, 1993). From his point of view, it can be used to simulate the sputtering of crystalline silicon targets. In terms of the sputtering angle distribution of the sputtered particles of the polycrystalline target, Martynenko also used magnetron sputtering to simulate the distribution of the sputtered atom emission angle of the polycrystalline target in his research (Martynenko, Rogov and Shul'ga, 2012). According to his experimental results, the maximum emission angle and the angle found on the target surface can be divided into two cases of about 0° and 30° . In the case of 0° , the model function is $f(\beta) = A \cos^n \beta$; when it is around 30° , the model function is $f(\beta) = A \cos^n \beta - B \cos^m \beta$. In order to simplify the calculation steps, a simplified formula 5.2 is

used in this experiment:

$$f(\beta) = \cos(\beta + \beta_0)^n \quad (5.2)$$

β is the emission angle of the high-energy particles sputtered from the target to the surface of the substrate in Figure 5.2, β_0 is the case of the maximum emission angle.

5.2.2 Film Thickness Simulation of Magnetron Sputtering with Mask

For modelling the mask with magnetron sputtering, additional parameters are required. As shown in Figure 5.2, the excited material atoms are sputtered onto the target substrate. Since atoms can be sputtered from any position on the sputtering target surface, each point on the sputtering target can be regarded as a point source. The number of particles reaching the substrate surface is proportional to $1/r^2$, where r is the distance between the point (x_t, y_t, z_t) on the target and the point (x_s, y_s, z_s) on the substrate. At the same time, the projection effect is considered by introducing the $\cos(\gamma)$ factor. γ was introduced earlier, which is the angle between the incident angle of deposition particles and the normal line of the substrate. With the factors to be considered listed above, mask design can now be considered. In order to determine whether the sputtered particles can reach the substrate surface or are blocked by the mask, a geometric analysis is used to describe the function of the mask shape. The parameter "Passrate" is defined is equal to 1 if the sputtered particle is not blocked by the mask, and equal to 0 if the particle is blocked.

Formula 5.3 is as follows, which describes that the particles on the target are excited from the point (x_t, y_t, z_t) and sputtered to the point (x_s, y_s, z_s) on the substrate.

$$Probability = \frac{\cos(\beta + \beta_0)^n \cdot Trackyield \cdot Passrate \cdot \cos(\gamma)}{r^2} \quad (5.3)$$

For mathematical calculation, the target at the coordinate position (x_t, y_t, z_t) is divided into a fine grid structure. The relative thickness of the film on the substrate can be obtained by selecting a specific point on the substrate and taking the sum of the probabilities of all target grid elements around the specific point. As mentioned earlier, the film thickness around the Microdyn's rotating drum can be considered uniform. This simplifies the model, and the optimal mask design only needs to be calculated using the centreline of the drum plate parallel to the rotating drum.

However, the particular point selected at the centreline of the drum board will make a circular motion as the drum rotates. As shown in Figure 5.2, a special data set for the calculation can be constructed for a special point X_s on the centre line by using the coordinator $(X_s, Y_{s0} - R\sin\theta, Z_{s0} - R\cos\theta)$ and move the angle to θ . Here (x_s, y_{s0}, z_{s0}) is the coordinator on the rotation axis. The final relative thickness at a particular point X_s can be obtained by integrating θ in the range $(-\theta_0, \theta_0)$. The resulting thickness simulation final equation is as follows Equation 5.4:

$$Thickness(X_s) = \sum_{\theta} \sum_{X_t, Y_t, Z_t} \frac{\cos(\beta + \beta_0)^n \cdot Trackyield \cdot Passrate \cdot \cos(\gamma)}{r^2} \quad (5.4)$$

By using Equation 5.4 above and the pre-set shape function of the mask, the results of the thickness simulations can be obtained.

5.2.3 Experimental results of Mask design

Work was carried out using a material combination of Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2 in order test the accuracy of the mask design model.

The LVF mask was CNC(Computer numerical control) machined from aluminium sheet, to the dimensions specified by the mathematical mask design model, as the figure 5.5 shown.

Figure 5. 5. Mask on the chamber.

According to the method introduced above, the Microdyn was used to deposit uniform Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2 thin film coatings. Ellipsometry and transmission measurements were performed in order to obtain the optical constants n and κ .

However, different sample analysis methods are required to measure and fit samples with graded thicknesses. When measuring by ellipsometry, the spot size of the measuring beam is

about 1 mm in diameter. For transmittance measurement, the spot size of the measuring beam should be controlled at 3 mm in diameter. The data in Figure 5.6 shows the thickness simulation results obtained using Equation 5.3. After using the designed mask, two linear thickness grading regions are obtained. In Figure 5.6, the thickness change rate is 1.6%/mm in the middle of the linear region on the left, which means that the linear thickness change rate measured by ellipsometry is 1.6%.

Figure 5. 6. Plot of equation 4.3 to obtain the simulation results for the thickness. $X_s=0$ mm is the middle position of the centreline of the drum plate.

More accurate results can be obtained using the thickness averaging method in the fitting. The measurement point on the sample is divided into several parts, and the optical properties of each part are calculated separately and then put together with the area weighting factor to correct and sum. Equation 5.5 below is an example of an ellipsometry calculation by fitting the measured data as a function of the mean Δ and Ψ .

$$\begin{cases} \bar{\Delta} = \sum_i r_i \cdot \Delta_i \\ \bar{\Psi} = \sum_i r_i \cdot \Psi_i \end{cases} \quad (5.5)$$

In Equation 5.5, r_i is the area weight for cross-section i . For example, there are five parts in Figure 5.6, and then r_i is 0.142, 0.231, 0.253, 0.231, and 0.142. In Figure 5.7, using linear thickness grading, the five section thicknesses are divided into $t+2\Delta$, $t+\Delta$, t , $t-\Delta$, and $t-2\Delta$, assuming that each section is approximately uniform in thickness. Therefore, according to the simulation results, the thickness variation rate of each part is about $1.6\%/5 = 0.3\%$.

Figure 5. 7. An example of the thickness averaging method, the film thickness is divided into several segments along the direction of the linear thickness gradient of the spot.

According to the optical properties of the measured materials mentioned above, a mask can be added to deposit the film after shading, the transmittance can be measured through the equipment, and the thickness distribution can be fitted. The results are shown in Figure 5.8. The thickness distribution measured after the experiment shows the gradient trend of the SiO_2 and Nb_2O_5 films formed under the mask. Close agreement in the coating thickness gradients for SiO_2 and Nb_2O_5 can be observed in the regions of high gradient. It shows that the design of Si and Nb targets and LVF sputter masks meets the current experimental requirements, and the simulation results, such as the thickness distribution experimental results, show very good consistency.

Figure 5. 8. Comparison of experimental and simulated results after thin film deposition using the mask. In this figure, the sample images are shown at the top, the thickness distribution graph measured by the experimental results of Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2 is in the middle position, and the thickness distribution results and experimental results comparison graph for SiO_2 are overlain at the bottom.

5.3 LVF production and results

To summarize the content introduced in the above sections, the selection of optical substrate and thin film coating materials is discussed, followed by a discussion of the design of the LVF and mask plate, and finally, the LVF film deposition method is explored in this section.

As described in Section 4.3 above, the ideal LVF is formed by combining a FPBP filter and a WBPB filter on both sides of the substrate to form an LVF. The design of the FPBP filter and the WBPB filter is accomplished by using the optical properties of high refractive-index material Nb_2O_5 and low refractive-index material SiO_2 . By modelling the double side coated filter design, as shown in figure 4.8 (visible light) and figure 4.11 (NIR), the thickness of the coatings at the short wavelength end of the wedge layer is about half of the 450 nm and 1500 nm wavelength sides, relative to the thickness of the 900 nm and 2500 nm wavelength sides, respectively. From the experimental measurement, the ratio of the thicker part of the mask designed by simulation in the linear gradient region is about three times that of the thinner part, which fully meets the design requirements for an LVF.

The production steps for an LVF can be summarized as the following steps, as shown in Figure 5.9. Firstly, by depositing a uniform thin film material and extracting the optical properties of the individual thin film materials used, the structural design of the multilayer filter can be completed. Then, the LVF sputtering mask is installed and a thickness graded single (Nb_2O_5) and double layer (SiO_2 on Nb_2O_5) is deposited. The thickness distribution of the deposited film after adding the mask is measured and the linear thickness change is calculated to check whether it can match the designed LVF structure. Secondly, a quarter of the desired coating design is deposited as a structure test before performing the full filter deposition run. Next, the substrates are cleaned and loaded onto the drum plates for deposition. The position of the substrate on the drum should be precise, and the error should be controlled within 3 mm so that the correct thickness is deposited onto the correct location and the desired coating thickness gradient is achieved. Finally, single side coated substrates are flipped, and the double-sided deposition of the thin film system will be carried out, in order to realise the narrow band Fabry Perot Bandpass filter and the wideband wide bandpass filter.

Figure 5. 9. The production flow chart of an LVF.

The test process of the optical properties of the thin film material has been introduced in the previous article, and the distribution measurement of the thickness of the Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2 thin films will be introduced after adding the mask. Figure 5.10 shows the test results for sample H20I1417. Sample H20I1417 is 840.87 nm SiO_2 thin film on 858.31 nm Nb_2O_5 thin film on MS substrate, using the Aquila NKD-8000 for measurement. It can be seen that the thickness distributions of the Nb_2O_5 film and the SiO_2 film are relatively uniform and matched in the linearity interval on the left.

Figure 5. 10. 840.87 nm SiO_2 film on 858.31 nm Nb_2O_5 film on MS substrate.

Finally, samples of FPBP filters, WPBP filters and LVFs in the visible and near-infrared bands were produced in batches. The LVFs produced in this experiment is divided into the wavelength range of 450 nm – 900 nm (visible light range) and the wavelength range of 1.5 μm - 2.5 μm (near-infrared range). For visible light LVF samples, the test data is shown in Figure 5.11 (a). The passband bandwidth is about 35 nm at 900 nm wavelength, about 20 nm at 450 nm wavelength, the peak position gradient is about 11.14 nm/mm, and the physical length of LVF is 44 mm. The thickness distribution trend is shown in Figure 5.11 (b).

Figure 5. 11. The LVF test data in the visible light band: (a) transmittance as a function of wavelength for different physical positions across the length of the LVF (b) Passband central wavelength as a function of physical position across the LVF.

For near-infrared LVF samples, the transmittance test data are shown in Figure 5.12(a). The passband bandwidth is about 130 nm at 2.5 μm wavelength, about 80 nm at 1.5 μm wavelength, the peak position gradient is about 42.68 nm/mm, the physical length of LVF is 25 mm, and the thickness distribution trend is shown in Figure 5.12 (b).

Figure 5. 12. The LVF test data in the near infrared light band: (a) transmittance as a function of wavelength for different physical positions across the length of the LVF (b) Passband central wavelength as a function of physical position across the LVF.

5.4 Summary

This chapter introduces the thin film manufacturing methods for an LVF. Starting with the modelling and design of the LVF mask that is required to produce a coating thickness gradient during the LVF production process, followed by a discussion of the process flow and characterization of the optical performance of a visible and a near infrared LVF. A good agreement is observed when comparing the modelled thickness distribution results with the experimentally measured values for a single and double layer of Nb₂O₅ and SiO₂ on Nb₂O₅ respectively.

LVFs were fabricated and comprised of a double side coated filter design with a narrow band FPBP filter on one face and a WBPB filter on the opposite. Two different LVFs were produced; one that is operational in the visible region of the electromagnetic spectrum and one that is operational in the near infrared. The visible light band LVF had a physical length of 44 mm, spanning a wavelength range of 450 nm – 900 nm. The near infrared LVF had a physical length of 25 mm, spanning a wavelength range of 1.5 μm - 2.5 μm.

Chapter 6 Characterization of Linear Variable Filter

6.1 Introduction

The design and manufacturing procedure for LVFs has been described in the previous chapters. In this chapter, the measurement process of LVF is introduced in detail, and the analysis results of LVF samples fabricated are presented.

In order to systematically measure and characterize the spatial gradient change of the optical transmittance of the LVF as a function of physical position, the linearity of the transmittance gradient change, the bandwidth and the lateral uniformity of the transmittance must be obtained. For more accurate, convenient and repeatable measurement, an automatic measurement system was developed to measure and record the transmittance spectrum of LVFs at different physical locations.

By changing the size of the beam spot during the measurement, the profile of the LVF spectral peak is measured and compared with the theoretically simulated results. The results show that a significant averaging effect is observed in the optical transmittance spectrum when larger beam spot sizes are used, and the actual measurement results match the theoretical results after simulation calculation.

In addition, an improved Pearson VII function is proposed to fit the spectral data profile at the peak position more accurately. The mathematical superiority of this function in expressing complex peak shapes was demonstrated by cross-comparison with measured data. At the same time, a method for deconvoluting the original LVF peak position spectral image profile from the measured average peak profile is provided and verified by corresponding to the actual measured data.

6.2 Equipment for measuring LVFs and Script Automated Measurement Program

6.2.1 Equipment for measuring LVFs

The NKD-8000 (Aquila) flexible film measurement platform used to measure LVF transmittance has been briefly introduced in 3.4.1 above. An image of the equipment is shown in Figure 3.12 in Chapter 3. The internal structure of the device is shown in 3.13 in Chapter 3. It is shown in Figure 6.1 again for the convenience of introduction. In Figure 6.1, there are

several main measurement components including; the sample placement platform, the arm that provides incident light, the arm that receives reflected light, and the arm that receives transmitted light. The original incident light emitted from the incident light arm is an approximately collimated light beam with a measured spot diameter of about 3 mm. In order to reduce the diameter of the light spot focused on the LVF for measurement, an additional lens system is customized and connected to the incident light arm. After addition of the customised lens system, the light spot size emitted from the incident light arm is reduced to about 0.5 mm, which can make the spectral data obtained in measuring different physical positions of the LVF more accurate. Due to the wide spectral coverage of the device, the general measurement spectral range is set at 350 nm - 1100 nm. Therefore, it is difficult to completely eliminate chromatic aberration in the additional lens system throughout the entire spectral range. It is known that the incident light spot size of Aquila varies by about 60 μm over the entire spectral range. Such an effect has been deemed to have a negligible effect on the measured spectral trace of the LVF. The Aquila's measurement resolution bandwidths are available in selectable, varying wavelengths. When the measurement range is in the ultraviolet band, the resolution is 0.5 nm; when it is in the near-infrared range, the resolution will increase to 1 nm. The sample stage is in the middle of Figure 5.1, and the computer can control the movement of the sample to achieve the effect of the fixed spot of the sample moving. When moving, the sample stage is controlled by three stepping motor axes: the x-axis, y-axis and z-axis. The z-axis is used to adjust the height of the sample stage and generally does not move during measurement.

Figure 6. 1. Internal view of NKD-8000 Aquila.

6.2.2 Script Automated Measurement Program

The Aquila's test software includes a function that can execute scripts and automatically measure samples. Therefore, in this project, in order to make the measurement of an LVF more accurate, a script measurement program specially used for LVF measurement is written. Through the LVF automatic scanning measurement program, the LVF sample can be accurately tested according to the change of physical position in the entire spatial range, and the spectral data at different spatial positions (2D scanning) can be collected. In the measurement of Aquila, the spectral data generally refers to the transmittance T and reflectance R .

Figure 6. 2. Script program measurement flow for measuring LVF.

The script program is written based on the script development language provided by the Aquila measurement software. It is mainly used to control the movement of the LVF in the

physical space (movement of the sample stage) and the process of collecting data. The process of collecting data has been introduced in 3.4.1 above. The program flow of script control is shown in Figure 6.2.

6.3 Parameters for evaluating and characterizing LVF properties

As an example, an LVF bandpass filter In Figure 6.3, panel (a) shows schematically the appearance of an LVF sample that would be observed by the naked eye under normal conditions. The centre wavelength of the passband of the LVF will change linearly along a horizontal direction (x-axis direction) of the filter, and this change will be expressed as a gradual increase or decrease of the centre wavelength of the passband. Along the vertical (y-axis) direction, the spectrum's central band-pass transmittance wavelength should maintain relatively high lateral uniformity.

In addition to typical optical filter evaluation parameters such as the physical size, mechanical properties, peak strength of the passband, wavelength range, out-of-band blocking, and angular tolerance range, LVFs have specific evaluation parameters that can be defined through optical characterization such as: LVF spatial gradient, LVF spatial gradient linearity, LVF passband bandwidth and lateral uniformity.

Figure 6. 3. Conceptual sample diagram (a) of BPF-type LVF and its theoretical spectral transmittance curve (b).

6.3.1 Spatial gradient of LVF

The spatial gradient of an LVF refers to the gradient of the linear variation range of LVF in

space. As shown in Figure 6.3, in the x-axis direction in Figure (a), the LVF spans the physical length from point 1 to point 3 in the horizontal direction along the x-axis. Figure (b) shows that from point 1 to point 3, the central passband wavelength changes from 420 nm to 680 nm. This parameter can be defined as the special change gradient of LVF, that is, the ratio of LVF wavelength range to the physical length. The general unit is nm/mm, which indicates the range of LVF wavelength range changes at a physical position of 1 mm.

In addition, this parameter is an important parameter to characterize the spectral range of LVF. It is generally used in developing miniaturized spectrometer equipment, for example, in using one-dimensional array detectors of different sizes, which can only pass light of a certain range of wavelengths. Not only does the LVF need to match the detector in terms of operating spectral range, but its physical length also needs to match the detector's length.

6.3.2 Linearity of LVF spatial gradient

The linear relationship between the centre wavelength of the LVF passband and the corresponding physical position is called the linearity of the LVF spatial gradient. Generally, by fitting the LVF peak spectral transmission data obtained at different physical locations across the length of the LVF, a linear equation can be obtained by taking the centre point of the bandpass. There will be a deviation between the wavelength obtained by measurement and the wavelength obtained by using the linear equation formula, and generally, this error will be within a certain tolerance range. There are two ways to define and parameterize this error. One is to use the wavelength to measure the error directly. For example, take $\pm\Delta\lambda$ in the wavelength range between λ_1 and λ_2 . The other is to fit the measured data by using R^2 based on a linear equation, such as the R^2 obtained by using the linear regression equation in Microsoft Excel, used in Figures 5.11(b) and 5.12(b).

6.3.3 Passband bandwidth of LVF

The passband bandwidth of an LVF refers to the width of the transmission curve peak in the measured LVF transmission spectrum at a certain wavelength, this bandwidth will directly determine the resolution of the measurement at this wavelength. Generally, half-width at half-maximum (HWHM) is used to characterise the bandwidth of a peak. HWHM is one half of the peak width at half of the peak height. However, HWHM does not remain constant over the operating wavelength range of the LVF. For example, in Fig. 5.3(b), the HWHM at the short-wavelength position is smaller than the HWHM at the long-wavelength position. When

designing an LVF film system using a Fabry-Perot cavity structure, the HWHM of the LVF passband will be proportional to centre wavelength. This theory assumes that the refractive index remains constant within the LVF wavelength range. Therefore, it is necessary to define the relationship between the LVF's bandwidth and the passband's central wavelength. In the following discussion, the fact that the HWHM obtained by measurement is inconsistent with the HWHM fitted by the original film design will be explained.

6.3.4 Transverse Uniformity of LVF

The lateral uniformity of an LVF is such that the thickness (and therefore bandpass centre wavelength) is graded in a single direction along the length of LVF only. As shown in Figure 6.3(a), the central bandpass wavelength of the LVF along the y-axis remains constant. However, due to the manufacturing and process of the LVF film, it may not be able to meet the ideal situation. Lateral uniformity can also be defined as the error in the centre wavelength within the wavelength range covered by the LVF. However, in actual measurement, it isn't easy to perfectly align the sample manually in the x-axis and y-axis directions.

6.4 Simulation of the effect of beam spot sizes on the optical transmittance

Typically, in current spectrometer equipment, the measurement spot beam size of most spectrometers is in the millimetre range. If a uniform optical thin-film device is measured, the effect of the spot size on the measurement result will be negligible. However, for LVF optics with a gradient thickness change, the bandpass wavelength of the LVF will gradually change along the x-axis direction (as shown in Figure 5.3). Measuring the spot size used by the equipment is therefore particularly important. The smaller the spot size, the more accurate the measurement data obtained at the LVF measurement position, as the transmittance measured by the larger spot is an average result over the transmitted spot area. Therefore, ideally, the spot size used in the measurement should be close to zero to obtain the most accurate passband transmission characteristic curve of the LVF at the measurement point. It is also necessary to find a function capable of reproducing the shape of the measured spectral profiles. This is examined in the following sections.

In this simulation, the following conditions need to be met in order to simplify the simulation:

1) The refractive index of the films are constant: the HWHM of the LVF can then be

determined as a percentage of the band-pass centre wavelength;

- 2) The light beam during measurement is sufficiently collimated that the influence of the incident angle distribution can be ignored;
- 3) The incident light beam is monochromatic;
- 4) The incident light is normal to the filter surface.

The spot of the incident beam in this experiment is defined as a circle with radius r .

In this simulation, the shape of the passband transmission peak without averaging effect is defined as $T(\lambda, \lambda_c)$, where λ_c is the central wavelength of the passband. In the measurement, the spot on the LVF sample is at position x , the value of the band-pass centre wavelength depends on x , as shown in formula 6.1:

$$\lambda(x) = \lambda_c - x \cdot g_s \quad (6.1)$$

In Equation 6.1, g_s refers to the spatial gradient of the LVF.

When the position $x=0$ is covered by the light spot on the LVF sample, the measured transmittance with the averaging effect can be obtained as shown in formula 6.2:

$$T_{ave}(\lambda, \lambda_c) = \frac{1}{\pi r^2} \int_{-r}^r 2 \cdot \sqrt{r^2 - x^2} \cdot T(\lambda, \lambda_c - x \cdot g_s) dx \quad (6.2)$$

Starting from a simpler case where there is no averaging effect, if the passband is rectangular and the spot size of the measurement point approaches zero, the Transmittance is described by Equation 6.3 as follows:

$$T_{ave}(\lambda, \lambda_c) = \begin{cases} T_{max}, & \text{if } \lambda_c - \lambda_c \cdot p_{bw} \leq \lambda \leq \lambda_c + \lambda_c \cdot p_{bw} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6.3)$$

In equation 6.3, T_{max} is the amplitude of the rectangular bandpass, λ_c is the wavelength at the bandpass midpoint, and p_{bw} is a fractional quantity equal to HWHM/λ_c .

Using Mathcad 15, the expected average transmittance for different centre wavelengths λ_c on LVFs can be simulated. In Figure 6.4 (Zhou, Cai *et al.*, 2021), simulations for a rectangular bandpass are shown. Here, p_{bw} is set to 0.75, T_{max} is set to 0.92 and the LVF spatial gradient g_s is set to 11.25 nm/mm. The thick dotted line is the case where the measurement spot radius r tends to 0. The solid line is where the measurement spot radius is set to 0.5 mm. The thin

dotted line is where the measurement spot radius is set to 1.5 mm, leading to a pronounced broadening of the passband and a much reduced transmittance.

Figure 6. 4. When p_{bw} is 0.75, the design T_{max} value is 0.92, the simulated spectrum shows the original rectangular passband at each centre wavelength λ_c on the LVF (Zhou, Cai et al.,2021). As the incident light spot radius increases, the passband broadens and the transmittance is reduced.

Next, a more general case is simulated using the Pearson VII distribution function to replace the rectangular transmission bandpass in the previous simulation. The Pearson distribution is a continuous family of probability distributions originally designed for modelling significantly skewed observations (Karl Pearson, 1916). The Pearson curve family can be divided into twelve types, and the Pearson VII distribution is used here. The specific simulation is shown in formula 6.4. Since the HWHM and maximum transmittance of the peak can be directly expressed in the formula, it is relatively easy to simulate the peak through this formula.

$$T(\lambda, \lambda_c) = \frac{T_{max}HWHM^{2m}}{[HWHM^2+(2^{1/m}-1) \cdot (\lambda-\lambda_c)^2]^m} \quad (6.4)$$

Among them, I_{max} is the maximum intensity of the peak, λ_c is the centre wavelength of the bandpass, and m is a variable parameter for adjusting the peak shape. When the value of m is greater than 10, the shape in the figure changes very little for the value of m . When the value of m is equal to 1, the Pearson VII distribution function results will be more similar to the results of the Cauchy-Lorentz distribution function.

In formula 6.4, the wavelength λ is an important variable in the equation, and the peak value is the line of $\lambda = \lambda_c$ as the line of symmetry, which is $(\lambda - \lambda_c)^2$ in the formula. However, the film gradient structure of LVF introduced in section 2.1.3, as shown in Figure 2.9, when using the Fabry-Perot cavity-type LVF design method, shows a transmission bandpass that is slightly asymmetrical. That is, compared with the long-wavelength side of the LVF, the edge on the short-wavelength side will be steeper. However, the asymmetry is not particularly pronounced in this case, so modelling with a Pearson type VII distribution function is still a good fit.

As introduced above, using the bandwidth parameter p_{bw} , leads to formula 6.5.

$$T(\lambda, \lambda_c) = \frac{T_{max}(\lambda_c \cdot p_{bw})^{2m}}{[(\lambda_c \cdot p_{bw})^2 + (2^{1/m} - 1) \cdot (\lambda - \lambda_c)^2]^m} \quad (6.5)$$

Therefore, using formulas 6.2 and 6.5, Mathcad 15 is used again for simulation fitting. When the value of p_{bw} is set to 0.75, the value of T_{max} is set to 0.92, and the transmission peak diagram of the Pearson VII distribution function at different central wavelengths λ_c on the LVF is simulated, and the data in Figure 6.5 is obtained. In Figure 6.5, the Experimental Data Analysis section describes the modification of the Pearson VII function for peak fitting and will be discussed further.

Figure 6. 5. When p_{bw} is 0.75%, the design value of T_{max} is 0.92, and the result fits to the average effect of each central wavelength λ_c on the LVF using the Pearson VII distribution function (Zhou, Cai et al., 2021).

In Figure 6.5, the spatial gradient g_s of the LVF is set to 11.25 nm/mm as in the first

simulation. The thick dotted line in the figure is where the spot radius r tends to 0, the solid line is where the spot radius r is equal to 0.5 mm, and the thin dotted line is where the spot radius r is equal to 1.5 mm.

The above two examples show that the light spot size will affect the measured spectral transmission peak height and passband width in measuring LVF characteristics. The functions listed above can be more appropriately used to describe the shape of the LVF measurement peak in these examples. However, the passband shape of the thin-film system after LVF design is relatively complex and cannot be accurately described by simple functions like the above two cases. Therefore, the value must be calculated using the average effect for this more complex case. In the following example, the incident circular incident light spot is divided into 31 sections along the horizontal direction. Then, the transmittance of the 31 strip-shaped spots is summed in an area-weighted manner to obtain the average transmittance. When the film's refractive index is fixed at a constant value, the shape of the LVF passband based on the FPBP cavity design will be proportional to its central wavelength, and the calculation of its average value can be simplified. The specific simulation results are shown in Figure 6.6.

Figure 6. 6. When p_{bw} is 0.835%, the LVF transmission spectrum using the Fabry-Perot cavity passband design, the simulation results of the average effect at each central wavelength λ_c (Zhou, Cai et al., 2021).

In Figure 6.6, the spatial gradient g_s of the LVF is set to 11.25 nm/mm as in the previous simulation. The refractive index of the high-refractive index material is fixed at 2.3113, the refractive index of the low-refractive index material is fixed at 1.4558, and the refractive index of the substrate is fixed at 1.5152. The thick dashed line in the figure is when the

incident light spot radius tends to 0, the solid line is when the spot radius is 0.5 mm, and the thin dashed line is when the spot radius is 1.5 mm.

The following conclusions can be drawn based on the above three simulation results under different conditions. First, the most important point is that the spot size of the incident light at the time of measurement greatly influences the averaging effect produced in the measurement results. Secondly, when the peak heights of the original transmission spectrum of the theoretical value are the same, the average peak transmission height on the short-wavelength side is lower than that on the long-wavelength side. Finally, by adding more conditions for simulation, it is concluded that the passband bandwidth and spatial gradient, g_s of the LVF will have a greater impact on the average effect produced by the incident spot size.

Therefore, in the characterization and measurement of an LVF, the incident light spot size of the measurement equipment will have a significant impact on the measured results. In the characterisation of an LVF and the subsequent development of an LVF based spectrometer, the standardization of the size of the light source and detector should be considered.

6.5 Actual measurement results and analysis

In chapter 4, the fabrication procedure of the LVFs produced during this work was presented. The fabrication was performed using the Microdyn sputtering tool. As previously discussed, the Microdyn is a large-scale thin-film sputtering device based on the microwave-assisted pulsed plasma reactive magnetron sputtering process. The LVF is a band-pass filter based on a three-cavity Fabry-Perot structure. It uses a thin-film film structure composed of a high-refractive-index material, Nb_2O_5 , and low-refractive-index material SiO_2 deposited onto microscope slide glass.

6.5.1 Measurement of an LVF under relatively small incident spot size

According to the previous simulation results, when the spot radius is 0.4 mm, the average effect on the measurement results is relatively small. It is easier to find the measured data's exact spectral bandwidth and transmission peak position by fitting the data with the functions described above. Using the Pearson VII function mentioned above to perform a fitting comparison with the measurement results, the results do not fit perfectly, as shown by the dotted line in Figure 6.7. It can be seen that the data results fitted by the Pearson VII function are too sharp at the tip of the peak to match the measured results. Therefore, try to replace the

power 2 in formula 6.5 with the power exponent n so that more peak shape description capabilities will be obtained in the graph, as shown in formula 6.6.

$$T(\lambda, \lambda_c) = \frac{T_{max} \cdot (\lambda_c \cdot p_{bw})^{n \cdot m}}{[(\lambda_c \cdot p_{bw})^n + (2^{1/m} - 1) \cdot (\lambda - \lambda_c)^n]^m} \quad (6.6)$$

Figure 6. 7. Fitting of the LVF transmission data using Pearson VII function and modified Pearson VII function and comparing with actual measurement results (Zhou, Cai *et al.*, 2021).

In Figure 6.7, the x-shaped line shows the transmission spectrum data obtained using the Aquila spectrometer equipment to measure the centre position of the LVF when the incident light spot r is 0.4 mm. The dotted line is the simulated LVF transmission data fitted using the formula 6.5 above and the Pearson VII function. It can be seen that there is a large difference between the top part of the peak and the actual value. The solid line is Formula 6.6, obtained by improving Formula 6.5. The data obtained after fitting the improved Pearson VII function is almost consistent with the measured data.

Fitting the measured LVF optical transmittance data determines the optical specifications of the LVF such as bandpass central wavelength, the transmission bandpass peak height, the transmission bandpass bandwidth, the spatial gradient of the LVF, the linearity and the lateral uniformity, etc. Figure 6.8 presents the LVF spectral transmission data measured for an LVF with a physical length of 44 mm. In the plot, the fitted results agree with the measured results. And it is consistent with the conclusion of the average peak effect obtained above. The transmission peak height of the short-wavelength region on the left in the figure is lower than the peak height of the middle part. However, the height of the transmission peak in the long wavelength region measured in the figure is slightly lower than that of the middle portion. This result may be due to the partial dispersion of the beam-focusing lens used in the

measurement. Because the material of the lens has a low refractive index, the size of the beam spot in the near-infrared band is larger than that in other wavelength ranges, resulting in such measurement results.

Figure 6. 8. When the incident light spot radius r is 0.4 mm, and the LVF sample is has a physical length of 44 mm, and the transmission measurement results are obtained at intervals of 4 mm.

In Figure 6.8, the x-shaped line shows the spectral transmission results of LVF samples measured at intervals of 4 mm when the incident light spot radius r is 0.4 mm. The solid line is the result of fitting the LVF transmission data using Equation 6.6, a modified Pearson VII function.

Figure 6. 9. When the incident light spot radius r is 0.4 mm, the measured relationship between the centre wavelength of the transmission passband and the physical position of the LVF shows the linearity of the LVF (Zhou, Cai et al., 2021).

In Figure 6.9, the central wavelength of the passband transmission parameter is plotted

against its physical position on the LVF, and the linearity relationship diagram of the LVF is obtained. By using the linear regression equation, it can be obtained that the spatial gradient S_g of the LVF is 10.832 nm/mm, the error R^2 is 0.9991, and the linearity deviation of the LVF in the wavelength range of 450 nm – 900 nm is within $\pm 1\%$.

Figure 6.9, in addition to the linearity obtained from the LVF measurement, also shows that the central wavelength of the passband decreases when the HWHM tends to decrease. That is because the refractive index dispersion occurs in the stacked film material used in the multilayer membrane system. In the central position of LVF, where the central wavelength of the passband is 674.9 nm, the percentage of HWHM in the central wavelength is 0.83%, and FWHM is 11.2 nm.

Figure 6. 10. The lateral uniformity data obtained when the measuring equipment's incident light spot radius r is 0.4 mm. (a) Transverse uniformity measurement at 2 mm intervals in the y -axis direction over a range of 20 mm, with a zoomed-in view of the top peak. (b) A plot of the central wavelength versus the physical position on the y -axis.

In this study, the developed LVF measurement script has the same function in the y -axis and

the scan measurement capability in the x-axis direction, which provides the ability to measure the lateral uniformity of the LVF. The measurement is performed by using a beam spot with an incident light spot radius of 0.4 mm, as shown in Figure 6.10. In Fig. 6.10(a), the entire transverse uniformity peak profile measured along the y-axis is shown and zoomed in on the peak location, showing subtle differences in the transmission profile at different locations.

In Fig. 6.10(b), the central wavelength of the transmission peak is obtained by data fitting, and the trend error of all measured values is within $\pm 0.5\%$, which indicates that the LVF fabricated in this paper has very high lateral uniformity. The trend line in the graph also shows that the sample placed on the sample stage of the measuring device may deviate slightly from the absolute orientation of the y-axis.

6.5.2 Fitting the peak profile of the LVF using the averaging effect

Figure 6. 11. Diagram of the steps in the method to start simulating the averaged results with a known peak profile.

From the previous sections of this chapter, the influence of the finite light spot size averaging

effect on the optical transmittance measurement results of the manufactured LVFs has been introduced. The desired peak profile is known through modelling , and the average effect is simulated through the peak profile. In this section, the peak profile will be simulated in turn by using the averaging effect, such as using a specific size of the incident light spot when measuring the LVF passband and then mathematically fitting the original passband peak profile. The general fitting steps are shown in Flowchart 6.11.

In order to test the feasibility of the method introduced above, the average peak profile in Figure 6.6 is used to calculate the theoretical passband profile of the three-cavity Fabry-Perot LVF when the incident spot radius r is 1.5 mm. The calculation result is shown as the x-shaped line in Figure 6.12.

Figure 6.12. Results of the data used to validate the description of the LVF peak profile by mean effects (Zhou, Cai et al., 2021).

In Figure 6.12, the measured incident light spot radius r is 1.5 mm, and the LVF with a spatial gradient of 11.25 nm/mm is measured. The goal is to deduce the original peak passband profile from simulated measurements with averaging effects. The x-shaped line in the figure is the simulated measurement data introduced above, the white dotted line is the original peak passband profile inferred from the average effect in this section, and the black line is the original LVF design peak profile. The white dotted line matches the black line quite well, which proves that the modified Pearson VII function has a high adaptability to the adjustment of the peak value according to the formula 6.6 proposed above. In the figure, the modified Equation 6.6 uses the parameters $I_{max} = 0.95$, $\lambda_c = 675 \text{ nm}$, $P_{bw} = 0.814\%$, $m = 0.656$, $n =$

8.38. The shape modified by this formula can be Cauchy-Lorentz, flat and square peaks, etc.

The average effect of the LVF measurement has been demonstrated by using the formula 6.6 in the previous section, and the average effect is proven again by the actual measurement results. Figure 6.13 shows the LVF measurement results similar to those in Figure 6.8. The difference is that the incident light spot radius r used in the measurement differs, and the spot radius r used in Figure 6.13 is 1.5 mm.

Figure 6. 13. Measured optical transmittance results for a 44 mm length LVF using a spot size of 1.5 mm, measured in increments of 4 mm along the length of the LVF.

Next, the results of the simulation are used to extract the actual passband profile of the LVF. This method is used to verify the feasibility of extracting the original passband profile from the actual measured data of LVF. The transmission data measured at the centre of the LVF is used here as a sample for calculation, and the results are shown in Figure 6.14. In Figure 6.14(a), the x-shaped line is the transmission data obtained when the measuring beam radius is 0.4 mm. The solid line is the peak profile extracted from the average effect when the spot radius is 0.4 mm, and the dotted line is the transmission data obtained when the spot radius is 0.45 mm. In Figure 6.14(b), the x-shaped line is the transmission data measured when the spot radius of the measuring beam is 1.5 mm. The solid line is the transmission peak profile extracted from the average effect measured at a spot radius of 1.5 mm.

Figure 6. 14. Extracted original profile of the measured passband at the centre of the LVF by using the modified Pearson VII function, Equation 4.6. (a) the extracted spectral profile using a beam spot size of 0.4 mm (b) the extracted spectral profile using a beam spot size of 1.5 mm (Zhou, Cai *et al.*, 2021).

Figure 6.14 shows the peak profiles extracted using two incident light spots with different radii. The results show that the peak profiles extracted from the data measured by the incident light spots with different radii are very similar. However, although the transmission data at the same position is measured on the LVF, the transmission peaks of the actual measurement data under different measurement spot radii are quite different from the extracted peak profiles. The reason for such a situation may be that the uniformity of light intensity in the light plate area is relatively scattered due to the different radii of the incident light spot. It may also be due to the measurement error in the spot size measurement, as a small error will cause a large change in the data when the peak profile is extracted.

6.6 Summary

In this chapter, a 2D automated measurement system for sample scanning is developed based on the Aquila NKD8000 spectrophotometer configuration. The system is based on the original light source of the equipment, a light source beam spot focusing device, a movable sample platform for placing samples, photodetectors for receiving transmitted light and reflected light and control software for spectrum collection.

By using this system, the measurement and characterization of the three-cavity Fabry-Perot type LVF sample designed and manufactured in this work is carried out. The main characteristic parameters of an LVF are simulated and discussed. The main characteristic

parameters include: the spatial gradient of the LVF, spatial gradient linearity of the LVF, passband bandwidth of the LVF at different physical positions and lateral uniformity of LVF. The basic physical properties of the LVF produced and used in this work were obtained through measurement and analysis, and the specific parameters are shown in Table 6.1.

Table 6. 1. Specific characteristic parameters of the visible LVF produced in this work.

Attribute Name	Value (unit)
Physical size (mm)	Length 44, width 20
Effective wavelength range (nm)	450 - 900
Passband wavelength at the centre position (nm)	674.9
Spatial gradient of LVF (nm/mm)	10.832
Linearity of LVF	0.9991
HWHM as a percentage of centre wavelength (%)	0.83%
FWHM at the centre position (nm)	11.2
Transverse Uniformity (nm)	± 0.05

Based on the above basic properties of the LVF, the spectral transmission peak parameters of the LVFs are modelled and analysed. A rectangular function, Pearson VII function and other methods are used to simulate the peak parameters of the LVF and compare them with the actual measurement results. After comparison, it is found that the measurement results of the LVF are easily affected by the spot size of the incident light used in the measurement, and the measured data will display an obvious averaging effect. Therefore, by using the incident light spot with a radius of 0.4 mm and 1.5 mm to measure the same position on the LVF, it is verified that the size of the incident light spot will produce an average effect and affect the measurement results.

In order to make the measurement results of the LVF match the results generated by the function simulation, the Pearson VII function is improved. The improved Pearson VII function is more flexible in describing the peak. It has the shape of the Cauchy-Lorentz function and can transform the peak profile into a flat top or a rectangle, so it is more suitable for describing the complex spectral peak profile. Finally, the improved Pearson VII function is used to complete the simulation of the spectral peak profile, and the simulation results can completely match the actual LVF measurement results.

Finally, a mathematical method for extracting raw spectral transmission data from measurements known to have averaging effects is also proposed. The method is verified by reversely deriving the theoretical passband profile fitted by using the incident light spot with a radius of 1.5 mm. Then, the extracted peak profile was compared with the spectral curve of the original design and found to be a good match. By comparison with the measured LVF data, the method's feasibility was verified.

Chapter 7 The Fabrication of a Miniature Spectrometer

This chapter introduces the miniaturized spectrometer based on an LVF. First, the overall structure of the miniaturized spectrometer is introduced, then, the selection of each component is discussed followed by a description of the control system, and finally the experimental scan procedure is introduced, and the measured results are displayed.

7.1 Structure and principle of Miniature spectrometer

7.1.1 System structure of micro spectrometer

In chapter 1, spectrometers are introduced and classified. A common spectrometer system is composed of the light source, relay optics, light dispersion system, collection optics and detecting system as the basic components. It is often used to measure and study the wavelength, intensity and spectral peak profile of the sample under test.

In this work, different spectrometer version configurations were designed, tested and iteratively improved. Three different micro-spectrometer versions were built, differing mainly by the LVF optomechanical transfer mechanism used to control the spatial location of the LVF in relation to the incident light spot and the spectrometer's detector. The three miniaturized spectrometer systems' basic components are roughly the same. In addition to the three basic parts introduced above, its main structure includes an optical collimation system and a focusing and converging system.

Light sources and illumination systems are the basic building blocks of all spectroscopic instruments. The main function of the light source in the spectrometer is to provide enough energy so that the sample to be measured can be excited to generate a spectrum. The light source needs sufficient output power and stability, and the emitted light energy will be transmitted to the subsequent system. The energy of the light source will directly affect the signal strength of the entire miniaturized spectrometer. The collimation system and focusing system serve as the light source. In order to maximise the optical throughput (ratio of total emitted optical power to the detected optical power), the light emitted by the light source is processed to minimize the loss of light energy so that the final sensor can receive improved signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

The first two versions of the miniature spectrometer were improved because of mechanical instability and lack of reproducibility in the data between measurements. Version 1 of the

miniaturized spectrometer model uses a gear transmission configuration to move the core light-splitting device, in this case, an LVF. Versions 2 and 3 use a linear screwdriver mechanism to move the LVF. However, because the version 2 uses a smaller motor power, an improvement was made to version 3 which included optimizing the stepper motor model and re-designing the entire unit to a modular design. The version 1 configuration is significantly different from versions 2 and 3 whereas 2 and 3 are rather similar.

Version 1: Gear-driven LVF-based miniaturized spectrometer configuration

As introduced above, the gear-driven LVF-based miniaturized spectrometer structure is shown in Figure 7.1. As shown in the figure, it mainly includes three parts: the optical system, the mechanical structure, the electronics including a single chip microcontroller unit (MCU).

Figure 7. 1. The structure of a miniaturized spectrometer based on gear transmission.

The optical system includes a light source, a beam-focusing lens, and a beam-collimating unit. The mechanical structure part mainly includes the LVF moving module with the stepping motor as the main body, and the LVF is evenly moved through the gear transmission on the stepping motor. The MCU control module includes a photoelectric detection module and a signal processing circuit. Generally speaking, the miniaturized spectrometer system mainly drives the LVF mobile module to move in a straight line at a uniform speed along the horizontal direction by controlling the gear rotation at the head of the stepping motor. The light emitted by the light source, after being converged and collimated by the optical module,

first transmits through the surface of the measured sample, then passes through the LVF through the optical fibre, and then is received by the photoelectric detection module and converted into an electrical signal. Finally, the required spectral information is generated through computer software processing.

Versions 2 and 3: LVF-based miniaturized spectrometer structure with screw drive

Spectrometer versions 2 and 3 each adopt a linear screw drive actuator as the optomechanical transfer mechanism, which makes the moving distance of the LVF more accurate and stable. The version 2 of the miniaturized spectrometer model is shown in Figure 7.2.

Figure 7. 2. Miniaturized spectrometer version 2, driven by a linear screw drive.

Spectrometer version 3 is similar to version 2, but the stepper motor is replaced with a model with a higher torque. At the same time, the modular design was introduced to allow for faster replacement of parts, as shown in Figure 7.3.

Figure 7. 3. Miniaturized spectrometer version 3, driven by a linear screw drive. A modular design was also introduced.

7.1.2 Optical System Module

In miniaturized spectrometer equipment, the optical system part is essential. In this work, the optical system part mainly includes five optical components; light source, compound parabolic concentrator (CPC), the convex lens, fibre collimator and optical fibre. The structure is shown in Figure 7.4.

Figure 7. 4. Schematic diagram of the optical system structure.

In this work, the research object is a spectrometer in the visible light and near-infrared spectral range, so selecting a suitable light source is necessary when measuring different samples. A halogen lamp is used as the light source in the visible light range, and the operating wavelength range covers 360 nm - 760 nm. In the near-infrared range, LED lamps with different wavelengths are used as light sources, and the operating wavelength range is within 1.7 μm - 2.3 μm .

A compound parabolic concentrator (CPC) is a low-focusing device not used for imaging functions. It can collect and converge the light emitted by the light source into the required receiving range as much as possible within the design receiving angle range, and the principle is shown in Figure 7.5. The light source's light will converge after multiple reflections in the CPC. The advantage is that the energy loss of the light source is small, and the divergent light is effectively collected to achieve the ideal concentration ratio. For this application, a CPC is used to collect the emitted source light and collimate it, before launching the light into the system's objective lens.

Figure 7. 5. Building a CPC and its design principles (Tian et al., 2018).

The CPC design process is presented in the paper by Tian et al. Using Snell's law, Fermat's principle and the ray tracing method, the following CPC is designed, as shown in Figure 7.6.

Figure 7. 6. CPC (a) Image of a CPC (b) Design model mesh of the CPC optical surface.

The numerical aperture of the fibre on its own produces an optical emission pattern with a large cone half angle that would not be detrimental to the spectral resolution of the device as a result of the large spot size averaging effect discussed in the previous chapters. As a consequence of this, an optical fibre collimator lens package was chosen to collimate the optical fibre emission profile incident on the LVF. Its function is to convert the light transmitted in the fibre into a collimated beam or to couple the light received from the outside into the fibre. Common fibre collimators can be divided into two types, one is a collimator that directly contacts the inside of the fibre, and the other is a method that passes through a mechanical section when connecting to the fibre. Finally, the F260SMA-A collimator from Thorlabs was selected, as shown in Figure 7.7. It was chosen because of the size of the visible and near-infrared photodetectors chosen in this paper. The effective size of the visible light detector is $2.4 \times 2.3 \text{ mm}^2$, and the effective size of the near-infrared detector is $1.0 \times 1.0 \text{ mm}^2$.

Figure 7. 7. Thorlabs' F260SMA-A collimator.

7.1.3 Core device linear variable filter

In the LVF spectrometer, an LVF replaces a prism or grating as the wavelength selection element. Compared with traditional optical structures, it is more suitable for the miniaturization of spectrometers due to its small size, high stability and lightweight.

The LVF is fabricated using a microwave plasma-assisted pulsed DC reactive sputtering process. Using Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2 as high and low refractive index film materials respectively, LVF samples in the visible light (450 nm - 900 nm) and near-infrared (1.5 μm - 2.5 μm) bands were fabricated, as shown in Figure 7.8. Chapters 4 and 5 detail the design, fabrication and characterisation procedures for the LVF.

Figure 7. 8. Photographs of (a) visible light (450 nm - 900 nm) LVF (b) near-infrared (1.5 μm - 2.5 μm) LVF.

7.1.4 Control Systems and Detectors

MCU (Micro Controller Unit)

The MCU, also known as a single-chip microcomputer, is a kind of Central Processing Unit (CPU). The MCU has a small footprint and energy consumption and has integrated core

memory, counter, USB, analog-to-digital conversion, UART, PLC, DMA and other peripheral interfaces, and even an LCD driver circuit are integrated on a single chip, forming a chip level computer system (Subbaroybhat, 2021). In this work, the main function of the MCU is to control the stepper motor to drive the LVF movement, collect and process the electrical signals measured by the photodetector, and finally transmit them to the computer.

There are many unbiased manufacturing brands and programming frameworks for MCUs today, but they are generally divided into three types: 8-bit, 16-bit, and 32-bit MCUs. The difference between these three types of MCUs lies in the speed of operation. Still, because MCUs are often used to perform a single automation task, one job is performed repeatedly (Subbaroybhat, 2021). Therefore, it is necessary to consider various factors for different tasks before choosing an MCU with appropriate computing power. Considering the comprehensive cost and the required functions, the MSP430G2553 microcontroller was finally selected as the control unit used in this work, as shown in Figure 7.9. The MSP430 microcontroller that appeared on the market at the end of the 20th century is a microcontroller developed by TI. The difference between this chip and other microcontrollers is that it integrates many digital and analogue peripherals with different functions. Its advantages are: (1) 16-bit chip processor, processing instruction set is efficient, supports 40 ns instruction cycle and 25 MHz clock crystal oscillator. (2) Low energy consumption only needs 1.8 V - 3.6 V voltage to work. (3) Various functions, built-in watchdog, timer, serial communication interface, ADC sampling, DMA and I/O and other functions. (5) Cost-effective, the development environment is easy to use, and the development cycle is relatively short. (6) The working state is stable and will not be affected by too much environment.

Figure 7. 9. Image of the MSP430G2553 microcontroller development board.

Stepper Motor and Stepper Motor Driver Board

A stepper motor is an electric drive motor that converts electrical pulse signals into corresponding angular or linear displacement. The stepper motor is composed of a stator and a rotor. Whenever the stepper motor receives a pulse signal, the rotor turns an angle or advances a certain distance. There are many structural forms and classification methods of stepper motors. According to the excitation method, they can be divided into reluctance type, permanent magnet type and mixed magnetic type. According to the number of phases, they can be divided into single-phase, two-phase, three-phase and multi-equal forms. Different types of stepper motors have different torque and frequency characteristics. Therefore, selecting the stepper motor according to the specific application is necessary.

In this article, the purpose of using the stepper motor is mainly to make the LVF move in a straight line at a uniform speed through the rotation of the stepper motor and duration of the spectral scan. At the same time, because it is necessary to stop the LVF for a small distance each time and use a detector to convert the optical signal into an electrical signal for reception, the position accuracy of the stepping motor must be relatively high. Factors that affect the position accuracy is the phase number, step angle and rotation resolution of the stepper motor. When the number of phases of the stepping motor is large, the step angle is small, and the rotation resolution is high, which means that its position accuracy is also high. Therefore, this characteristic defined the choice of the stepper motors used in the miniaturized spectrometers versions 1 and 2. This motor is relatively small compared to other types on the market. Its model is Nanotec's two-phase stepper motor ST2018, its step angle is 1.8° , and its size is NEMA8 (20 mm). The wiring and physical diagram of the motor are shown in Figure 7.10.

Figure 7. 10. Nanotec's ST2018 stepper motor (a) Schematic diagram of ST2018 wiring diagram (b) Image of the ST2018.

The model of the driver board used with the ST2018 stepping motor is DRV8835, and its physical and schematic diagrams are shown in Figure 7.11.

Figure 7. 11. ST2018 stepper motor driver board DRV8835 (a) DRV8835 driver board schematic diagram (b) Image of DRV8835 driver development board.

As shown in Figure 7.11(a), the DRV8835 stepper motor driver board integrates two drivers for the stepper motor drive, which output a maximum current of 1.5 A to the two H-bridges of the stepper motor. By sequentially outputting current to the H-bridge, the stepper motor can rotate step by step, and its operating principle is shown in Figure 7.12. Its drive type is related to the input interface, and common input interfaces include step/direction, phase/enable, etc. Step/direction refers to sending a pulse on the Step pin, the driver changes its output to make the motor perform a step, and the level on the Direction pin determines the direction of rotation. Phase/enable refers to the stator winding of each phase. The potential of Enable determines whether the phase is energized, and the potential of Phase determines the direction of the phase current (Carmine Fiore, 2022).

When the two-phase stepper motor ST2018 is working, it first receives the control signal from the host computer, the pulse signal is transmitted to the control unit of the driver board, and the driver module sends out current to make the stepper motor work. The feedback unit on a stepper motor is used to protect the motor from damage due to incorrect commands.

Figure 7. 12. Flow chart of the working principle of the stepping motor and the driver board.

The common two-phase stepper motor working mode can be divided into wave drive, full-step drive and half-step drive. In these three working modes, the current direction change is determined by the arrangement of the stator coils. In order to move the rotor, it is necessary to control the direction of the current while energizing the coil. The direction of the current determines the direction of the electromagnetic field generated by the collar itself.

A pattern in which only one phase is energized at a time is called a wave mode, as shown in Figure 7.13. Flowing the current from the positive potential of one phase to the negative potential is called positive flow, as shown in the figure below from A+ to A-. If the current flows from negative potential to positive potential, it is called negative flow. The figure below divides it into four steps from left to right. The current flows positively or negatively in phase A or B, and the rotor moves in a circle in the middle with the change of the electromagnetic field. These four steps constitute a cycle.

Figure 7. 13. Wave pattern of stepper motor operation (Carmine Fiore, 2022).

When the two phases are energized simultaneously, it is called full-step mode, as shown in Figure 7.14. The principle is similar to the wave mode above, but because both phases of the motor are energized at the same time, more current flows in the stepper motor, and the resulting magnetic field will be stronger, and therefore the torque will be higher.

Figure 7. 14. Full-step mode of stepper motor operation (Carmine Fiore, 2022).

After combining the wave pattern and the full-step pattern, the new pattern formed is called the half-step pattern, as shown in Figure 7.15. In this mode, the rotation angle of the motor rotor is more precise, from the original phase change of 90° to 45° , so the distance of each

step is shorter and more precise. But the disadvantage is that the torque will fluctuate due to single-phase and two-phase energization.

Figure 7. 15. Half-step mode of stepper motor operation (Carmine Fiore, 2022).

In the above figure three working modes of the stepping motor, the pulse signal sent by the MCU repeatedly changes between on and off, and each on or off is recorded as a pulse signal. The command of a pulse signal will be converted into electric energy for powering the stepper motor after being received by the motor driver board. The on and off of the voltage correspond to the "High" level signal and the "Low" level signal, as shown in Figure 7.16.

Figure 7. 16. Relationship between "High" and "Low" level signals and motor step angle.

In the early version 1 spectrometer, the stepper motor can be controlled very precisely. Therefore, the stepper motor rotation step angle of 1.8° is defined as one step, and it is only necessary to calculate the number of steps of the stepper motor to move the LVF and complete the journey accurately. This process does not require complex calculations and adjustments, and it can work normally with only the driver. A two-phase stepper motor with a step angle of 1.8° takes 200 steps to rotate the circumference of a stepper motor bearing.

Therefore, the step angle of the stepper motor can be defined as θ_{step} , and the total rotation angle θ_{sum} of the stepper motor is the relationship between the step angle θ_{step} and the pulse signal P .

$$\theta_{sum} = \theta_{step} \cdot P \quad (7.1)$$

Four wires control the two-phase stepper motor ST2018 used in this project. The control signal sent by the control board to the motor is shown in Figure 7.17.

STEP	A	B	A\<	B\<		CCW
1	+	+	-	-	 CCW	
2	-	+	+	-		
3	-	-	+	+		
4	+	-	-	+		

Figure 7. 17 Rotation control signal of ST2018 stepper motor.

After converting the gear transmission mode of spectrometer version 1 to the linear lead screw drive of spectrometer version 2, the conversion reduces the step angle, increasing the accuracy of each step. However, due to the excessive friction between the screw and its support base or between the LVF support frame and the model ground when using the screw drive, the ST2018 stepper motor may sometimes lose steps or get stuck. As a result, spectrometer version 3 was designed where the ST2018 with a holding torque of 1.8 Ncm was replaced with a 17HS4401 with a holding torque of 42 Ncm, as shown in Figure 7.18.

Figure 7. 18. 42 mm width stepping motor 17HS4401 physical picture.

The stepper motor is the same as the ST2018 two-phase stepper motor, and the step angle is also 1.8° . The driver used in conjunction with the 17HS4401 stepping motor is gradually being driven by a TB6600 two-phase motor, as shown in Figure 7.19, (a) is the wiring diagram and (b) image of the driver. Its input voltage is DC 9 V - 40 V, and the recommended switching power supply is 5 A.

Figure 7. 19. TB6600 stepper motor driver (a) TB6600 wiring diagram (b) Image of the TB6600 driver module.

Photodetector

The function of photodetectors is to convert light signals into electrical signals, and the mechanism involved is based on the photovoltaic effect of semiconductor materials. The photovoltaic effect refers to the phenomenon that light causes a potential difference between different parts of inhomogeneous semiconductors or semiconductors combined with metals.

The basic working principle of a photodetector includes the following steps. First, photogenerated carriers are generated on the photodetector through light irradiation. The carriers then diffuse, or drift, in the photodetector, eventually creating an electrical current. Finally, the photocurrent is amplified in the amplifying circuit and converted into a voltage signal to be detected. Commonly used photoconductive detector materials for visible band wavelengths include CdS, CdSe, CdTe, Si and Ge. In the near infrared, common materials include; PbS, InGaAs, PbSe and InSb.

Figure 7. 20. Image of BPW21R Silicon Photodiode detector in through-hole TO can package.

In this work, detectors in the visible and near-infrared bands need to be used in conjunction with the visible and near infrared LVFs respectively. Therefore, the BPW21R Si PN photodiode is selected as the detector in the visible light band and has a peak photo-response at 565 nm. An image of the through-hole TO can package is shown in Figure 7.20 which contains an Si photodiode. In the infrared light band, an uncooled Pb25S PbS detector is used, and has a peak photo-response at is 2.4 μm , image shown in Figure 7.21.

Figure 7. 21. Image of uncooled PB25S10104S type PbS detector in through-hole TO can package.

The BPW21R is a planar Si PN photodiode with a TO-5 hermetic package dedicated to high-precision linear data measurement. The BPW21R is suitable for this work due to its high dark resistance and linear photocurrent response under illumination.

PB25S10104S is an integrated detector with an uncooled photoconductive unit, contained within a TO-46 hermetic package, and its spectral range is between 1 μm - 3 μm . The photoconductive detector is widely used in analytical, security and radiometric work.

7.2 Control system design and interface program

7.2.1 MSP430 MCU and IDE Introduction

The MSP430 is a 16-bit single-chip microcomputer launched by Texas Instruments. Different MSP430 series integrate peripherals such as; Flash memory, RAM, timer, GPIO, ADC and serial communication module. The MSP430 consumes very low power during operation, making it ideal for battery-powered devices or work requiring high power consumption.

The MSP430G2553 MCU development board used in this work, as shown in Figure 7.22, belongs to the MSP430G2xxx series. The MCU chip's main features are as follows: the CPU operation speed can reach 16 MHz, the operating voltage range is between 1.8 V - 3.6 V, 16 KB of Flash memory and 512 bytes of RAM, etc. Integrated peripherals in the MSP430G2553 include GPIO, timer, ADC, comparator, USCI serial communication and capacitive touch. It also supports 20 pins, making connecting to the chip easier for external devices for prototyping. All addressing instructions can read/write access to the port control register, and each I/O port has an independently programmable pull-up/pull-down resistor. Registers can be used to edit the output state of the pins, and all 20 pins can perform bit operations. In addition, it also provides an onboard flash memory simulation tool, which can be directly connected to the computer, making it easier to program, debug and do other development work on the project.

Figure 7. 22. MSP430G2553 MCU development board produced by TI.

The Integrated Development Environment (IDE), which refers to tools for software development, including editors, compilers, debuggers, graphical user interfaces and other applications that integrate multiple tools. The MSP430G2553 MCU controller chosen for use in this work has two official development software provided by TI: Code Composer Studio (CCS) and Energia. CCS is an IDE for TI DSPs, microprocessors and application processors. It includes compilers, source code editors, project build environments, debuggers, profilers, emulators, and many other features for each TI device family. Energia is a LaunchPad that introduces Wiring and Arduino frameworks based on TI MSP430. In comparison, Energia has a lower threshold for use, and it is easy to get started with an Arduino foundation. Therefore, this article selects Energia as the compilation environment for the stepper motor control program.

7.2.2 Programming of MCU

In this article, the main purpose of programming the MCU is to control the stepper motor precisely, collect data signals from the photodetector and communicate with the computer. The Energia IDE is mainly used to compile the control program of the stepper motor.

Stepper motor

The control principle of the stepper motor has been introduced in section 7.1.4. The MCU sends signals to the stepper motor driver board, and then the driver board controls the motor's stepping direction, stepping mode and stepping speed. The stepper motor control program used in this work was compiled in the Energia IDE.

Details of the procedure, written using the Energia software (an Arduino IDE framework provided by Texas Instruments for controlling the MSP430 LaunchPad), for controlling a stepper motor with an MCU, have been attached in Appendix 3.

Conversion of Analog and Digital signals

In the MSP430 type MCU, a built-in digital-to-analogue converter (ADC) is included, which can be used to convert analogue signals into digital signals. In MSP430, the ADC can collect the analogue signals of multiple channels, convert them into digital signals and provide them to the MCU for centralized processing.

The ADC needs a clock to drive the conversion. MSP430 provides multiple clock sources. You can choose the appropriate clock source according to your needs. The clock source can

be selected by setting the bits in the control register.

The sampling time refers to when the ADC samples the analogue signal. In MSP430, the sampling time can be adjusted by setting bits in the control register. A longer sampling time improves sampling accuracy but increases the ADC's response time.

The resolution of an ADC refers to how accurately it can convert an analogue signal to a digital signal. In MSP430, the resolution of ADC can be adjusted by setting bits in the control register. Higher resolution can improve the accuracy of ADC but will increase the conversion time and power consumption. Its resolution size can be expressed as the following formula 7.2.

$$R = \frac{U_R}{2^{10}-1} \quad (7.2)$$

U_R in the above formula, 7.2 is the reference voltage in the ADC. MSP430G2553's reference voltage is 3.3, 2.5 or 1.5 V, and the corresponding resolution is 3.22, 2.44 and 1.47 mV. The reference voltage is used in the ADC to convert the analogue signal into a digital signal. In the MSP430, you can choose internal reference voltage or external reference voltage. The internal reference voltage is usually 1.5 V or 2.5 V, while an external circuit can provide the external reference voltage.

After the ADC converts the analogue signal into a digital signal, it can be stored in different data formats. In the MSP430, you can choose left-justified or right-justified data format. Left-justified data formats store the high-order bits in one register, while right-justified data formats store the low-order bits in one register.

The ADC of the MSP430 can operate by means of interruption. When the ADC completes the conversion, an interrupt can be triggered to notify the microcontroller to process the conversion result.

In conclusion, in the MSP430 ADC is a very useful module that can easily convert analogue signals to digital signals, and parameters such as sampling time, resolution, reference voltage, data format, etc., can be adjusted by setting the control register bits.

Establishment of serial communication

The MSP430 can communicate with other devices through serial communication (UART). Serial port communication is a protocol based on asynchronous transmission, which connects

peripherals and computers through data signal lines and can perform two-way data transmission. However, this communication method uses fewer data lines, and the communication distance and transmission speed are relatively limited.

There is a built-in serial port hardware module in the MSP430 called USCI (Universal Serial Communications Interface), which supports various serial port protocols, including UART, SPI and I2C. In serial communication, setting a baud rate to specify the data transmission rate is also necessary. The higher the baud rate, the faster the data transfer rate. In the MSP430, the baud rate can be set by setting bits in the USCI control register. At the same time, it is also necessary to set the clock source and frequency divider to generate the correct baud rate clock.

Serial communication needs to define the data format for transmission, including data bits, stop bits and parity bits. In the MSP430, these parameters can be defined by setting the bits of the USCI control register. The interrupt function in the MSP430 is supported by the USCI module, which can trigger an interrupt when receiving or sending is completed. That allows the microcontroller to perform other tasks while waiting for the serial communication to complete, increasing the system's efficiency. The general serial port communication method is realized by software or hardware. Using hardware can greatly simplify code writing but requires some external circuit support. Using the software method requires writing more codes, but the details of the serial communication can be controlled more flexibly.

The establishment of serial communication requires a few steps. First of all, it is necessary to determine the serial communication parameters, including baud rate, data bits, stop bits, parity bits, etc. These parameters must match the external device receiving the communication to carry out normal communication. Next, you need to configure the IO port of the MSP430 so that the serial data input and output can be sent to the correct pins. In the MSP430, you can use the P1SEL and P1SEL2 registers to configure the IO port of the serial port and set it to the corresponding UART function. Then, you need to set the USCI module in the MSP430. Its function is a hardware module responsible for serial communication, and it needs to be configured accordingly before it can be used. UCAXCTL0 and UCAXCTL1 registers can be used to set the working mode, baud rate and other parameters of the USCI module. Finally, data can be sent to external devices through the USCI module once the serial communication is established. You can use the UCAXTXBUF register to store the data sent into the buffer and use the UCAXTXIFG flag to detect whether the sender has been completed.

The USCI module in MSP430 receives the data transmitted by the external equipment. When the external device sends data, the MSP430 will trigger the UCAXRXIFG flag and store the received data in the UCAXRXBUF register. Once the data is received, it can be processed accordingly. The received data can be processed in the interrupt service routine or stored in variables for the main program to process.

7.2.3 The interface control system on Windows

The MCU and its programming control have been introduced in the previous article. This section will introduce a software compilation and its functions used in the main PC to control the lower computer through a graphical interface.

The interface of Windows control

MFC (Microsoft Foundation Classes) is a class library provided by Microsoft for developers. Through C++, some APIs in Windows are encapsulated. An application framework is included in MFC, and developers can directly implement target functions by calling these APIs in MFC, including windows, controls, message loops, document views, menus, etc. These features greatly reduce the effort required for development.

Developers generally select MFC applications from several classes derived from the MFC class and a CWinApp class object and then combine them to form an overall structure. In addition, MFC Appwizard automatic generation framework is also provided.

In C++, the created MFC application program can generally be divided into control, dialogue, frame, document view, and function classes. The control class represents the window controls in Windows, such as buttons, text boxes, list boxes, etc. The required controls can be easily added to the created frame through these classes. The dialogue box class represents the dialogue boxes in Windows, and there are two types of modal dialogue boxes and non-modal dialogue boxes. The framework class contains the framework of Windows applications, such as views, menus, toolbars, and so on. The document view class represents the document view model in Windows. Functional classes provide some common functions for programs, such as string processing, file operations, memory management, etc.

In this work, using a dialogue-based MFC application, a windowed interface that controls the movement of the stepper motor by sending instructions to the MCU is compiled in Visual Studio 2015, as shown in Figure 7.23.

Figure 7. 23. MFC program for controlling a miniaturized spectrometer.

The program includes the following functions:

1. Connect the main PC and the MCU through serial communication.
2. Send commands through serial port communication to control the stepper motor's rotation. The function includes one step of forward rotation setting, one step of reverse rotation, forward rotation until it touches the contact switch, and reverse rotation until it touches the contact switch.
3. Judging whether the data signal touches the contact switch fed back from the lower computer.
4. Use GPIB to connect the host computer and the multimeter and complete the data collection in the interface.

The connection between Interface and the MCU program

The program and the MCU use the serial port communication described above to send instructions and collect data. Therefore, serial port communication's programming and connection process will not be repeated. As shown in Figure 7.23, the MCU is connected to the main PC by selecting the appropriate serial port number in the drop-down menu in the

upper left corner. In MCU programming, different motor motion states are represented by setting different serial port commands. Figure 6.24 is an example of the program for stepping the motor forward.

```
void CInrfaceDlg::OnBnClickedButtonForward()
{
    //MCU programming "0" represents the motor forward one step
    if (m_setOk == true)    //Determine whether to open and initialize the serial port
    {
        char buf[100]={0};
        int forward = 48; // Decimal "48" corresponds to ASCII code "0"
        memcpy(buf, &forward, sizeof(forward));
        m_ctrComm.put_Output(COLEVariant(buf));
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        MessageBox("Please select the COM port!", "Remider", MB_OK | MB_ICONWARNING);
    }
}
```

Figure 7. 24. Using C++ programming, the main PC sends instructions to the lower computer to control the stepper motor to rotate a unit length.

The connection between Interface and the multimeter

A multimeter is connected to the main PC using General-Purpose Interface Bus (GPIB). The multimeter used in this project is an Agilent 34401, and the GPIB communication between the host computer and the Agilent multimeter is completed by calling the Virtual Instrument Software Architecture (VISA) library. Part of the functions in the VISA library are shown in Figure 7.25.

Function(s)	Description
visa.h	This file is included at the beginning of the file to provide the function prototypes and constants defined by VISA.
VisSession	The Visession is a VISA data type. Each object that will establish a communication channel must be defined as visession.
viOpenDefaultRM	You must first open a session with the default resource manager with the viOpenDefaultRM function. This function will initialize the default resource manager and return a pointer to that resource manager session.
viOpen	This function establishes a communication channel with the device specified. A session identifier that can be used with other VISA functions is returned. This call must be made for each device you will be using.
viPrintf and viScanf	These are the VISA formatted I/O functions that are patterned after those used in the C programming language. The viPrintf call sends the IEEE 488.2 *RST command to the instrument and puts it in a known state. The viPrintf call is used again to query for the device identification (*IDN?). The viscanf call is then used to read the results.
viClose	This function must be used to close each session. When you close a device session, all data structures that had been allocated for the session will be deallocated. When you close the default manager session, all sessions opened using that default manager session will be closed.

Figure 7. 25. Some functions in the VISA library.

In the interface program, the communication between the host computer and the multimeter is completed by calling the instructions in the VISA library. The program is shown in Figure 7.26.

```

viPrintf(vi, "*RST\n"); // reset device
viPrintf(vi, "*IDN?\n"); //Query device Identification
viScanf(vi, "%t", receiveBuf);

DeviceState.Format("Device State: Connected!");
DeviceInfo.Format("Device Information: %s \n", receiveBuf);

viPrintf(vi, "VOLT:DC:RES?\n"); // Query voltage resolution
viScanf(vi, "%t", receiveRes);

DeviceRes.Format("%s \n", receiveRes);

viPrintf(vi, "VOLT:DC:RANGE MAX\n"); // set voltage range as max
viPrintf(vi, "VOLT:DC:RANGE?\n");
viScanf(vi, "%s", receiveRange);

```

Figure 7. 26. The program connects the main PC and the multimeter.

7.3 Summary

In this chapter, the structure of the designed miniaturized spectrometer, the control program design ideas and the main program compilation code are discussed.

The main structure of the miniaturization spectrometer designed in this paper consists of three parts: light source, light dispersion system (and LVF mobile module) and detection and receiving system. The specific parameters and selection reasons of each part are introduced

respectively. In the test, the spectrometer version 2 and version 3 using the screw drive methods were redesigned due to the poor stability of the gear drive used in version 1. The difference between versions 2 and 3 is the upgraded torque of the motor and introduction of the modular design, making potential next stage development work easier to do.

The design of the control module was also completed. The design module includes lower computer program (MCU control program) and upper computer interface program (Windows desktop control interface). In the lower program, the signal processing and control algorithm of the stepping motor was written using Energia compilation software.

In the upper computer software, the spectral data processing algorithm was written, the simple and easy to use software interface was developed, and realized the acquisition, processing and graphical display of the spectral data. In the chapter 7, the following is discussed; the LVF used in the miniaturized spectrometer was determined, and the mapping of the LVF central transmittance wavelength to the spatial location (determined by stepper motor control) was realized by the curve fitting and the characteristic line of the standard light source.

Chapter 8 Experimental Process and results analysis

8.1 Miniature spectrometer model manufacturing

The design scheme of the miniaturized spectrometer has been introduced in section 7.1.1. In order to analyse the performance, the measurement of actual samples is undertaken. Firstly, the chassis needs to be manufactured, followed by integration of all the individual components, and the connections between them. It should be noted that according to the distribution of components, it is necessary to connect the MCU with the component motor and its drive board through wires. The components' assembly level needs to meet the stepper motor's surface and motion accuracy. The chassis was fabricated using 3-dimensional (3D) printing. The design was printed out using an Anet A8 3D printer, as shown in Figure 8.1.

Figure 8. 1. Image of the Anet A8 3D printer used to manufacture spectrometer chassis in this work.

The advantage of 3D printing is that it can be personalized, and small batch production can be completed through drawings, increasing the efficiency of the production cycle. In addition, the manufacturing cost is also low by using the matching polylactic acid (PLA) as the 3D printing material. By using computer control and precise nozzles, the PLA material is processed layer by layer into the desired 3D model. The design model has been shown in Figures 7.1, 7.2, and 7.3.

8.2 System connection and debugging

According to the structure introduced above, by using 3D printing equipment to print it out and installing the stepper motor and photodetector, an image of the actual assembly is shown in figure 8.2.

Figure 8. 2. Miniaturized spectrometer model based on LVF (a) with the low torque ST2018 stepping motor gear transmission (b) with the low torque ST2018 stepping motor screw drive (c) with the high torque 17HS4401 stepping motor wire Lever transmission.

Spectrometer version 1 has the gear transmission configuration shown in Figure 8.2 (a). When the motor rotates the gear to make the LVF move, it should be uniformly linear. However, due to problems such as gear fit or insufficient material hardness, there will be a certain probability of shaking or sliding, resulting in inconsistency in the data measurement process.

Therefore, spectrometer version 2 was realised using the same motor but coupled to a different mechanical transmission mode, (b) is obtained by changing the transmission mode and increasing the limit. The advantage of this transmission method is that the movement position of the LVF is fixed on the XYZ three axes through the screw. Because of the screw drive, the progress of the LVF during lateral movement is increased.

The distance the LVF moves for both the spectrometer version 1 and version 2 was measured and compared. The reason for measuring the distance of LVF movement is that in spectral measurement, the linearity of the LVF optical transmittance vs position is relatively large. If the step distance is unequal during measurement, it will lead to large data measurement errors.

Spectrometer version 1 (gear transmission model) was assembled and initialised. Initialization refers to moving the LVF module to the same starting position, as shown in Figure 8.3.

Figure 8. 3. Spectrometer version gear-driven LVF micro-spectrometer (a) The stepping motor moves from right to left (b) The stepping motor moves from left to right.

The number of rotation steps of the stepper motor is set to 100, the LVF mount is moved from one side to another and ten sets of data is measured. Next, using a vernier calliper, the moving distance of the LVF mount is measured, the motion error is calculated followed by the mean root square, standard deviation and error range, as shown in Tables 8.1 and 8.2. Since the root mean square eliminates the influence of the sign when calculating the error, it can better reflect the discreteness of the data.

Table 8. 1.. Gearing moves from motor left to right

Number	Measurement data (mm)				Analyse and calculate (mm)		
	Initial position	Stop position	Moving distance	Moving distance error	Average moving distance		
1	56.24	16.59	39.65	0.01	39.64		
2	55.83	16.04	39.79	0.15	39.64		
3	56.04	16.48	39.56	-0.08	Average per move(mm)		
4	55.87	16.1	39.77	0.13	0.40		
5	55.68	16.09	39.59	-0.05	Root mean square (RMS) of distance traveled		
6	56.19	16.52	39.67	0.03	0.09539392		
7	55.8	16.2	39.6	-0.04	Standard deviation		
8	55.64	16.08	39.56	-0.08	0.09539392		
9	55.65	16.17	39.48	-0.16	Tolerance		
10	55.98	16.25	39.73	0.09	39.64	±	0.095394

Table 8. 2 . Gearing moves from right to left of motor

Number	Measurement data (mm)				Analyse and calculate (mm)	
	Initial position	Stop position	Moving distance	Moving distance error	Average moving distance	
1	10.12	49.66	39.54	-0.16	39.704	
2	10.08	49.77	39.69	-0.01	39.70	
3	9.85	49.59	39.74	0.04	Average per move(mm)	
4	9.81	49.53	39.72	0.02	0.40	
5					Root mean square (RMS) of distance traveled	
	9.75	49.53	39.78	0.08		
6	10.18	49.98	39.8	0.10	0.087200917	
7					Standard deviation	
	9.9	49.65	39.75	0.05		
8	10.12	49.84	39.72	0.02	0.087200917	
9	9.84	49.38	39.54	-0.16	Tolerance	
10	9.82	49.58	39.76	0.06	39.70	± 0.087201

Next, spectrometer version 2 (driven by the lead screw) is tested, as shown in Figure 8.4. During the test, the stepper is controlled to move 250 steps, and the test is performed ten times, starting at both ends of the movement.

Figure 8. 4. Spectrometer version 2, lead screw drive type LVF micro-spectrometer (a) The stepper motor moves from left to the right, (b) moves from right to left.

Prior to the above, it is necessary to confirm that the contact switch is in the starting position when the slider is in the closed state. The specific method is to move the slider one step in the opposite direction at the top position so that the contact switch is closed. Then, a vernier calliper is used to measure the moving distance, analyse its motion error, and calculate the mean root square, standard deviation and error range, as shown in Tables 8.3 and 8.4.

Table 8. 3. The screw drive moves from the right to the left of the motor

Number	Measurement data (mm)				Analyse and calculate (mm)		
	Initial position	Stop position	Moving distance	Moving distance error	Average moving distance		
1	71.08	31.03	40.05	0.04	40.005		
2	71.07	31.05	40.02	0.01	40.01		
3	71.08	31.06	40.02	0.01	Average per move(mm)		
4	71.16	31.18	39.98	-0.03	0.16		
5	71.15	31.16	39.99	-0.01	Root mean square (RMS) of distance traveled		
6	71.18	31.18	40	0.00	0.026551836		
7	71.16	31.15	40.01	0.00	Standard deviation		
8	71.15	31.12	40.03	0.02	0.026551836		
9	71.18	31.18	40	0.00	Tolerance		
10	71.43	31.48	39.95	-0.05	40.01	±	0.026552

Table 8. 4. Screw drive moves from motor left to right

Number	Measurement data (mm)				Analyse and calculate (mm)		
	Initial position	Stop position	Moving distance	Moving distance error	Average moving distance		
1	21.76	61.77	40.01	0.01	39.997		
2	21.69	61.66	39.97	-0.03	40.00		
3	21.69	61.69	40	0.00	Average per move(mm)		
4	21.68	61.64	39.96	-0.04	0.16		
5	21.65	61.66	40.01	0.01	Root mean square (RMS) of distance traveled		
6	21.69	61.68	39.99	-0.01	0.017916473		
7	21.69	61.69	40	0.00	Standard deviation		
8	21.65	61.65	40	0.00	0.017916473		
9	21.66	61.68	40.02	0.02	Tolerance		
10	21.63	61.64	40.01	0.01	40.00	±	0.017916

In summary, as observed with spectrometer versions 1 and 2, the moving distance of the LVF is when the stepper motor moves one step away from the angular distance. The average moving distance of the gear of spectrometer version 1 is 0.4 mm, and the average moving

distance of the screw drive in spectrometer version 2 is 0.16 mm. To compare, the precision of gear transmission through screw transmission is improved by a factor of 2.5. Compared with the error range, the error generated by the screw drive is much smaller than that of the gear drive. Therefore, the screw drive is better suited as the LVF translation mechanism for the miniaturized spectrometer.

Only the motor torque is different between spectrometer version 2 and 3, and the step angle is 1.8° , so the measurement data should be similar to spectrometer version 2, so the above analysis was not performed for spectrometer version 3.

8.3 Experimental test results

8.3.1 Measurement results of a gear-driven miniaturized spectrometer

The LVF in the visible light (450 nm - 900 nm) band was installed into both the miniaturized gear and lead screw transmission spectrometer models. The gear-driven spectrometer version 1 LVF micro-spectrometer is shown in Figure 8.5.

The figure 8.5 shows that the light emitted by the light source is guided by the optical fibre and collimated by the fibre collimator. After passing through the sample (10 layers Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2) to be tested, it is received by the optical fibre at the other end. Then the beam is guided through the fibre collimator to be collimated to a small spot of about 1 mm to pass through the LVF sample. The MCU controls the stepper motor, and the drive board initiates rotation after being commanded, driving the gear on the head of the stepper motor to rotate, making the LVF holder move from one side to the other until it reaches the full length of the LVF. During this process, the detector behind the LVF received different responses to the detector voltage read by the multimeter.

Figure 8. 5. Image of the manufactured LVF miniaturised spectrometer, driven by gears.

Three scans must be performed in order to make one complete sample measurement. Firstly, it is necessary to test the background noise intensity I_b received by the detector when the LVF moves without light input, known as a dark measurement. Next, the light source is connected here to measure the standard reference intensity I_r received by the detector when the LVF moves without the sample under light input. Finally, after placing the sample, the detector response intensity I_s received by the detector is measured when the LVF moves under the condition of light input. The final transmission spectrum T of the sample can be calculated as a function of I_s , I_b and I_r by formula 8.1.

$$T = \frac{I_s - I_b}{I_r - I_b} \quad (8.1)$$

The measured results are shown in Figure 8.6. In this figure, the abscissa represents the number of steps the stepping motor moves, and the ordinate represents the spectral response intensity measured by the detector at different steps.

Figure 8. 6. The data(10 layers Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2) measured by the gear-driven spectrometer version 1 LVF micro-spectrometer, the x-axis is the number of steps of the stepping motor, and the y-axis is the spectral transmittance.

In Section 5.3, the LVF test parameters used in this work have been given. Here, the linearity of the LVF is needed to calculate the spectral transmittance corresponding to the spot irradiation wavelength position on the LVF. The linearity formula 8.2 of the LVF is as follows,

$$\lambda = 11.145s + 670.55 \quad (8.2)$$

In the above formula, λ represents the central wavelength, and s is the physical position of the light spot on the LVF. Next, the physical position s of the light spot on the LVF is calculated by the number of steps x of the stepping motor, as shown in the following formula 8.3.

$$s = 4.9 \times (x - 13) + 455 \quad (8.3)$$

After converting the number of steps of the stepping motor into the required spectral wavelength, the test data shown in Figure 8.7 is obtained. ‘Scalar’ is a spectrometer manufactured by ScalarTechnologies and has also been used to measure the sample.

Figure 8. 7. Comparison of data after measuring the same sample(10 layers Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2) using a geared LVF model and a Scalar spectrometer.

It can be seen from Figure 8.7 that the data measured by the gear-driven miniaturized spectrometer version 1 designed in this work has good agreement with the data measured by the commercially available Scalar spectrometer. It can be seen from the results that the miniaturized spectrometer works well, and the measured data can generally be replicated using a separate spectrometer device. Still, the data errors at both ends of the short wavelength and long wavelength are relatively large. The main cause of this error may be caused by the noise of the photodetector and the accuracy error of the distance when the stepper motor moves. Therefore, the mode of gear transmission is improved to lead screw transmission, and the specific measurement results are as follows.

8.3.2 Measurement results of miniaturized spectrometer driven by lead screw

Based on the structural design of the previous gear-driven miniaturized spectrometer version 1, the model of the screw drive is similar to it in general parts, with a little change in structure. Figure 8.8 shows the small motor screw drive spectrometer version 2 and large motor screw drive miniaturized spectrometer version 3 models.

Figure 8. 8. LVF miniaturized spectrometer with screw drive (a) Small motor spectrometer version 2 and (b) Large motor spectrometer version 3.

When measuring samples, the procedure is similar to the above-mentioned gearing procedure. The transmission spectrum data of the sample can be obtained by formula 8.1. It is also necessary to convert the number of steps of the stepping motor into the physical position of the light spot on the LVF. Because the step size of the screw drive is smaller than that of the gear drive, formula 8.4 is used for the conversion.

$$s = 3 \times (x - 40) \times 3 \times 1.6 \quad (8.4)$$

By measuring a single-layer Nb₂O₅ thin film on glass sample, the data measurement results of

the miniaturized spectrometer driven by the screw drive are verified, as shown in Figure 8.9.

Figure 8. 9. The data comparison of Nb_2O_5 single-layer film measured by the LVF miniaturized spectrometer driven by the lead screw and the Lambda 40 standard benchtop spectrometer.

In order to compare the test data of the screw drive mode with the miniaturized spectrometer model of the gear drive mode, the same sample is used for measurement, and the data results are shown in Figure 8.10.

Figure 8. 10. The test data (10 layers Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2) of the LVF miniaturized spectrometer driven by the gear transmission and the lead screw are compared with the Scalar measurement data.

In Figure 8.10, the red line is the data measured by the Scalar spectrometer, the black line is the data measured by the miniaturized spectrometer using the screw drive LVF, and the blue line is the data measured by the miniaturized spectrometer using the gear drive LVF. For the

same sample, the results of miniaturized spectrometers driven by gears and leadscrews tend to be similar to those of standard large-scale spectrometers. However, there are still some differences between the miniaturized spectrometer designed in this work and the Scalar spectrometer in terms of the accuracy of the data and the data at the boundary. However, between the two miniaturized spectrometers with gear transmission and lead screw transmission, the data measured by the gear transmission is relatively rough. It is because during the movement of the LVF, the measurement is affected by the vibration after the movement, and the LVF cannot be kept truly parallel to the detector. The model using the screwdriver does not have this problem, and the data is smoother and flatter in comparison.

8.4 Summary

In this chapter, testing of the manufactured miniaturised spectrometer is presented. These tests include, for versions 1, 2, and 3 of the miniaturized spectrometer, the moving distance and accuracy test of the LVF mobile module under different transmission modes (since versions 2 and 3 are driven by a screw, only one group is tested); version 1 is used to test the same sample with the commercially available spectral measurement equipment, Ocean Insight Scalar, to compare the data. version 2 is compared with the spectral measurement equipment Lambda 40. Version 1, version 3 and the Ocean Insight Scalar spectrometer are used to measure the same sample and compare the data.

Through the test of the movement of the LVF module in different transmission modes, from the data, the following can be concluded for spectrometer version 1; after each motor step, the actual moving distance of the LVF module is 0.4 mm. In the moving distance over the LVF length, the error in distance generated by each step of the stepper motor is 0.09 mm, which is almost negligible. In the version 2 where the lead screw is used as the transmission mode, after each step of the stepping motor, the lead screw driven by the stepping motor will push the LVF mobile module to a distance of 0.16 mm. Compared with the gear transmission, the movement accuracy is improved by 2.5 times. After moving, the relative error of the moving distance is 0.02 mm, which is also negligible.

By using the designed miniaturized spectrometer in the data measurement of the sample, it is compared with the data measured by the large spectrometer. The lead screw driven spectrometer had better spectral overlap with the scalar spectrometer compared to the gear driven spectrometer, suggesting that the improved LVF movement mechanism improves the

LVF position accuracy. In both versions of the LVF spectrometer, the absolute amount of transmittance is different from the scalar spectrometer. According to the content of Chapter 5 above, it can be speculated that this phenomenon may be due to the average size of the beam spot irradiated on the LVF. It is evident in figure. 7.9 that the measurements at the upper and lower edges are only close but do not match the scalar spectrometer. Fiber collimators can provide a relatively large beam spot size at the LVF, but this will result in broadening and flattening of the spectral features. This can be optimized by using lenses or different gauge fibres to create a smaller beam spot size, perhaps by using an LVF with a lower spectral gradient as well. Future research may be conducted to investigate how to use the LVF micro-spectrometer to adapt to the larger incident spot size and measure more accurate data that matches the commercially available Ocean Insight Scalar spectrometer which is considered the benchmark performance.

Chapter 9 Summary and Suggestions for Future Work

The main objective of this thesis is the innovative manufacture of visible and near-infrared LVF samples by using the drum-based microwave plasma-assisted pulsed DC magnetron reaction sputtering system. The LVF was analysed and characterized after manufacture. After the LVF was characterised, a miniaturized spectrometer was manufactured that uses the LVF as a wavelength separation optic. Due to the replaceability of the LVF, the designed miniaturized spectrometer can measure wavelength ranges, including visible light (450 nm - 900 nm) and near-infrared (1.5 μm - 2.5 μm). Compared with the large footprint benchtop spectral measurement equipment, miniaturized spectrometer devices are small in size, low in cost and easy to use, rendering them more suitable for wider application for consumer and industrial use.

9.1 Summary of the work and results.

9.1.1 Summary of Results

1. The high throughput microwave plasma-assisted DC magnetron reactive sputtering system, the Microdyn was described. The Microdyn was used to manufacture the LVFs used throughout this work. Using Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2 as high and low refractive index thin film coating materials respectively, a 44 mm length visible light (450 nm - 900 nm) and 25 mm length near-infrared (1.5 μm - 2.5 μm) band LVF sample was designed and fabricated.
2. A model is developed to describe the discrepancy between the measured LVF optical transmittance spectrum and the theoretical spectrum as a result of the finite spot size of the incident spectrometer beam. It can be challenging to create the minimum beam spot size, and the averaging effect produced by a larger spot in the measurement will have a greater impact on its spectral measurement results. The reason for the deviation between the theoretical and actual values of the LVF spectral data in the characterization is explained using various mathematical models to simulate the average effect in the measurement results.
3. Existing spectrometers are classified and summarized according to the relevant literature. Existing spectrometers described in the literature are classified and discussed. Next, a low-cost miniaturized spectrometer structure based on an LVF is proposed.
4. A range of components are selected in order to realise the build of the miniaturised LVF spectrometer. Such components include an MCU, stepper motor, stepper motor driver, LVF,

photodetector, etc. The following component models were selected; a Texas Instruments MSP430G2553 was selected as the MCU, a Nanotec ST2018 was used as the stepper motor designed for spectrometer versions 1 and 2, and an 17HS4401 was used as the stepper motor designed for spectrometer version 3. Two LVFs with visible light and near-infrared wavelengths were designed and manufactured. The photodetectors used were a Vishay BPW21R Si photodiodes in the visible light region and a Laser Components PB25S10104S type PbS detectors in the near-infrared region.

5. Serial communications between the host computer and the MSP430G2553 MCU were realized in order to control the stepper motor, and convert, collect and transmit the measured data. The opto-mechanical-electrical integration design of the miniaturized spectrometer equipment is realized.

6. A miniaturized spectrometer model is manufactured using 3D printing equipment. The 3D printed conventional material PLA is used for production. Scans performed by the developed miniaturized LVF spectrometer are compared to a commercial benchtop spectrometer and a commercial miniature spectrometer.

9.1.2 Summary of Innovation

1. My research with group is the first to use drum-based microwave plasma assisted magnetron reactive sputtering equipment to prepare LVF samples in the world.

2. During the production process of LVF, since the drum-based microwave plasma assisted magnetron reactive sputtering equipment is rotating, the film formed by sputtering in the circumferential direction of the drum is almost uniform in thickness. Therefore, the LVF sample will not experience stress in the vertical direction, nor will the sample bend.

3. The drum-based microwave plasma assisted magnetron reactive sputtering process I use, in contrast to conventional Ion beam sputtering techniques described in the literature, can mass produce LVF samples at low cost.

4. For characterising manufactured LVFs, an automated program was developed for the Aquila spectrophotometer that controls the motion of the measurement platform in order to reduce human error in positional accuracy of the LVF under test. Such a program enables greater accuracy in determining the true linearity of the LVF. This is essential for characterising the spectral resolution over a given wavelength for a spectrally selective device

using an integrated LVF as the wavelength separation optic.

5. Using LVF samples, I developed a new miniaturized low-cost spectrometer introduced in this thesis. Both visible and near-infrared wavelength range LVF miniaturized spectrometers were developed. The device has a small footprint, low weight, moderate resolution and good accuracy, rendering it as a potential candidate for field or aircraft deployment. Potential applications include spectral scanning of solids, liquids or gases in the field where space and weight limitations prevent use of large and expensive optical systems. One particular application envisioned is the scanning of air quality in industrial or aerospace environments where the presence of VOCs pose a significant threat to personnel safety. For VOCs speciation and identification, spectral information is needed. Such an application would require the use of a near-infrared miniature spectrometer such as the one developed in this work, operating in the $1.5\ \mu\text{m} - 2.5\ \mu\text{m}$ spectral fingerprint region for commonly encountered by-product VOCs such as benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene and xylene.

6. Mechanisms for optimal spatial translation of the LVF for a miniature spectrometer were investigated. By improving the transmission mode of the stepping motor, the movement accuracy of the stepping motor is increased by 2.5 times during measurement. The gear transmission mode was improved to lead screw transmission, which improves the transmission efficiency, resulting in a smoother and more reliable motion of the LVF, and amplifies the torque of the stepping motor to improve accuracy and eliminate drift.

7. A modular LVF spectrometer chassis was developed using 3D printed parts. The first version of the spectrometer chassis comprised a monolithic 3D printed chassis structure. Using this design choice, any errors in the 3D printing method rendered the entire unit as unusable resulting in increased manufacturing labour, time and material expense. To overcome this, the design was changed that comprised segmented modular parts. The modular design allows each part to be printed separately, greatly increasing the error tolerance rate. Because each part can be easily disassembled, replacing parts is easier and faster.

9.2 Prospects for Future Work

Although the miniaturized spectrometer equipment designed in this paper has been successfully built, plenty of room for future development remains.

1. It is necessary to simplify the control program of the interface host computer. The current

procedures are not refined enough. In order to make the system more user friendly and to cater for a general lay-person audience, the control system must be simplified to enable plug-and-play usage. Currently, the measurement steps are cumbersome and demanding, which is not conducive to ease of use. Therefore, the simpler the control mode setting of the device, the better.

2. Although the developed miniaturized spectrometer is small, the spatial footprint can still be reduced. Without compressing the volume of the optical system, the instrument's volume can be reduced by improving the integration of the system electronics. For prototyping, a benchtop power supply unit was used to power the system, so a smaller footprint mobile power supply unit can be added to upgrade the miniaturized spectrometer into a portable miniature spectrometer. Integration of wireless capability such as Bluetooth communications can be incorporated to minimise wiring and enable remote operation with, for example a laptop or mobile phone application.

3. With regards to the stability and accuracy of the system, there is room for improvement. Since the LVF is in motion, the bottom slide rail is required to limit the position of the LVF support seat so as to minimise motion of the LVF in directions perpendicular to the desired scanning direction that would result in measurement errors that would be induced and exacerbated by mechanical disturbances. As a result, friction is introduced, limiting smooth and reliable translation of the LVF. To overcome this, the motor is replaced with a larger motor with a higher torque. However, after the test, it was found that there may still be errors due to the 3D printing material used. An investigation into the spectrometer chassis material choice should be conducted in order to optimise for rigidity to improve the systems mechanical integrity. A ceramic or metal chassis might be better suited for applications requiring field deployment.

4. For the construction of spectrometers, MCU development boards and motor driver development boards are currently used, and development boards are usually used to test the suitability of microchips (MCU chips or h-bridge driver chips) in products. In the current experiment, a chip development board is used. In the final design, these chips will be integrated into a highly compact PCB design before the product goes to market. In this way, the volume of electronic products will be much smaller, and eventually only include the main chip and some peripherals. The volume of the spectrometer can be reduced again, resulting in

a more compact structure.

5. LVF-type spectrometers have broad application prospects. With the reduction of cost and spatial footprint, LVFs can replace optical gratings where necessary, and be used in more general-purpose spectrometers, for introduction into a mass market. For health and safety applications, miniaturised LVF spectrometers can ease the burden of healthcare costs and improve people's living standards. It is envisioned that use of LVFs as a wavelength separation optic will enable mass market exploitation of miniaturised spectrometers, taking devices outside the laboratory and truly popularizing this technology.

6. A near-infrared $1.5\ \mu\text{m} - 2.5\ \mu\text{m}$ LVF has been manufactured, and a near-infrared miniaturized spectrometer has also been produced (based on version 3, the light source kit, near-infrared LVF and PbS detector have been replaced). However, the measurement data may benefit from further refinement, so the results are not included in this thesis. As for the difference between the measurement results and the standard results in the near-infrared band, my guess is the following points: 1) The measurement is liquid, and I measure it by using the method of dropping the solution in two pieces of JGS3. During the measurement process, in order to ensure the accuracy and stability of the measurement, the rotation speed of the stepper motor will be slowed down. This results in extended measurement time, and the liquid solution in JGS3 will evaporate over time, resulting in inaccurate measurement results. 2) The stability of the infrared light source and detector may change in performance over time, resulting in inaccurate measurements.

Future work should be devoted to solving these problems and further promoting the development of the research field. At the same time, the structure and measurement methods of the micro-spectrometer should be developed to improve the accuracy and stability of measurements. The development of more practical applications of miniaturized spectrometers will promote the development of science and society.

Appendix 1: History of thin film manufacturing technology and processes

1.1 Introduction

In modern times, the application of optical films in various industries is becoming ever more extensive. It has made outstanding contributions in the fields of industrial manufacture (Xu, 2022), agriculture (Song *et al.*, 2019), construction (Águas *et al.*, 2015), transportation (Raffaella and Relly, 2017), medicine (Shorokhov *et al.*, 2018), military (Ratches, 2006), astronomy (Quijada *et al.*, 2018), infrared physics (Chen *et al.*, 2020) and laser technology (Lowndes *et al.*, 1996), etc. At the same time, it plays a vital role in people's daily work and life. In today's rapidly changing science and technology, the development of chip manufacturing (Banger *et al.*, 2011), energy utilization (Benda, 2020), aerospace technology (Martin, Wrbanek and Fralick, 2001) and other fields are inseparable from thin film technology, which puts forward higher requirements for the development of optical thin films.

Since 1970, various vacuum coating technologies have been applied on an industrial scale. Thin film technology has developed by leaps and bounds (Mattox, 2003). Coating technology has achieved fruitful results in both academic and practical applications. Thin film technology has become the most active research field in contemporary vacuum technology and material science, which plays a pivotal role in the new technology revolution (Benelmekki and Erbe, 2019). In recent years, semiconductor chip technology has been highly valued, and thin film technology is one of the key technologies for semiconductor chip manufacturing.

The optical and optoelectronic thin films produced by thin film technology, have been widely used in various emerging technology fields. Thin-film technology and thin-film materials can be used in thin-film photonic crystals, quantum dot films, multi-dimensional structures at nanometre or subwavelength scales, ferroelectric nonlinear films with high photoelectric coefficients, photorefractive films, photon detection films, sensing functional films, high-density volume recording films and organic light-emitting display films have developed rapidly in these fields, all of which are related to the development and application of various special properties and the characteristics of optical films. Also, because the optical film has a good spatial periodic structure, the designer can perform complex manual tailoring and design of the film's structure, composition and performance according to the optical film theory to

achieve excellent performance that other technologies cannot easily obtain.

1.1.1 Origin of Thin Film deposition

A thin film is a material with a thickness ranging from a few angstroms to a few microns. The earliest thin film technology can be traced back to 5000 years ago, where the ancient Egyptians used chemo-mechanical methods to make a single-layer gold film for decoration with a thickness of less than 3000 Å (Greene, 2014). The origin of optical thin films can be traced back to the 18th century when humans first discovered and explained the interference process of light (Belinskii and Klyshko, 1993). Maxwell put forward the theory of electromagnetic field in *A Treatise on Electricity and Magnetism*, published in 1873, which further improved the theoretical basis of optical thin film technology (Maxwell, 1873). So far, the two fundamental theories of thin-film optics, the electromagnetic field theory and the light interference theory, have all been established.

In modern history, an early coating method was developed by William Nicholson and Anthony Carlisle in the late 18th and early 19th centuries. At the same time as the discovery of the water electrolysis reaction, it was observed that some copper was deposited around the negative line (NICHOLSON, 1800). In 1817, Joseph von Fraunhofer, the German optician, obtained the first reduced reflection film by chance, using concentrated sulfuric acid [H₂SO₄] and HNO₃ for etching and redepositing films, which was the first subjectively produced optical film in human history (J. Fraunhofer, 1817). In 1835, Justus Von Leibig invented a silver-plating process to coat glass with silver instead of mercury, greatly improving the utility of the mirror, and they were the first industrial optical films made in the world (William, 2002). Hares invented the first consumable-electrode arc-melting furnace in 1839 and used it to melt platinum (Pt) for various electrochemical reaction experiments, the first documented experimental device for thermal evaporation (Moss and Richards, 1960). Until the mid-19th century, the chemical solution coating method was gradually replaced by vacuum coating, except for some applications of large area window glass coatings. At this point, the prelude of the modern thin film process was gradually opened.

1.1.2 Early-stage vacuum science and technology

A vacuum is any space with much lower pressure than atmospheric pressure. Modern film process is generally carried out under vacuum conditions, attainment of a vacuum is an

indispensable condition required for coating. The earliest vacuum pump was invented by Otto van Guericke around 1640. A piston vacuum pump was created to remove water in mines, as shown in Figure 1.1 (HERBERT and LOU, 1912). The real introduction of the vacuum pump into the scientific world was in 1654 when von Guericke performed the famous experimental "Magdeburg Hemisphere" demonstration (Mattox, 2003). Since then, after a long period of improvement and research (most of the work revolves around vacuum sealing and leakage), in 1907, W.Gaede invented the oil-sealed rotary vane mechanical pump. In 1913, I. Langmuir invented the mercury diffusion pump, which W. Gaede improved in 1922 (ANDRADE, 1960). In 1937, L. Malter built the first metal oil diffusion pump (Malter and Marcuvitz, 1938); before this, both fractionation and non-fractionation diffusion pumps were made of glass. Oil diffusion pumps ("diff pumps") are still the primary high vacuum pump in many large vacuum coating systems today. W. Gaede invented a turbomolecular pump in 1912, but the vertical shaft high-speed turbomolecular pump commonly used in modern coating equipment was independently developed in 1958 by H.A. Steinhertz (Hablanian, 1997).

So far, the basic conditions required for the vacuum physical coating process have all appeared. Next, the two most important processes for preparing optical thin films in the industry will be introduced in Appendix 2.1 vacuum evaporation and sputtering. The emergence of the metal oil diffusion pump mentioned above provides indispensable help for the large-scale application of these two coating processes.

Figure 1.1. Multi-stage water pump used to pump water inside the mine (HERBERT and LOU, 1912, p. 185).

1.1.3 From 1850s to early 1900s

The earliest recorded sputtering phenomenon was in 1852, when W. R. Grove introduced a steel needle close to the surface of a highly polished silver-plated copper plate (ordinarily used for Daguerreotypes) at a pressure of about 0.5 Torr with hydrogen and air, as shown in Figure 1.2 (Grove, 1852). When the silver surface was anode, a ring-shaped deposit would appear on the surface, but at that time, he focused on the effect of voltage reversal on the discharge and did not study the properties of the deposited film. When he transformed the surface of silver into a cathode, the iron oxide film was removed by ion etching. He uses "molecular disintegration" to describe this phenomenon in his article but removes and sputter-etches the surface oxide film onto the silver substrate. Faraday also reported the sputter deposition of thin films in glow discharge tubes in his 1854 article (Faraday, 1854). In 1857 Faraday produced the film when he exploded a wire in a vacuum, possibly the first evaporated film (Faraday, 1857). In 1887, Nahrwold (Nahrwold, 1887) discovered the sublimation of metals by heating and depositing a platinum (Pt) film in a vacuum, which was used by Kundt in 1888 to measure the refractive index of this film (Bunshah and Deshpandey, 1988).

Figure 1.2. Grove's "sputtering" apparatus (1852) (Grove, 1852). 1 is the coil apparatus, the contact breaker being in front. 2 is a Gas pump, a structure proposed by Grove, used for the study of electrical or chemical experiments of gases. P. An imperforate piston with a conical end, which, when pressed down, accurately fits the end of the tube, the apex touching the valve V, which opens outwards. A. Aperture for the air to rush from the receiver when the piston has been drawn beyond it. B. Bladder containing the gas to be experimented on.

In 1858, M. Plücker observed the discharge of rarefied gases and found that a Pt film was formed inside the discharge tube (Plücker, 1858). In 1877, Yale University professor Wright, Arthur W published a paper on using electrodeposition equipment to make mirrors and study their properties. However, in his description, this process is more like arc evaporation than sputtering. Professor Wright is considered the first to describe the properties of vacuum deposited thin films (A.W.Wright, 1877). Professor Wright's original motivation for this experiment was to remove the residual mercury vapour in the vacuum glass tube. His device circuit is shown in Figure 1.3 (Boxman, 2001).

Figure 1.3. Instrumental diagrams by Raymond L. Boxman based on descriptions in A. W. Wright's written text (Boxman, 2001).

Thomas Alva Edison invented the electric light bulb using carbonized cotton filaments in 1879, bringing sputtering to commercial use for the first time (Edison., 1880). He patented the arc-based vacuum deposition technique in 1884, but the U.S. Patent Office challenged his patent because Professor Wright first proposed the phenomenon in his 1877 paper (Mattox, 2003). Finally, Edison's patent application was passed in 1894 because Edison believed that Professor Wright used pulsed arc in the experiment, and he used continuous arc (Edison, 1894). In 1892, Edison electroplated his phonograph using vacuum deposition techniques to create a "seed coat" (Edison, 1892). In 1902, he innovated on his previous invention of 1894, covering a phonograph record with an extremely small metal film by electrodeposition (his description), and gave a patent drawing of a sputtered cathode (his description was a metal electrode) used to deposit metal thin films.

In 1891, British chemist William Crookes published an article entitled "Electrical

Evaporation" in the journal "Science", which is considered to be the first widely-read article on sputtering (Crookes, 1891). In the late 19th century, sputter deposition was used to make mirrors (except for silver mirrors made by depositing silver from chemical solutions) (Mattox, 2003).

1.1.4 Fifty years of the 20th century

In 1904, Edison improved on two of his 1894 and 1902 patents on vacuum deposition technology, which could deposit an extremely thin film of vaporized metal on multiple phonographs or other objects in the same vacuum chamber (Edison, 1904). In 1907, the process of "reactive deposition" for the first time in history was believed to have been proposed by Soddy in his paper, which mainly describes the evaporation of solid calcium onto a surface to reduce the residual pressure in the sealed tube (Soddy, 1907). The same year, Italian Pirani applied for a patent for E-beam vacuum melting technology in Germany. He used this technology to produce tantalum or other highly refractory metals into a homogeneous body (von Pirani, 1907). In 1908, German physicist Johannes Stark argued that ions would collide and sputter upon impact, which later generations would summarize as the theory of momentum transfer for sputtering (Stark, 1908).

Irving Langmuir measured the vapour pressure of various metals between 1910 and 1920. He developed a method to determine the vapour pressure of metals by measuring the rate of metal vaporization (Langmuir, 1913; Langmuir and Mackay, 1914). In 1912, Pohl and Pringsheim published a paper called the production of metal mirrors by vacuum distillation, which was the first time using a magnesium oxide crucible as a container to evaporate solid materials in a vacuum, which is considered to be the first time thin film deposition by a vacuum thermal evaporation process (Pohl and Pringsheim, 1912). In 1917, sputtered thin film resistors deposited on long glass rods were commercially produced (Robbins, 1998).

German physicist Güntherschulze published several articles on DC sputtering (cathode sputtering) between 1926 and 1955, and in 1930 was the first to propose and describe the theory of sputtering that is affected by ion energy (Güntherschulze and Meyer, 1930). In 1931, the US Government Printing Office introduced the process of sputter deposition of mirrors in the article "The making of mirrors by the deposition of metal on glass" (Gardner and Case, 1931). In the same year, Ritschl proposed the thermal evaporation of silver from a basket of tungsten filaments to form a semi-silvered mirror, and he is considered the first to use

filament evaporation to form thin films in a vacuum (Strong, 1933).

In 1933, Strong evaporated large-gauge tungsten filaments wetted by molten aluminium by using the method of filament evaporation, then made aluminium films and mirrors by vacuum evaporation (Strong, 1933); Overbeck reported sputtering of materials on circular tin cathodes on glass, there are different optical properties under the condition of passing different gases, this is a reactive sputtering deposition (Overbeck, 1933).

In 1935, Bosch of Bosch Company in Germany began to study the vacuum evaporation of metals in paper foil capacitors (Henderson, 1945). He found that the "self-healing" phenomenon occurs when arcs exist between low melting point film electrode materials. In the same year, Smakula of German Carl Zeiss Co., Ltd coated a single-layer anti-reflection film on the optical lens (Smakula, 1935). 1936 Strong heated and evaporated calcium fluoride (CaF₂) with an antireflection effect under vacuum conditions and successfully prepared artificial antireflection films on glass substrates (Strong, 1936). In 1937, Penning described a discharge tube for exciting neutrons by bombarding a target with ions in his paper. A glow discharge used as an ion source could be maintained at a pressure of 10⁻³mm under the action of a magnetic field (Penning and Moubis, 1937). That is the first reported magnetron-enhanced sputtering coating process. In 1939, Cartwright and Turner tried to combine the films of low-refractive and high-refractive-index materials to produce a double-layer anti-reflection film, which was successfully coated (Cartwright and Turner, 1939). In 1950, Wehner's article Momentum Transfer in Sputtering by Ion Bombardment marked the beginning of the sputtering theory (Dufour, 1950); semiconductor and microelectronics industries got off the ground (Gorham, 1991).

1.1.5 The last 50 years of the 20th century

In the 50 years after 1950, due to the rapid development of vacuum technology and vacuum measurement technology, thin-film technology was rapidly industrialized and took off. In 1955, O.S. Heavens first published a book called *Optical Properties of Thin Solid Films*, which laid the foundation for the subsequent development of optical films (Heavens, 1973); Wehner introduces the method of RF sputtering of dielectrics in the book (Wehner, 1955). In 1958, Gunther successfully developed the epitaxial growth technology of thin films (Günther, 1958). In 1959, Temescal Metallurgical Corp developed a corrosion-resistant and wear-resistant metal coating (Smith, 1959).

In 1965, Maissel successfully developed a biased sputter deposition process (Maissel and Schaible, 1965). In 1968, Mattox used ion plating to improve thin film deposition, which was later aggregated in the aerospace industry as ion vapour deposition (Mattox, 1968). In 1969, British scholar Macleod used interference matrix to explain and calculate optical thin films and published a monograph, "Thin-film Optical Filters" (Macleod, 1986). The illustration in the book shows a classic thin film deposition experiment, as shown in Figure 1.4.

Figure 1.4. Preparing a plant for the manufacture of narrowband filters. (Courtesy of Walter Nurnberg FIEP FRPS, the editors of Engineering, and Sir Howard Grubb, Parsons & Co Ltd.) (Macleod, 1986, p. 2)

In 1975, Japan's ULVAC company received an order from IBM for System731, the world's first fully automatic vacuum evaporation equipment (ULVAC Group, 1975); Murayama successfully developed the RF reactive ion coating technology and deposited three thin films of In₂O₃, TiN and TaN on glass substrates (Murayama, 1975); Penfold applied for a patent for columnar DC (cathode) magnetron sputtering technology (Penfold, 1975); Cho and Arthur developed molecular beam epitaxy (Cho and Arthur, 1975); Schiller developed alternating ion plating technology (Schiller, Heisig and Goedicke, 1975). In 1991, Rossnagel and Mikalsen introduced collimated magnetron sputter deposition (Rossnagel *et al.*, 1991). In 1992, Scherer *et al.* reported a new dual-cathode reactive AC magnetron sputter deposition method (Scherer *et al.*, 1992). In 1994, Rossnagel and Hopwood successfully developed a magnetron ionized

metal atom cathode sputtering technology (Rossnagel, 1994).

At the 35th Photovoltaic Experts Conference in Honolulu, Hawaii, in 2010, Mints (Mints, 2010) reported that the photovoltaic industry grew at a 33% compound growth rate over the 30 years from 1979 to 2009. From the first commercialization of thin-film photovoltaic products in 1982 to 2009, the thin-film photovoltaic industry had a higher compound annual growth rate than crystal products. In the 16 years from 1982 to 1998, thin-film photovoltaic power grew at a compound annual growth rate of 21%. Between 1999 and 2009, the thin-film photovoltaic industry grew at a compound annual growth rate (GR) of 52%, and the entire photovoltaic industry had a compound GR of 46% during this period. From 2004 to 2009, the production capacity of thin-film photovoltaic products increased by 2,509%, from 98 MWP to 2.5 GWP. The rapid growth of the thin film optical industry market reflects the huge development prospects of the thin film industry. The current thin-film materials market size is \$11.6 billion, and in 2029, the market size will reach \$16.12 billion, according to Maximize Market Research PVT. LTD (Maximize Market Research PVT. LTD, 2022).

Appendix 2: Summary of Thin film deposition technology

Most modern thin-film technologies are prepared under a vacuum, which is necessary for thin-film deposition processes. The deposition of thin films mainly include physical vapour deposition (PVD) and chemical vapour deposition (CVD). In PVD, the deposition of thin film material mainly comes from the surface of a solid or liquid. In CVD, the deposition material of the thin film mainly comes from the vapour of the gaseous reactant or the liquid reactant containing the thin film elements and the gas required for the reaction (Mattox, 2018). This section will focus on physical vapour deposition, including methods such as sputtering, thermal evaporation, and ion plating, and give a brief overview of chemical vapour deposition. Among them, the film deposition process used in this paper is the plasma-assisted microwave DC magnetron reactive sputtering deposition process.

2.1 Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD)

The process in which a thin film is deposited onto a substrate which is exposed to one or more volatile precursors that react or decompose on the substrate surface to produce the desired thin film is called chemical vapour deposition, as shown in Figure 2.1 (Martin, 2010; Madhuri, 2020). This process is widely used in the industrial field of high-temperature and corrosion protection.

Figure 2.1. Schematic diagram of traditional chemical vapour deposition (Madhuri, 2020).

Compared with other thin film deposition techniques, the CVD process can be controlled to very high precision for producing two-dimensional nanomaterials. Moreover, the CVD process can mass-produce 2D nanomaterials with high crystal quality and purity. These two-dimensional nanomaterials are not only used in the fields of electronics and optoelectronics but also the field of solar energy. However, CVD has disadvantage of high production costs,

which can be fatal when choosing a thin film manufacturing method (Pottathara *et al.*, 2019).

2.2 Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) - Vacuum Thermal Evaporation

After evaporation material is heated to a certain temperature in a vacuum environment, the material is vaporized or sublimated, and the phenomenon that its atoms or molecules escape from the surface is called thermal evaporation (Mattox, 2003, p. 19). Vacuum thermal evaporation is the first widely used vacuum coating technology (Mattox, 2018). Thermal evaporation mainly heats the evaporation material in two ways, one is heating by the resistance of a filament or crucible, and the other is heating by an electron beam. Because these two methods will not pollute or react with the materials used for evaporation during the heating process and will not release unnecessary gases during the heating process, they are the most suitable for thermal evaporation processes.

At a certain temperature, the pressure during the equilibrium process between the vapour of the evaporated material in the vacuum chamber and the solid or liquid is called the saturated vapour pressure at that temperature (Mattox, 2018). The saturated vapour pressure P_v can be derived from the Clausius-Clapeyron equation (the law of ideal gas) (LibreTexts, 2022):

$$\frac{dP_v}{dT} = \frac{\Delta H}{T(V_G - V_L)} \quad (2.1)$$

In the formula: ΔH is the molar heat of vaporization, V_G and V_L are the molar volumes of the vapour phase and liquid phase, respectively, and T is the absolute temperature (LibreTexts, 2022). Considering that the molar volume of the vapour phase is much larger than the molar volume of the liquid phase $V_G \gg V_L$, and the vaporized steam is considered as an ideal gas, it can be obtained:

$$V_G - V_L \approx V_G = \frac{RT}{P_v} \quad (2.2)$$

R is a constant, simplifying formula 2.1 and 2.2 can get:

$$\frac{dP_v}{P_v} = \frac{\Delta H \cdot dT}{R \cdot T^2} \quad (2.3)$$

Equation 2.3 is known as the Clausius-Clapeyron equation. In this way, since the heat of vaporization ΔH is a slowly varying function of temperature, ΔH can be approximately regarded as a constant and further integrated to obtain the change of equilibrium vapour pressure with temperature:

$$\ln P_v = C - \frac{\Delta H}{R \cdot T} \quad (2.4)$$

C is the integral constant, which can be simplified as:

$$\lg P_v = A - \frac{B}{T} \quad (2.5)$$

A and B are constants., The values of A and B can be measured in experiments. Equation 2.5 gives an approximate relationship between the vapour pressure and the temperature of the evaporating material. This relationship can be used to measure almost all elements' saturation vapour pressures and draw vapour pressure curves. According to these curves, it is easy to obtain: the temperature required to achieve the normal film evaporation rate, the sensitivity of the evaporation rate to temperature changes, and whether the evaporation state is melting or sublimation (Jinfa *et al.*, 2006). The two main types of thermal evaporation, resistive heating and electron beam are briefly described below.

2.2.1 Resistance Heating Thermal Evaporation

Resistive heating evaporation is also known as filament evaporation, and these resistive evaporation filaments are fabricated into different physical structures. For example, tantalum (Ta), molybdenum (Mo), tungsten (W) and other high-melting-point metals are used to make an evaporation source of appropriate shape. The material to be evaporated is placed in it. The evaporation material is directly heated and evaporated, or the material is put into a crucible to be evaporated such as alumina (Al₂O₃) or beryllium oxide (BeO) for indirect heating and evaporation, which is the resistance heating evaporation method (Jinfa *et al.*, 2006; Mattox, 2018; Kafle, 2020a). It is worth noting that this method is only suitable for materials with a low melting point (1000 °C - 2000 °C), and the melting point of the evaporation source material must be much higher than the evaporation temperature. This prevents the evaporation source material from affecting the film quality as an impurity.

Figure 2.2 is a schematic diagram of a resistive thermal evaporation system (Kafle, 2020a). A good vacuum is required during the evaporation process, at least controlled in a vacuum environment of 10⁻⁵ mTorr, to ensure that the evaporation trajectory of the atoms before condensing on the substrate will not be disturbed by too many factors (Li and Chu, 2016). In the figure, a resistance wire is used as a heater to heat the evaporated material placed in the evaporator and finally deposited on the substrate to form a thin film., Heat is generated after electrification, the material evaporates, and the resistivity increases accordingly. When the

temperature reaches 1000 °C, the resistivity of the evaporation source is 4 - 5 times that of room temperature; at 2000 °C, the resistivity increases to 10 times (Lévy, 2016). In this way, the molecules or atoms of the evaporation material can obtain enough kinetic energy from the Joule heat generated on the evaporator to evaporate (Jinfa *et al.*, 2006).

Figure 2.2. Resistive heating evaporation system (Kafle, 2020a).

The advantages of the resistive heating evaporation process are; simple equipment, convenient operation, and easy automatic deposition of thin films. However, its shortcomings are also obvious. Refractory metals and high-temperature medium materials cannot be directly evaporated; direct contact with evaporation materials during heating is prone to contamination of thin film materials. Therefore, on this basis, people have developed electron beam heating evaporation, which can effectively reduce these shortcomings.

2.2.2 Electron Beam Heating Thermal Evaporation

When a metal is in a high-temperature state, some of its electrons have gained enough energy to eject from the surface, this process is used in electron beam thermal evaporation.

Figure 2.3 (Bashir *et al.*, 2020) is a schematic of an electron beam thermal evaporation apparatus. Increasing the voltage to the filament generates heat after being energized, the resistivity increases, and thermionic emission of electrons occurs. The thermal electrons emitted from the cathode are accelerated by the high-voltage electric field between the cathode and the anode and converge into beams. The direction of electron movement is

changed under the influence of the external magnetic field. Such a high-speed moving electron beam bombards the material's surface to be coated under the deflection of the electromagnetic field so that the kinetic energy is converted into heat energy, thereby evaporating the material. Placing the filament under the evaporation material prevents the filament from being ejected together with electrons after being heated and melted, thus polluting the evaporation material (Bashir *et al.*, 2020). The characteristics of electrons being gathered depend on factors such as the filament's position and size of the high-voltage electric field of the cathode and anode (Jinfa *et al.*, 2006). The degree to which the electron beam is deflected depends on the magnitude of the field current. Finally, the evaporated material atoms are deposited on the above constantly rotating substrate, and the uniformity of the deposited film is ensured by rotation at a certain speed.

Figure 2.3. Schematic diagram of electron beam thermal evaporation (Bashir et al., 2020).

Compared with the resistive thermal evaporation mentioned above, electron beam thermal evaporation has the advantage of evaporating high melting point materials; electron beam evaporated material will only be deposited on the surface of the substrate material, and there will be no contamination of the film due to melting of the crucible or resistance wire; due to the greater energy density during evaporation, the kinetic energy of evaporated molecules increases, resulting in a denser film and improved film quality; less heat loss, and high melting point materials can be evaporated with less power (Mattox, 2003, 2018; Bashir *et al.*,

2020). In addition, rapid evaporation can be achieved when evaporating alloy materials to avoid the fractionation of alloys (Jinfa *et al.*, 2006).

2.3 Ion plating Deposition technology (PVD)

An ion plating is a new film deposition process that combines vacuum thermal evaporation and sputtering (Effects, Growth and Potential, 2009; Mattox, 2018). It ionizes the evaporated particles in the evaporation path from the evaporation source to the substrate and then accelerates to the substrate with negative bias voltage. Figure 2.4 is the schematic diagram of ion plating (Effects, Growth and Potential, 2009).

Because ion plating is a process that combines thermal evaporation and sputtering, its advantages are as follows: (1) The adhesion of the film is stronger. The bombardment of high-energy particles will bring several different effects. The bombardment of the substrate makes the substrate cleaner. It generates high temperature so that the reaction can proceed quickly, makes molecules or atoms with poor adhesion leave the substrate by sputtering, and promote the diffusion and chemical reaction of thin film materials on the substrate surface. (2) The quality of the film is higher, and the density of the film layer is denser. The surface mobility of high-energy particles is relatively large and sputtering again can eliminate the negative effect during film deposition, improving the film density. (3) The uniformity of the film is better, and the film deposition can be performed on both the front and rear surfaces of the substrate. (4) The film deposition rate is faster (Jinfa *et al.*, 2006; Effects, Growth and Potential, 2009; Mattox, 2018).

ION PLATING CONFIGURATIONS

Figure 2.4. Schematic diagram of ion plating with different structures. (a) Structure of thermal evaporation source bombarded by the plasma; (b) Electron beam thermal evaporation structure assisted by ion source; (c) Arc evaporation source structure bombarded by the plasma; (d) The structure in which the deposition source and the ion source alternately bombard the substrate (Effects, Growth and Potential, 2009).

The related applications of ion plating are also rich in variety. It is used to manufacture high-hardness mechanical tools and wear-resistant solid lubricating films and to manufacture durable decorative films on metals and plastics, for example, aluminium coating on aircraft fasteners to avoid galvanic corrosion; densification of high and low refractive index films on optical components (Effects, Growth and Potential, 2009).

2.4 Vacuum Sputtering (PVD)

The phenomenon of bombarding the surface (target) of a solid material with energetic particles, thereby causing solid atoms or molecules to be ejected from the surface of a solid material through momentum transfer, is called sputtering (Mattox, 2018), as shown in Figure 2.5 (Powell and Rossnagel, 1999a). Under the high-speed collision of incident ions, atoms or molecules are sputtered out of the solid surface, which is the basic condition for thin film deposition. The primary particles that sustain the glow discharge during sputtering are secondary electrons emitted during the sputtering process, whose energy is equal to the potential of the target.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 2.5. Schematic of the physical sputtering process (Powell and Rossnagel, 1999a, pp. 23–49).

The basis of the sputtering process is the glow discharge phenomenon of the gas. Glow discharge is when a current is passed through a gas to form a plasma. When the applied voltage exceeds the trigger voltage threshold, the ionization of the gas becomes self-sustaining, and the different colours of light emitted by different gases can be observed. Figure 2.6 (Chetvorno, 2013) shows a DC glow discharge's dark and bright regions and the corresponding potentials, field strengths and charge densities nearby. Since the electrons emitted by the cathode have an energy of only about 1 eV, the Aston Dark Space is formed near the cathode because the energy is too small to ionize or excite the atoms. Next to Aston Dark Space is the Cathode Glow, caused by the central atom formed by the decay of the excited gas molecules and the recombination of the particles entering the region after the accelerated electrons collide with the gas molecules.

As the electrons emitted by the cathode gain more energy and leave the cathode, the gas molecules will be ionized, producing many ions and low-speed electrons, forming a Cathode Dark Space that does not emit light related. The Cathode Dark Space generates the high-density positive ions required for sputtering. They are accelerated to the cathode, and the low-speed electrons are accelerated to the anode, forming the largest voltage drop and high space charge density region in the tube. Ionization in the Cathode Dark Space results in a high electron density, and low-velocity electrons are more likely to recombine with positive ions, which excites gas molecules to produce Negative Glow. The area between the Negative Glow and the Positive Column is the Faraday Dark Space. In this interval, as the electrons lose

energy, less and less light is emitted, thus becoming a Dark Space. During the sputtering process, the substrate is placed on the Negative Glow. However, the distance between the cathode and the substrate is at least 3 ~ 4 times that of the Cathode Dark Space (Fridman, 2012).

Figure 2.6. The phenomenon of DC glow discharge and its electrical characteristics (Chetvorno, 2013).

Momentum theory is the basic principle of thin film sputtering. The momentum theory is that after the ion hits the target, a part of the momentum is transferred to the target atom. If the target atom receives more kinetic energy than the sublimation heat energy, it can be separated from the lattice and ejected (Powell and Rossnagel, 1999a).

The sputtering threshold is the minimum energy required for the incident ions to sputter atoms from the cathode target. The sputtering threshold is related to the element of the target. For elements of the same period in the periodic table, the larger the atomic number, the smaller the sputtering threshold. For most metals, the sputtering threshold ranges from 10 eV to 30 eV (Powell and Rossnagel, 1999a).

The sputtering rate Y refers to the ratio of the number of positive ions emitted on average to the number of atoms sputtered after the bombardment when positive ions hit the cathode target. The following formula can be used:

$$Y = \frac{(\text{number of ejected particles})}{(\text{number of incident particles})} \quad (2.6)$$

The sputtering rate is related to the type, energy, and angle of incident ions, the material type, lattice structure, surface state, heat of sublimation and other factors of the target. Figure 2.7 shows the relationship between different incident energies and metal material sputtering rates under the normal incidence of Ar ions (Jinfa *et al.*, 2006). The sputtering rate is proportional to the energy of the incident ions. Still, after the energy reaches a certain level, the sputtering rate tends to saturate and decline because the probability of sputtering increases because the accelerated ions are driven deeper into the target (Powell and Rossnagel, 1999a).

*Figure 2.7. The relationship between the energy of normally incident Ar⁺ and the sputtering rate of some metals (Jinfa *et al.*, 2006).*

When sputtering with different sputtering particles, heavy metal elements can obtain higher particle energy, and light metal elements can obtain larger particle velocity. The energy of the sputtered particles will increase due to the mass of the target element. In contrast, the energy of the sputtered particles is lower for materials with a high sputtering rate (Powell and Rossnagel, 1999a).

In summary, if a higher sputter deposition rate is desired, one can increase the cathode voltage

and current density. The other is using heavier particles to participate in sputtering or using a lower sputtering pressure. However, these parameters are limited in cathode sputtering, so the effective method is to change the electrode configuration or apply an appropriate magnetic field.

2.4.1 DC (direct current) Sputtering

DC sputtering is the earliest sputtering deposition method to be applied (Grove, 1852). It comprises two electrodes, cathode and anode, called secondary or cathode sputtering. After evacuating the chamber (sputtering chamber) to a back vacuum of $\sim 10^{-3}$ mTorr - 10^{-4} mTorr, and injecting inert working gas (usually using Ar, the sputtering pressure is about 2^{-8} mTorr), several hundreds of volts will produce a glow discharge phenomenon. The ions are accelerated towards the target, and through the transfer of momentum, the target atoms are sputtered and deposited on the plated substrate. The schematic diagram is shown in Figure 2.8 (Frey, 2015).

Figure 2.8. Schematic diagram of DC sputtering (Frey, 2015, p. 144). a Inert gas inlet, b vacuum pump exhaust port, c cathode, d target, e anode, f substrate or deposition layer, g cathode black area, h anode area, i shield.

DC sputtering has the advantages of a simple structure and can be used for long-time sputtering. The disadvantage is also obvious. When sputtering dielectric materials is required, the sputtering rate is low due to the insulating properties of the dielectric materials. The surface of the substrate will generate a higher temperature after being bombarded by electrons for a long time, so it is necessary to select a substrate material that can withstand high temperatures (Frey, 2015).

2.4.2 Radio Frequency Sputtering

Radio Frequency (RF) indicates the electromagnetic frequency that can be radiated into space. The frequency range is between 300 kHz and 300 GHz. RF sputtering is a technique that uses radio frequency technology to change the electric potential in a vacuum environment (Low *et al.*, 2021). The principle of the traditional RF sputtering system is shown in Figure 2.9(a)(b).

*Figure 2.9. (a) Conventional RF Sputtering System (Ohring, 2002b) (b): Voltage period of the RF sputtering (Jinfa *et al.*, 2006).*

The DC cathode sputtering process introduced above cannot be used to sputter dielectric insulating materials. It is because if an insulating material target is used in a DC sputtering device, the positive ions bombarding the target surface will accumulate on the target surface, making it positively charged, and the target potential will rise accordingly, making the electric field between the electrodes gradually smaller until the glow discharge is extinguished and the sputtering stops, the DC sputtering device cannot sputter and deposit insulating dielectric films. For sputter deposited insulating materials, DC power is replaced by AC power. Since the positive and negative of the AC power supply alternate periodically, when the sputtering target is in the positive half cycle, electrons flow to the target surface, neutralize the positive charges accumulated on the surface, and accumulate electrons to make the surface present have a negative bias. During the negative half cycle of the RF voltage, positive ions are attracted to bombard the target, thereby realizing sputtering, as shown in Figure 2.9(b). Since ions are more massive than electrons, their mobility is small, and they don't concentrate on the target surface as quickly as electrons. Therefore, the electrons on the target surface rises slowly, and a negative bias voltage is formed on the target. The radio frequency sputtering device can also sputter a conducting target (Low *et al.*, 2021).

The radio frequency AC electric field enables electrons and ions to bombard the target

alternately. When the two poles are connected with a radio frequency power supply (usually using an industrial frequency of 13.56 MHz), the electrons in the plasma between the two poles, which are constantly oscillating, will obtain energy from the high-frequency electric field. The electrons that have gained enough energy will collide with the gas molecules introduced into the chamber and ionize them to generate many electrons and ions. At this time, generating secondary electrons to maintain the discharge no longer needs to be in a high-vacuum environment, and the high-frequency electric field can be coupled into the chamber through other impedance forms. Therefore, the electrodes of RF sputtering systems are no longer limited to conductive materials. Since the radio frequency sputtering method will generate a self-bias on the target. The target will be in a relatively large negative potential state while the radio frequency electric field is acting. As a result, the gas ions are spontaneously bombarded and sputtered. On the substrate, the self-bias voltage is small, and the bombardment and sputtering of gas ions on it will be negligible, which is the main deposition process of radio frequency sputtering.

The self-bias voltage is because the mass of electrons is much smaller than that of ions, so the movement speed of electrons is much larger than that of ions. Therefore, relative to the plasma, any part near the plasma is in a negative potential state. Assuming there is no charge accumulation on an electrode at the beginning after being driven by RF voltage, it can act as an anode to receive electrons and a cathode to receive ions. As shown in Figure 2.9(b), in a positive half cycle, the electrode will receive many electrons and make the electrode negatively charged. In the following negative half-cycle, it will accept a small number of ions moving slower, so its negative charge is partially neutralized. After a few cycles, the electrode will have a certain amount of negative charge and present a certain negative potential to the plasma.

RF sputtering can be used to sputter insulating dielectric materials. If you want to sputter metal materials, you only need to connect a capacitor in series with the target electrode. However, compared with the cathode sputtering system powered by a DC power supply, the power supply of RF sputtering is bulky and relatively expensive, and the radio frequency noise emitted by the system may even affect the operation of other electrical equipment. In order to overcome the above shortcomings, people have developed a film deposition method called magnetron sputtering.

2.4.3 Magnetron Sputtering

The definition of a magnetron is a device that controls the direction of electron movement through a magnetic field. Magnetron sputtering is a high deposition rate vacuum thin film deposition process that enables the deposition of many types of materials onto many types of substrates by using a special magnetic field applied to a diode sputtering target (Juhasz and Best, 2011). People first used sputtering for thin film deposition, then turned to evaporation in the 1940s due to the higher deposition rate, and finally returned to sputtering after the invention of the magnetron in 1978 (Thornton, 1978).

Most disadvantages of the sputtering processes described above are due to the low sputtering rate, especially the cathode sputtering process. Its ionization rate of gas molecules during the discharge process is only 0.3%~0.5% (Jinfa *et al.*, 2006). In order to perform sputtering with a high deposition rate under low pressure, it is necessary to increase the ionization rate of the gas effectively. In magnetron sputtering, due to the introduction of an orthogonal electromagnetic field, the ionization rate of the gas is increased from 5% to 6%, which is ten times or higher than other sputtering deposition processes (Helmersson *et al.*, 2006). For many materials, the sputtering rate under magnetron even reaches the rate of electron beam evaporation.

The gas ionization rate can be increased by using an orthogonal electromagnetic field because the electrons in the orthogonal electromagnetic field will make helical motion due to the action of the electromagnetic field, and this motion greatly increases the probability of collision between electrons and gas molecules. However, the mass of ions is much larger than that of electrons. When ions make a cycloidal motion under the action of an electric field, they have already bombarded the target and transferred all the energy they carry to the target (Jinfa *et al.*, 2006).

The strength of the magnetic field will also directly affect the amount of magnetic flux passing through the surface of the target, which directly determines the degree of magnetron control. Since the magnetic field is mostly inhomogeneous, the surface of the target is also irregular. After multiple sputtering times, the target will become thinner and thinner due to sputtering, the magnetic flux will increase, and sputtering will become easier. This phenomenon will reduce the utilization rate of the target.

Three kinds of magnetron sputtering methods are using commonly: planar magnetron,

cylindrical magnetron and S-gun magnetron sputtering (Greene, 2017). This discussion mainly includes the planar magnetron sputtering process.

Figure 2.10. Cross section of circular or rectangular targets and fixed magnet arrays (Smith, 1996, p. 483; Powell and Rossnagel, 1999b).

As shown in Figure 2.10, this is the schematic diagram of the commonly used planar magnetron sputtering configuration. A magnetic field B of $2 \times 10^{-2} T - 5 \times 10^{-2} T$ (200 G - 500 G) magnitude is formed on the surface of the target by a permanent magnet (Vossen, 1980, p. 135). The high-voltage electric field E between this magnetic field B and the substrate constitutes an orthogonal electromagnetic field (i.e. Lorentz force). Under the action of the electric field E , the electrons move to the substrate and collide with the incoming working gas (usually Ar) during the movement so that they are ionized to generate positive ions and new electrons; the new electrons continue to move to the substrate, and the positive ions generated by the ionization are accelerated to the cathode target under the action of the electric field, and bombard the surface of the target with high energy, causing the target to sputter. In the sputtered particles, the neutral target atoms or molecules form a thin film on the substrate, and the secondary excited electrons will drift in the direction of $E \times B$ under the action of the orthogonal electromagnetic field that interacts with the electric field and magnetic field. It is called $E \times B$ drift, and its trajectory is similar to a cycloid. Suppose the magnetic field forms a closed loop. In that case, the electrons will move in a circular motion on the surface of the target in an approximate cycloidal form, which makes the path of the electrons longer and trapped in the plasma region close to the surface of the target. At the same time, many positive ions ionized in this region bombard the target under the acceleration

of the electric field, thereby obtaining a higher deposition rate (Smith, 1996).

Magnetron sputtering can not only obtain a high deposition rate, but also, as the number of collisions increases when sputtering metal, the energy of the secondary electrons will be exhausted gradually and gradually move away from the target surface, and finally are incident, under the action of an electric field on the substrate (Powell and Rossnagel, 1999b). Because the electron energy is very low, the energy transferred to the substrate is very small, so the substrate can maintain a lower temperature. This phenomenon is of great significance to single-crystal materials and plastic substrates. Magnetron sputtering can work with both DC and RF discharges, which enables the successful preparation of both metallic and dielectric thin films. However, the current magnetron sputtering is still not perfect. It cannot realize low-temperature and high-speed sputtering of ferromagnetic materials because almost all magnetic flux needs to pass through the magnetic target, so an external magnetic field cannot be applied near the surface of the target; the insulating target will cause the temperature of the substrate to rise due to the long sputtering time, which will lead to a decrease in the quality of the film; because the uneven erosion of the target will lead to low utilization, only 30% of the target can be used, which increases the cost of consumables.

2.4.4 Ion Beam Sputtering

Ion Beam Sputtering (IBS), also known as Ion Beam Deposition (IBD), is an important method for preparing high-quality thin films, which has been widely used in optical communication wavelength division multiplexing filters (Becker and Scheuer, 1990; Sargent and O'Brien, 2003). Its working principle is not complicated. It is a method of bombarding a target with a high-energy ion source and sputtering the material, forming a thin film deposited on the sample's surface (Kafle, 2020b). The film properties of ion beam-deposited films, such as refractive index, absorption, scattering, adhesion, and packing density, can be fine-tuned by changing the parameters of the beam. Ion beam deposition (IBD) is one of three methods of depositing thin films using ion beam sputtering, the other two being reactive ion beam deposition (RIBD) and ion beam assisted deposition (IBAD) (Sargent and O'Brien, 2003).

Figure 2.11(a) is an ion beam sputtering system with a single ion source, while Figure 2.11(b) is an ion beam-assisted sputtering system that includes two ion sources (Abela, 2010, p. 301). The structure of Figure 2.11(a) is easy to understand. The ion beam emitted by the ion source bombards the target and sputters the material onto the substrate. The structure of Figure

2.11(b) is a little more complicated. This system is characterized by using a high-power sputtering ion source to generate high-density high-energy ions to bombard the target because high-speed sputtering deposition can be implemented under high-vacuum conditions. The energy of the auxiliary ion source on the side is low, which is used to improve the density and reactivity of the film and realize the preparation of ultra-low optical loss and super multi-layer film at low temperatures (Abela, 2010).

Figure 2.11. (a) Schematic diagram of an ion beam sputtering system, (b) Schematic diagram of an ion beam assisted sputtering system (Abela, 2010, p. 301).

For ion beam sputtering, ion impact flux and neutral ratio, base and operating pressure, ion energy and substrate temperature are all important process parameters. These parameters are generally within the controllable range of the hardware, so the film's physical structure and growth deposition rate can be controlled by changing the parameters (Abela, 2010). Generally, an RF excitation source with a frequency of 13.56 MHz is used as an ion source. It will effectively ionize the Ar gas when the positive electric field focuses the ion source discharges and the ions generated by the ionization. After being accelerated by the negative electric field of the accelerating grid, the neutraliser will neutralise them and then bombard the target. The working gas of the sputtering ion source and the neutralizer is generally Ar gas, while the auxiliary ion source uses a mixed reaction gas and Ar gas. The oxygen and argon flow ratio needs to be greater than 0.6 for commonly used oxide films. Otherwise, the oxide film is easily absorbed (Smith, 1996; Jinfu *et al.*, 2006; Abela, 2010).

Ion beam sputtering technology has been widely used in high-precision optical thin film technology. Its system stability is superior, and its working air pressure, electron beam current density, accelerating voltage, and other unstable factors can be controlled within 0.5% during long-term work. And the film deposition speed is fast, and the optical and mechanical properties are better than others. The main disadvantage is that the uniformity of the deposited

film is poor compared to electron beam thermal evaporation. Moreover, during the sputtering process, the grid of the ion source will be deformed so that the thickness of the film will change, and at the same time, the internal stress of the film will increase.

2.4.5 Reactive Sputtering

Wasa et al. (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012) introduced the definition of reactive sputtering in their book *Handbook of Sputter Deposition Technology (Second Edition)*: "Reactive sputtering is defined by the reaction between atoms sputtered from a metal target and reactive gas molecules diffused from a discharge gas on the substrate to produce compound thin films." The basic process of reactive sputtering is depositing a compound film on a substrate. After the metal atoms sputtered from the metal target through the inert working gas are combined with the active molecules of the reactive gas and react, they are deposited on the substrate and form a compound film (Ohring, 2002a). When the reaction occurs on the substrate, the deposited film should be metal or metal oxide, and the reaction will be affected by the deposition rate and the pressure of the reactive gas. Reaction sources are divided into two different types: one is a gas source, and the other is a solid source (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012).

Generally used targets for reactive sputtering with a gas source are pure metals, alloys or mixtures. The gas source is a reactive gas mixture mixed with a reactive gas and an inert working gas. For example, reactive sputtering of metals in O₂ to obtain corresponding metal oxides, nitrides in N₂ or NH₃, Nitrogen oxides obtained in O₂+N₂ mixed gas, carbides obtained in C₂H₂ or CH₄, fluorides obtained in HF or CF₄, etc., are shown in Table 2.1 (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012).

Table 2.1. Different reactive gases used in different reactive sputtering (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012).

Compound	Reactive Gas or Liquid
Oxide	Air, O ₂ , or H ₂ O
Nitride	N ₂ or NH ₃
Oxy-nitrides	O ₂ + N ₂
Sulfides	H ₂ S
Carbides	C ₂ H ₂ or CH ₄
Fluorides	HF or CF ₄
Arsenide	As

There are necessary conditions for the reaction between the reactants. The reactant molecules must have enough energy to form an intermolecular Kroff barrier. The relationship between potential barrier ε' and energy is as follows: Formula 2.7:

$$E_a = N_A \varepsilon' \quad (2.7)$$

Figure 2.12. Schematic diagram of the energy change of the reactants during the reaction.

In formula 2.7, E_a is the activation energy of the reaction, and N_A is Avogadro's constant. According to the transition state model theory, when the molecules of the two reactants react, they first pass through the transition state of the activated complex and then react to form the reactant, as shown in Figure 2.12.

Thin film deposition equipment (such as Microdyn) sends the reaction gas and the sputtering gas to the vicinity of the substrate and the target respectively to form a pressure gradient. That

can effectively reduce the phenomenon of target poisoning (this will be introduced in the introduction of the principle of Microdyn in the second chapter below), as shown in Figure 2.13 (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012, p. 332).

Figure 2.13 is a schematic diagram of DC magnetron reactive sputtering (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012). This equipment is to fix the substrate on the drum, and the drum makes a uniform circular motion in the chamber. The right side is divided into two areas. One is the sputtering area, and the other is the oxidation area. In the sputtering area, the metal atoms on the target are sputtered out by the DC magnetron and deposited on the substrate. As the drum rotates, the substrate is immediately transferred to the oxidation zone, where the substrate deposited with metal atoms reacts rapidly with the ionised reactive gas. In the figure, the oxygen ion is the oxidation reaction. An oxide film is formed on the substrate with the implantation of oxygen ions. Because of the circular motion of the drum, the substrate is continuously cycled through the sputtering zone and the oxidation zone, and an oxide film is formed.

Figure 2.13. Schematic diagram of reactive sputtering (Wasa, Kanno and Kotera, 2012, p. 332).

Using the reactive sputtering process makes preparing metal oxide films from pure metals such as Ti, Ta, Zn and Sn, much easier. Al is easily oxidized, and it is easy to form a dense Al_2O_3 oxide film on the surface of the target, thereby affecting sputtering. Because of the low reactivity, obtaining a non-absorbing SiO_2 film from Si is difficult. Compared with other thin film sputtering methods, it is simpler to control the structure and composition of thin film

deposition using reactive sputtering, so it is easier to obtain thin films that have better optical and mechanical properties than films deposited using traditional thin film deposition methods.

2.4.6 Pulsed DC Magnetron Reactive Sputtering

Reactive sputtering has been introduced above, which is a thin film deposition method in which reactive gas or a mixture of reactive gas and inert gas reacts with a sputtered film (Westwood, Glocker; and Shah, 2018, p. 26). Generally, by sputtering in this way, a thin film compound will be formed on the substrate, which is the product of the reaction between the selected sputtering material and the incoming reactive gas (Westwood, Glocker; and Shah, 2018, p. 26). At present, because the control of pulsing the target and use of a magnetic field during reactive sputtering, thin films of many complex compounds (Song *et al.*, 2023) and multilayer designs (Song *et al.*, 2019; Zhou, Cai *et al.*, 2021) can be fabricated. Moreover, by using this film deposition method to deposit conductive materials (Alajlani *et al.*, 2017), non-conductive materials (Wang *et al.*, 2009) and their combined films (Fleming *et al.*, 2018), the deposition rate close to that of traditional sputtering materials can be achieved.

In reactive sputtering, to stably form a specific compound on the surface of the substrate, it is necessary to make the sputtering material react with the reactive gas and "land" on the substrate's surface by the partial pressure of the gas. If the reactant finally formed on the target after the reaction is a conductor, the sputtering is maintained stably. If the final reactant formed after the reaction is a non-conductive compound such as TiO_2 , AlN or Al_2O_3 , when the positive ions bombard the target, they cannot neutralize the electrons from the target, and a positive charge will form on the surface of the target (Westwood, Glocker; and Shah, 2018). In this case, the target becomes like a capacitor. If the dielectric constant of the compound region formed by the reaction is greater than the potential difference between one side of the discrete dark region of the compound in the chamber and one side of the target substrate region, more and more charge will accumulate on the target surface. In this case, the voltage drop in the dark region of the cathode (described above in DC sputtering) is reduced to a point where it cannot cause the sputtering of ions striking the target. Suppose the dielectric constant of the compound area formed by the reaction is smaller than the potential difference between the dark area of the insulating layer and the target side. In that case, the compound area formed by the reaction will be broken down. This situation causes most of the discharge current to be concentrated in a small surface volume and causes localized evaporation, a

phenomenon known as the "arc" of the target (Boxman, Sanders and Martin, 1996). Generally, when an "arc" appears, there will be a change in the potential of the target and a drastic change in the concentration of the reactant gas. Generally, it will lead to uneven film quality and some film material defects. The phenomenon of arcing results in particles with large sizes to be ejected from the target surface and land on the substrate, disrupting coating homogeneity and stoichiometry and therefore negatively impacting its optical properties (Westwood, Glocker; and Shah, 2018).

Therefore, to reduce the appearance of arcing, people invented AC and pulsed DC reactive sputtering (Steidel, Jaffe and Kumagai, 1972; Cormia, Trumbly and Andresen, 1977). From the estimated thickness of the dielectric compound, the frequency needed to sufficiently avoid arcing is on the order of kHz . AC or pulsed DC magnetron reactive sputtering can be performed at 10 kHz using an electron current to discharge the positive charges accumulated on the target surface. Through the phenomenon that the anode discharges when the potential is positive in traditional sputtering, a large positive voltage is applied at the target to maintain the diode discharge mode (Cormia, Trumbly and Andresen, 1977). In this case, sputtering occurs only during the negative half-cycle, and electrons neutralize the excess positive charge during the positive half-cycle.

Appendix 3: Software

In Appendix 3, instructions to write the MCU for the purpose of controlling the stepper motor. First of all, if you want to control the stepper motor through a program compiled in the MCU, you need to define each parameter of the stepper motor and define them on different pins of the MCU by using the high and low levels of each pin of the MCU to control the actions of different synchronous motors. This can be accomplished by programming the MCU using code as shown in Figure 3.1.

```
#include <Stepper.h>

const int stepsPerRevolution = 200;           // 400 steps per revolution
const int BUTION1 = 12;
const int BUTION2 = 13;
boolean statel = true;
boolean state2 = true;
// initialize the stepper library on pins 8 through 11; P2.0 P2.1 P2.2 P2.3 ; BIN1 AIN2 AIN1 BIN2
Stepper myStepper(stepsPerRevolution, 8,9,10,11);

int stepCount1 = 0;                          // number of steps the motor has taken
int stepCount2 = 0;
int Str;
int Stop1 = 0;
int Stop2 = 0;
int Stop3 = 0;
int Stop4 = 0;                              //stop1,2,3,4 are set variables
int sensorValue =0;
int i;
void(*resetFunc)(void)=0;
```

Figure 3.1. Energia IDE defines stepper motor parameters.

Then, the stepper motor is controlled through the instructions issued by the host computer (main PC), and the motion mode of the stepper motor needs to be defined. In the early version of the control program, spectrometer versions 1 and 2 defined the motion modes of the stepper motors as four modes: four-step angle forward rotation (code 0), four-step angle reverse rotation (Code 1), rotate forward until it touches the contact switch (code 2), and rotate in the reverse direction until it touches the contact switch (code 3), as shown in Figure 3.2.

```

if(Str == '0')
{
  if(state1 == LOW)
  {
    myStepper.setSpeed(0);           //Set RPM to 0
    myStepper.step(0);              //Set the number of steps the motor rotates to 0 steps,
    resetFunc();                   //and the direction is positive rotation
  }
  else
  myStepper.setSpeed(30);          //Set RPM to 30
  myStepper.step(4);              //Set the number of steps the motor rotates to 4 steps, and the direction is positive rotation
  delay(500);                     //Delay 200 milliseconds;
  sensorValue = analogRead(5);     //The sensor value reads the value from the specified analog pin (pin 5)
  float voltage = sensorValue * (3.3 / 1023.0); //Print out the value read:
                                     //3.3/1023 is the reading resolution
                                     //Input voltages between 0 and 3.3V are mapped to integer values between 0 and 1023
  Serial.println(voltage);        //Print data to the serial port as human-readable ASCII text
  Str = Stop1;
}

if(Str == '1')
{
  if(state2 == LOW)
  {
    myStepper.setSpeed(0);
    myStepper.step(0);
    resetFunc();
  }
  else
  myStepper.setSpeed(30);          //Set the RPM to 30
  myStepper.step(-4);             //Set the number of steps the motor rotates to 4 steps, and the direction is reverse rotation
  delay(500);                     //Delay 200 milliseconds;
  sensorValue = analogRead(5);     //The sensor value reads the value from the specified analog pin (pin 5)
  float voltage = sensorValue * (3.3 / 1023.0); //print out the read value
  Serial.println(voltage);        //Print data to the serial port as human readable ASCII text

  Str = Stop2;
}

if(Str == '2')
{
  for (state1; state1==HIGH;)
  {
    state1 = digitalRead(BUTTON1);
    myStepper.setSpeed(30);
    myStepper.step(4);
    sensorValue = analogRead(5);
    float voltage = sensorValue * (3.3 / 1023.0); // print out the value you read:
    Serial.println(voltage);
    delay(500);
  }
  Str = Stop3;
}

```

```

if(Str == '3'){
  for(state2;state2==HIGH;)
  {
    state2 = digitalRead(BUTTON2);
    myStepper.setSpeed(30);
    myStepper.step(-4);
    sensorValue = analogRead(5);
    float voltage = sensorValue * (3.3 / 1023.0);    // print out the value you read:
    Serial.println(voltage);
    delay(500);
  }
}

```

Figure 3.2. MCU control program for controlling ST2018.

Therefore, when the main PC control software sends a signal (code 0, 1, 2, 3) to the MCU, the MCU will run the control types corresponding to these four modes.

Finally, the program is improved in spectrometer version 3 of the large motor control MCU program. Because the motor signal is different, the definition of the motor pin and the drive signal have changed. In addition, the four motion modes of the motor are reduced to three, and only four-step angles of forward rotation (code 0), a one-step angle of reverse rotation (code 1) and a stop mode (code 2) are added. The details are shown in Figure 3.3. In this way, the program of the MCU is simplified, the response to the command of the main PC is improved, and the situation that the stepper motor cannot be stopped will no longer appear.

```

if(Str == '0') //close to the motor
{
  if(statel == LOW)
  {
    Str = Stop1;
    Serial.println("a");
    delay(200);
  }
  else
  {
    digitalWrite(dirPin, HIGH); // Set the spinning direction CW/CCW (HIGH is counterclockwise)
                                // Enables the motor to move in a particular direction
                                // Makes 200 pulses for making one full cycle rotation

    for(int x = 0; x < 2; x++)
    {
      // These four lines result in 1 steps:
      digitalWrite(stepPin, HIGH);
      delayMicroseconds(800);
      digitalWrite(stepPin, LOW);
      delayMicroseconds(800);
    }
    delay(200); // 200ms delay

    sensorValue = analogRead(11); //The sensor value reads the value from the specified analog pin (pin 11)
    float voltage = sensorValue * (3.3 / 1023.0); //Print out the value read:
                                                //3.3/1023 is the reading resolution
                                                //Input voltages between 0 and 3.3V are mapped to integer values between 0 and 1023

    Serial.println(voltage); //Print data to the serial port as human-readable ASCII text
    //Serial.print("CCW");
    Str = Stop1;
  }
}
}

```

```

if(Str == '1')
{
    //away from the motor
    if(state2 == LOW)
    {
        Str = Stop2;
        Serial.println("b");
        delay(200);
    }
    else
    {
        digitalWrite(dirPin, LOW); // Set the spinning direction CW/CCW (LOW is clockwise)
        // Enables the motor to move in a particular direction
        // Makes 200 pulses for making one full cycle rotation

        for(int x = 0; x < 2; x++)
        {
            // These four lines result in 1 steps:
            digitalWrite(stepPin, HIGH);
            delayMicroseconds(800);
            digitalWrite(stepPin, LOW);
            delayMicroseconds(800);
        }
        delay(200); // 200ms delay
        sensorValue = analogRead(11); //The sensor value reads the value from the specified analog pin (pin 11)
        float voltage = sensorValue * (3.3 / 1023.0); //Print out the value read:
        //3.3/1023 is the reading resolution
        //Input voltages between 0 and 3.3V are mapped to integer values between 0 and 1023
        //Print data to the serial port as human-readable ASCII text

        Serial.println(voltage);
        //Serial.print("CW");
        Str = Stop2;
    }
}

if(Str == '2')
{
    Str = Stop3;
    Serial.println("stop3");
}

```

Figure 3.3. The stepper motor control program used in the spectrometer version 3.

List of publications

In Scientific Journals

Shun Zhou, Shigeng Song, Sijia Cai, Daxing Han, Zhentao Wu, Jian Song, Bo Lu, Zhengping Jiang, David Lovering, Weiguo Liu, and Des Gibson. Development of measurement system and analysis method for characterization of linear variable bandpass filters[J]. *Optics Express*, 2021, 29(14): 21386-21399.

Shigeng Song, Sijia Cai, Daxing Han, Carlos García Nuñez, Gong Zhang, Gavin Wallace, Lewis Fleming, Kieran Craig, Stuart Reid, Iain W. Martin, Sheila Rowan, and Des Gibson. Tantalum oxide and silicon oxide mixture coatings deposited using microwave plasma assisted co-sputtering for optical mirror coatings in gravitational wave detectors[J]. *Applied Optics*, 2023, 62(7): B73-B78.

In Conference Proceedings

Shigeng Song, Sijia Cai, Daxing Han, Carlos García Nuñez, Gong Zhan, Gavin Wallace, Lewis Fleming, Kieran Craig, Stuart Reid, Iain Martin, Sheila Rowan, and Des Gibson. Tantalum Oxide and Silica Mixture Coatings Deposited Using Microwave Plasma Assisted Co-sputtering for Optical Mirror Coatings in Gravitational Wave Detectors[C]//*Optical Interference Coatings*. Optica Publishing Group, 2022: WB. 2.

Jonathan Pomfret, Sijia Cai, Daxing Han, Des Gibson, Shigeng Song, David Hutson, and Peter Mackay. Design and Fabrication of a patterned dual colour filter using Microwave plasma assisted Sputtering and Photolithography[C]//*Optical Interference Coatings*. Optica Publishing Group, 2022: MD. 8.

Lewis Fleming, Des Gibson, Shigeng Song, David Hutson, Sam Ahmadzadeh, Sijia Cai, Daxing Han, Ewan Waddell, and John Saffell. High throughput microwave plasma assisted sputter deposition of linear variable filters and deployment into visible and near infrared spectrometers[C]//*Optical Interference Coatings*. Optica Publishing Group, 2022: ThC. 4.

References

- A.W.Wright (1877) 'Production of Transparent Metallic Films', *American Journal of Science and Arts (1820-1879)*, XIII(73), pp. 49–55.
- Abela, S. (2010) 'Physical vapour deposition of magnesium alloys', *Surface Engineering of Light Alloys: Aluminium, Magnesium and Titanium Alloys*, pp. 294–322. doi: 10.1533/9781845699451.2.294.
- Abney, W. D. W. and Festing, E. R. (1883) 'III. Note on the absorption spectrum of iodine in solution in carbon disulphide', *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London*, 34(220–223), pp. 480–482. doi: 10.1098/rspl.1882.0071.
- Advanced Energy Industries Inc. (2015) *Sparc-le V User Manual - REMRSEC Facilities*. Available at: <https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/view/50640627/sparc-le-v-user-manual-remrsec-facilities>.
- Águas, H. *et al.* (2015) 'Thin Film Silicon Photovoltaic Cells on Paper for Flexible Indoor Applications', *Advanced Functional Materials*, 25(23), pp. 3592–3598. doi: 10.1002/adfm.201500636.
- Alajlani, Y. *et al.* (2017) 'Characterisation of Cu₂O, Cu₄O₃, and CuO mixed phase thin films produced by microwave-activated reactive sputtering', *Vacuum*, 144, pp. 217–228. doi: 10.1016/j.vacuum.2017.08.005.
- Alexander, W. (2023) *MEMS - the smallest dimensions, the highest precision*. Available at: <https://www.hiperscan.com/en/mems-211>.
- ANDRADE, E. N. D. C. (1960) *The History of the Vacuum Pump, Fundamental Problems in Vacuum Techniques Ultra-High Vacuum*. Pergamon Press Ltd. doi: 10.1016/b978-1-4832-8302-9.50010-7.
- B&W Tek. (2023) *TE Cooled InGaAs Array Spectrometer (1.7µm)*. Available at: <https://bwtek.com/products/sol-1-7/>.
- Balabin, R. M., Safieva, R. Z. and Lomakina, E. I. (2007) 'Comparison of linear and nonlinear calibration models based on near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy data for gasoline properties prediction', *Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems*, 88(2), pp. 183–188. doi: 10.1016/j.chemolab.2007.04.006.

Balas, C., Pappas, C. and Epitropou, G. (2016) *Multi/Hyper-Spectral Imaging - Handbook of Biomedical Optics, Handbook of Biomedical Optics*.

Banger, K. K. *et al.* (2011) ‘Low-temperature, high-performance solution-processed metal oxide thin-film transistors formed by a “sol-gel on chip” process’, *Nature Materials*, 10(1), pp. 45–50. doi: 10.1038/nmat2914.

Bashir, A. *et al.* (2020) *Interfaces and surfaces, Chemistry of Nanomaterials*. INC. doi: 10.1016/b978-0-12-818908-5.00003-2.

Beć, K. B., Grabska, J. and Huck, C. W. (2020) ‘Principles and Applications of Miniaturized Near-Infrared (NIR) Spectrometers’, *Chemistry - A European Journal*, 27(5), pp. 1514–1532. doi: 10.1002/chem.202002838.

Becker, J. and Scheuer, V. (1990) ‘Coatings for optical applications produced by ion beam sputter deposition’, *Applied Optics*, 29(28), p. 4303. doi: 10.1364/AO.29.004303.

Belinskii, A. V. and Klyshko, D. N. (1993) ‘Interference of light and Bell’s theorem’, *Uspekhi Fizicheskikh Nauk*, 163(8), p. 1. doi: 10.3367/ufnr.0163.199308a.0001.

Benda, V. (2020) *Photovoltaics, including new technologies (Thin film) and a discussion on module efficiency, Future Energy: Improved, Sustainable and Clean Options for Our Planet*. Elsevier Ltd. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-08-102886-5.00018-9.

Benelmekki, M. and Erbe, A. (2019) ‘Nanostructured thin films background , preparation and relation to the technological revolution of the 21st century’, *Nanostructured Thin Films*, 14, pp. 1–34. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-08-102572-7.00001-5.

Blanco, M. *et al.* (2000) ‘NIR calibration in non-linear systems: Different PLS approaches and artificial neural networks’, *Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems*, 50(1), pp. 75–82. doi: 10.1016/S0169-7439(99)00048-9.

Boreysho, A. S. *et al.* (2007) ‘Detection of explosives traces on documents by attenuated total reflection method’, *International Conference on Lasers, Applications, and Technologies 2007: Environmental Monitoring and Ecological Applications; Optical Sensors in Biological, Chemical, and Engineering Technologies; and Femtosecond Laser Pulse Filamentation*, 6733, p. 67331W. doi: 10.1117/12.753346.

Boxman, R. L. (2001) ‘Early history of vacuum arc deposition’, *IEEE Transactions on*

- Plasma Science*, 29(5 I), pp. 759–761. doi: 10.1109/27.964470.
- Boxman, R., Sanders, D. and Martin, P. (1996) *Handbook of vacuum arc science & technology: fundamentals and applications*, Noyes publications. Available at: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780815513759500266>.
- Boyle, R., Sukumaran, S. and Chen, R. (2017) ‘Quantitative determination of hydrogen concentration in silicon nitride dielectric films on silicon wafers using FTIR spectroscopy’.
- Brimrose Corp (2021) ‘Data Sheet Versatile AOTF-NIR Spectrometer – Luminar 5030’. Available at: <https://www.brimrose.com/aotf-nir-spectrometers/luminar5030>.
- Bunshah, R. F. and Deshpandey, C. V. (1988) ‘Evaporation Processes’, *MRS Bulletin*, 13(12), pp. 33–39. doi: 10.1557/S0883769400063673.
- C. LUECK (2022) *The Story of MicroDyn*. Available at: <https://www.depsci.com/blog/the-story-of-microdyn/>.
- Cabib, D., Lavi, M. and Orr, H. (2010) ‘Revival of circular variable filters’, *Electro-Optical Remote Sensing, Photonic Technologies, and Applications IV*, 7835, p. 78350O. doi: 10.1117/12.864926.
- Carmine Fiore (2022) *Stepper Motors Basics: Types, Uses, and Working Principles*, MPS Proprietary Information. Patent Protected. Unauthorized Photocopy and Duplication Prohibited. Available at: <https://www.monolithicpower.cn/cn/stepper-motors-basics-types-uses>.
- Cartwright, H. and Turner, A. F. (1939) ‘Multilayer films of high reflecting power’, *Physical Review*, 55, p. 1128.
- Chen, C. *et al.* (2020) ‘Widely tunable mid-infrared light emission in thin-film black phosphorus’, *Science Advances*, 6(7), pp. 1–8. doi: 10.1126/sciadv.aay6134.
- Chetvorno (2013) *Glow discharge structure*, *Wikimedia*. Available at: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Glow_discharge_structure_-_English.svg.
- Cho, A. Y. and Arthur, J. R. (1975) ‘Molecular beam epitaxy’, *Progress in Solid State Chemistry*, 10, pp. 157–191. doi: 10.1016/0079-6786(75)90005-9.
- Choudhury, A. K. R. (2014) ‘Colour measurement instruments’, in *Principles of Colour and*

- Appearance Measurement*. Elsevier, pp. 221–269. doi: 10.1533/9780857099242.221.
- Cormia, R., Trumbly, T. and Andresen, S. (1977) ‘Method for coating a substrate’. Available at: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US4046659A/en>.
- Crookes, W. (1891) ‘Electrical Evaporation’, *Science*, ns-18(443), pp. 62–65. doi: 10.1126/science.ns-18.443.62.
- Delta Optical Thin Film A/S (2016) *Delta Optical Thin Film A/S announces the launch of several Linear Variable Bandpass Filters that are specifically designed for Hyperspectral Imaging*, *optics.org*. Available at: <https://optics.org/products/P000020892>.
- Dufour, C. (1950) ‘Mécanisme pour la préparation par évaporation dans le vide de filtres interférentiels à couleur variable’, *Journal de Physique et le Radium*, 11(7), pp. 353–354. doi: 10.1051/jphysrad:01950001107035300.
- Edison, T. A. (1880) ‘US Patent No. 223898’, *United States Patent*.
- Edison, T. (1892) ‘Process of duplicating phonograms’. doi: 10.1145/178951.178972.
- Edison, T. (1894) ‘Art of Plating one Material With Another’. Available at: <https://patentimages.storage.googleapis.com/f8/89/8a/4822c9bad685d0/US526147.pdf>.
- Edison, T. A. (1904) ‘Apparatus for vacuously depositing metals.’ Available at: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US767216A/en>.
- Effects, N., Growth, F. and Potential, S. (2009) *Ion Plating*. Third Edit, *Handbook of Deposition Technologies for Films and Coatings: Science, Applications and Technology*. Third Edit. Elsevier Ltd. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-8155-2031-3.00006-5.
- Emadi, A., Wu, H., de Graaf, G. and Wolffenbuttel, R. (2012a) ‘Design and implementation of a sub-nm resolution microspectrometer based on a Linear-Variable Optical Filter’, *Optics Express*, 20(1), p. 489. doi: 10.1364/oe.20.000489.
- Emadi, A., Wu, H., de Graaf, G. and Wolffenbuttel, R. (2012b) ‘Design and implementation of IR microspectrometers based on linear-variable optical filters’, *Optical Sensing and Detection II*, 8439, p. 84391O. doi: 10.1117/12.922320.
- Emadi, A., Wu, H., de Graaf, G., Enoksson, P., *et al.* (2012) ‘Linear variable optical filter-based ultraviolet microspectrometer’, *Applied Optics*, 51(19), p. 4308. doi:

10.1364/AO.51.004308.

Faraday, M. (1854) 'Experimental researches in electricity: Twenty-ninth series', *Royal Society*, 6(2053–9134), pp. 165–168. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspl.1850.0058>.

Faraday, M. (1857) 'Experimental Relations of Gold (and other Metals) to Light.', *Phil. Trans. R. Soc.*, 147(0), pp. 145–181. Available at: <http://rstl.royalsocietypublishing.org/cgi/doi/10.1098/rstl.1857.0011>.

Fleming, Cai, L. *et al.* (2022) 'High throughput microwave plasma assisted sputter deposition of linear variable filters and deployment into visible and near infrared spectrometers', in *Optical Interference Coatings Conference (OIC) 2022*. Washington, D.C.: Optica Publishing Group, p. ThC.4. doi: 10.1364/OIC.2022.ThC.4.

Fleming, L. *et al.* (2018) 'Reducing N₂O induced cross-talk in a NDIR CO₂ gas sensor for breath analysis using multilayer thin film optical interference coatings', *Surface and Coatings Technology*, 336, pp. 9–16. doi: 10.1016/j.surfcoat.2017.09.033.

Fraunhofer, J. (1817) 'Determination of the Refractive and Dispersive Power of Different Kinds of Glass, with Reference to the Perfecting of Achromatic Telescopes', *Denkschr. Konigl. Akad. Wiss.*, (Munich), pp. 193–226.

Fraunhofer, J. von (1817) 'Bestimmung des Brechungs- und des Farbenzerstreungs-Vermögens verschiedener Glasarten, in Bezug auf die Vervollkommnung achromatischer Fernröhre', *Annalen der Physik*, 56(7), pp. 264–313.

Frey, H. (2015) 'Cathode Sputtering', in *Handbook of Thin-Film Technology*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, pp. 133–165. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-05430-3_6.

Fridman, A. (2012) *Plasma chemistry*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Gardner, I. and Case, F. (1931) 'The making of mirrors by the deposition of metal on glass', *US Government Printing Office*.

Goeckner, M. J., Goree, J. A. and Sheridan, T. E. (1991) 'Monte Carlo simulation of ions in a magnetron plasma', *IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science*, 19(2), pp. 301–308. doi: 10.1109/27.106828.

Goran_tek-en (2023) *Dispersion_prism-svg*, *Wikimedia Commons*. Available at: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Dispersion_prism-svg.svg.

- Gorham, D. A. (1991) *A History of the World Semiconductor Industry*, *IEE Review*. doi: 10.1049/ir:19910162.
- Greene, J. E. (2014) ‘Tracing the 5000-year recorded history of inorganic thin films from ~3000 BC to the early 1900s AD’, *Applied Physics Reviews*, 1(4), p. 041302. doi: 10.1063/1.4902760.
- Greene, J. E. (2017) ‘Review Article: Tracing the recorded history of thin-film sputter deposition: From the 1800s to 2017’, *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology A: Vacuum, Surfaces, and Films*, 35(5), p. 05C204. doi: 10.1116/1.4998940.
- Grove, W. R. (1852) ‘VII. On the electro-chemical polarity of gases’, *Royal Society*, 142, pp. 87–101. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstl.1852.0008>.
- Günther, K. G. (1958) ‘Aufdampfschichten aus halbleitenden III-V-Verbindungen’, *Die Naturwissenschaften*, 45(17), pp. 415–416. doi: 10.1007/BF00603228.
- Güntherschulze, A. and Meyer, K. (1930) ‘Kathodenzerstäubung bei sehr geringen Gasdrücken’, *Zeitschrift für Physik*, 62(9–10), pp. 607–618. doi: 10.1007/BF01843478.
- H. A Macleod (2018) *Thin-Film optical filters 5th Edition*.
- Hablanian, M. H. (1997) *High-Vacuum Technology: A Practical Guide Mechanical Engineering (Marcel Dekker, Inc.), High-Vacuum Technology*. New York. doi: 10.1201/9780203751923.
- Hass, G. (1955) ‘Filmed Surfaces for Reflecting Optics*’, *Journal of the Optical Society of America*, 45(11), p. 945. doi: 10.1364/josa.45.000945.
- Heavens, S. (1973) *Optical Properties of Thin Solid Films, Vacuum*. doi: 10.1016/0042-207x(73)91379-1.
- Helmersson, U. *et al.* (2006) ‘Ionized physical vapor deposition (IPVD): A review of technology and applications’, *Thin Solid Films*, 513(1–2), pp. 1–24. doi: 10.1016/j.tsf.2006.03.033.
- Henderson, F. E. (1945) *Manufacture of Metal-lized Paper Capacitor Units, U.S. Technical Industrial Intelligence Committee*. Available at: <https://www.cdvandt.org/cios-xxvii-44.htm>.
- HERBERT, C. H. and LOU, H. H. (1912) *GEORGIUS AGRICOLA, De Re Metallica*:

Translated from the First Latin Edition of 1556 ... by Herbert Clark Hoover and Lou Henry Hoover. THE MINING MAGAZINE SALISBURY HOUSE, LONDON, E.G.

Herschel, W. (1800) 'XIV. Experiments on the refrangibility of the invisible rays of the sun', *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London*, 90(1), pp. 284–292. doi: 10.1098/rstl.1800.0015.

Hovis, W. A., Kley, W. A. and Strange, M. G. (1967) 'Filter Wedge Spectrometer for Field Use', *Applied Optics*, 6(6), p. 1057. doi: 10.1364/ao.6.001057.

Hulinks (2023) *Software for the Design and Manufacture of Optical Thin Film Coatings*. Available at: <https://www.hulinks.co.jp/en/tfcalc-e>.

INFICON Inc. (2001) *IC/5 Thin Film Deposition Controller*. USA.

Jeffrey, W. *et al.* (1995) 'Small satellites (MSTI-3) for remote sensing: pushing the limits of sensor and bus technology', in Barnes, W. L. and Horais, B. J. (eds) *Platforms and Systems*, pp. 206–216. doi: 10.1117/12.198948.

Jeter, J. W. and Blasius, K. R. (1999) 'Wedge spectrometer concepts for space IR remote sensing', in Larar, A. M. (ed.) *Optical Spectroscopic Techniques and Instrumentation for Atmospheric and Space Research III*, p. 211. doi: 10.1117/12.366375.

Jhabvala, M. *et al.* (2003) 'Development of a 4–15 μm infrared GaAs hyperspectral QWIP imager', *Infrared Physics & Technology*, 44(5–6), pp. 445–455. doi: 10.1016/S1350-4495(03)00172-5.

Jianfei, Z. *et al.* (2012) 'Structure Design and Analysis of a New Type MEMS Fabry-Perot Filter', *Acta Optica Sinica*, 32(8), p. 0822005. doi: 10.3788/AOS201232.0822005.

Jinfa, T. *et al.* (2006) *Modern optical thin film technology*. china, zhejiang: Zhejiang University Press.

Juhasz, J. A. and Best, S. M. (2011) 'Surface modification of biomaterials by calcium phosphate deposition', in *Surface Modification of Biomaterials*. Elsevier, pp. 143–169. doi: 10.1533/9780857090768.1.143.

Kafle, B. P. (2020a) *Introduction to nanomaterials and application of UV-Visible spectroscopy for their characterization, Chemical Analysis and Material Characterization by Spectrophotometry*. doi: 10.1016/b978-0-12-814866-2.00006-3.

- Kafle, B. P. (2020b) 'Introduction to nanomaterials and application of UV-Visible spectroscopy for their characterization', in *Chemical Analysis and Material Characterization by Spectrophotometry*. Elsevier, pp. 147–198. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-814866-2.00006-3.
- Karl Pearson (1916) 'IX. Mathematical contributions to the theory of evolution.—XIX. Second supplement to a memoir on skew variation', *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical or Physical Character*, 216(538–548), pp. 429–457. doi: 10.1098/rsta.1916.0009.
- Kirby, N. E. *et al.* (2006) 'The automatic alignment and mosaic of video frames from the variable interference filter imaging spectrometer', *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 27(21), pp. 4885–4898. doi: 10.1080/01431160600771553.
- Klein, M. E. *et al.* (2008) 'Quantitative hyperspectral reflectance imaging', *Sensors*, 8(9), pp. 5576–5618. doi: 10.3390/s8095576.
- Korpel, A. (1981) 'Acousto-Optics—A Review of Fundamentals', *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 69(1), pp. 48–53. doi: 10.1109/PROC.1981.11919.
- Krasilnikova, A. *et al.* (2005) 'Spatially resolved spectroscopy for non-uniform thin film coatings: comparison of two dedicated set-ups', in, p. 59651V. doi: 10.1117/12.625183.
- Langmuir, I. (1913) 'The Vapor Pressure of Metallic Tungsten', *Physical Review*, 2(5), pp. 329–342. doi: 10.1103/PhysRev.2.329.
- Langmuir, I. and Mackay, G. M. J. (1914) 'The vapor pressure of the metals platinum and molybdenum', *Physical Review*, 4(4), pp. 377–386. doi: 10.1103/PhysRev.4.377.
- Lemarquis, F., Abel-Tiberini, L. and Koc, C. (2010) '400-1000 Nm All-Dielectric Linear Variable Filters for Ultra Compact Spectrometers', 10565(October 2010), p. 515. doi: 10.1117/12.2552593.
- Lévy, F. (2016) 'Film Growth and Epitaxy: Methods', in *Reference Module in Materials Science and Materials Engineering*. Elsevier. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-803581-8.01012-2.
- Li, C. *et al.* (2017) 'Modeling and validation of uniform large-area optical coating deposition on a rotating drum using microwave plasma reactive sputtering', *Applied Optics*, 56(4), p. C65. doi: 10.1364/ao.56.000c65.
- Li, P. H. and Chu, P. K. (2016) 'Thin film deposition technologies and processing of

biomaterials', *Thin Film Coatings for Biomaterials and Biomedical Applications*, pp. 3–28. doi: 10.1016/B978-1-78242-453-6.00001-8.

LibreTexts (2022) 23.4: *The Clausius-Clapeyron Equation*. Available at: [https://chem.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Physical_and_Theoretical_Chemistry_Textbook_Maps/Physical_Chemistry_\(LibreTexts\)/23%3A_Phase_Equilibria/23.04%3A_The_Clausius-Clapeyron_Equation](https://chem.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Physical_and_Theoretical_Chemistry_Textbook_Maps/Physical_Chemistry_(LibreTexts)/23%3A_Phase_Equilibria/23.04%3A_The_Clausius-Clapeyron_Equation).

Loesel, J. and Laubier, D. (2008) 'Study of accessible performances of a spectro imager using a wedge filter', *Optical Design and Engineering III*, 7100, p. 710013. doi: 10.1117/12.796966.

Low, F. W. *et al.* (2021) 'Graphene and its derivatives, synthesis route, and mechanism for photovoltaic solar cell applications', in *Sustainable Materials for Next Generation Energy Devices*. Elsevier, pp. 103–132. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-820628-7.00005-8.

Lowndes, D. H. *et al.* (1996) 'Synthesis of novel thin-film materials by pulsed laser deposition', *Science*, 273(5277), pp. 898–903. doi: 10.1126/science.273.5277.898.

Macleod, H. A. (1986) 'Thin-Film Optical Filters', *Thin-Film Optical Filters*. doi: 10.1887/0750306882.

Madhuri, K. V. (2020) *Thermal protection coatings of metal oxide powders*, *Metal Oxide Powder Technologies*. INC. doi: 10.1016/b978-0-12-817505-7.00010-5.

Madsen, C. K. and Zhao, J. H. (1999) 'Optical Filter Design and Analysis: A Signal Processing Approach (Wiley Series in Microwave and Optical Engineering) Edition: 1', in *Optical Filter Design and Analysis*. New York, USA: John Wiley & Sons, Inc., p. 418. doi: 10.1002/0471213756.ch5.

Maissel, L. I. and Schaible, P. M. (1965) 'Thin films deposited by bias sputtering', *Journal of Applied Physics*, 36(1), pp. 237–242. doi: 10.1063/1.1713883.

Malter, L. and Marcuvitz, N. (1938) 'On a modification of hickman's distillation pump', *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 9(3), pp. 92–95. doi: 10.1063/1.1752444.

Martin, L. C., Wrbanek, J. D. and Fralick, G. C. (2001) 'Thin film sensors for surface measurements', *ICIASF Record, International Congress on Instrumentation in Aerospace Simulation Facilities*, (September), pp. 196–203.

Martin, P. M. (2010) 'Deposition Technologies', in *Handbook of Deposition Technologies for*

- Films and Coatings*. Elsevier, pp. 1–31. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-8155-2031-3.00001-6.
- Martynenko, Y. V., Rogov, A. V. and Shul'ga, V. I. (2012) 'Angular distribution of atoms during the magnetron sputtering of polycrystalline targets', *Technical Physics*, 57(4), pp. 439–444. doi: 10.1134/s1063784212040196.
- Mattox, D. (1968) 'Ion Plating Technique Improves Thin Film Deposition', 2(April), pp. 3–4. Available at: <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/19680000212/downloads/19680000212.pdf>.
- Mattox, D. M. (2003) *The Foundations of Vacuum Coating Technology, The Foundations of Vacuum Coating Technology*. doi: 10.1007/978-3-662-10329-6.
- Mattox, D. M. (2018) *The Foundations of Vacuum Coating Technology(Second Edition), The Foundations of Vacuum Coating Technology*. doi: 10.1007/978-3-662-10329-6.
- Maximize Market Research PVT. LTD (2022) *Thin Film Material Market: Global Overview and Forecast (2022-2029) by Deposition Process, Types, Applications, and Region*. Available at: <https://www.maximizemarketresearch.com/market-report/global-thin-film-material-market/72328/>.
- Maxwell, J. C. (1873) *Electricity and Magnetism, A Treatise on Electricity and Magnetism*. doi: 10.1017/cbo9780511709333.002.
- Mika, A. M. (1990) 'Linear-Wedge Spectrometer', *Spectroscopy*, 1298, pp. 127–131.
- Miller, M. F. *et al.* (2001) 'Process for integrating dielectric optical coatings into micro-electromechanical devices'. Available at: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US6271052B1/en>.
- Mints, P. (2010) 'The commercialization of thin film technologies: Past, present and future', *Conference Record of the IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference*, pp. 2400–2404. doi: 10.1109/PVSC.2010.5614355.
- Moss, A. R. and Richards, D. T. (1960) 'The arc-melting of niobium, tantalum, molybdenum and tungsten', *Journal of The Less-Common Metals*, 2(6), pp. 405–425. doi: 10.1016/0022-5088(60)90024-2.
- Murayama, Y. (1975) 'Thin film formation of In_2O_3 , TiN, and TaN by rf reactive ion plating', *Journal of Vacuum Science and Technology*, 12(4), pp. 818–820. doi: 10.1116/1.568679.

Nahrwold, R. (1887) 'Ueber Luftelectricität', p. 467.

NICHOLSON, W. (1800) 'Account of the new Electrical or Galvanic Apparatus of Sig. Alex. Volta, and Experiment performed with the same', *Journal of natural philosophy, chemistry, and the arts*, p. 179. Available at: https://archive.org/details/cbarchive_121695_accountsofthenewelectricalorga9999/page/n2/mode/lup?view=theater.

Nikolov, K. (2016) *Health impact of displays' blue light emissions and our solution to the problem*. Available at: <https://laptopmedia.com/reviews/health-impact-of-display-blue-light-and-our-solutions-for-you/>.

O'Brien, N. *et al.* (2013) 'Near infrared spectroscopic authentication of seafood', *Journal of Near Infrared Spectroscopy*, 21(4), pp. 299–305. doi: 10.1255/jnirs.1063.

O'Brien, N. A. *et al.* (2012a) 'Miniature near-infrared (NIR) spectrometer engine for handheld applications', *Next-Generation Spectroscopic Technologies V*, 8374, p. 837404. doi: 10.1117/12.917983.

O'Brien, N. A. *et al.* (2012b) 'Miniature near-infrared (NIR) spectrometer engine for handheld applications', 8374, p. 837404. doi: 10.1117/12.917983.

O'Leary, S. K., Johnson, S. R. and Lim, P. K. (1997) 'The relationship between the distribution of electronic states and the optical absorption spectrum of an amorphous semiconductor: An empirical analysis', *Journal of Applied Physics*, 82(7), pp. 3334–3340. doi: 10.1063/1.365643.

Ocean Insight. (2023) *History of Ocean Insight*. Available at: <https://www.oceaninsight.com/about/our-history/>.

Ohring, M. (2002a) *Materials Science of Thin Films*. Elsevier. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-524975-1.X5000-9.

Ohring, M. (2002b) 'Plasma and Ion Beam Processing of Thin Films', in *Materials Science of Thin Films*. Elsevier, pp. 203–275. doi: 10.1016/B978-012524975-1/50008-2.

Omega Optical, L. (2021) *Omega's History*. Available at: <https://www.omegafilters.com/our-company/company-history>.

Overbeck, C. J. (1933) 'Color in Films of Sputtered Tin', *Journal of the Optical Society of*
214

America, 23(3), p. 109. doi: 10.1364/JOSA.23.000109.

Pavri, B. E. *et al.* (1999) 'Development of radiometric system models for performance comparison of proposed instruments', in Leonelli, J. and Althouse, M. L. (eds), pp. 15–24. doi: 10.1117/12.336866.

Peatross, J. and Michael, W. (2015) *Physics of Light and Optics, Physics of Light and Optics*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1364/FIO.2010.JWA64>.

Penfold, A. S. (1975) 'Magnetic field generation apparatus'. Available at: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US3919678A/en>.

Penning, F. M. and Moubis, J. H. A. (1937) 'Eine Neutronenröhre Ohne Pumpvorrichtung', *Physica*, 4(11), pp. 1190–1199. doi: 10.1016/S0031-8914(37)80178-0.

PerkinElmer Life And Analytical Sciences (2005) '60 Years of PerkinElmer Innovation in Infrared Spectroscopy'.

PerkinElmer Ltd (2000) 'Lambda 20 / Lambda 40 Installation and Maintenance Guide', *Computer*, pp. 87–88.

Peter Sigmund (1993) *Fundamental processes in sputtering of atoms and molecules. Munksgaard*. Kongelige Danske videnskabernes selskab. Available at: https://books.google.co.uk/books/about/Fundamental_processes_in_sputtering_of_a.html?id=kHIyAQAAIAAJ&redir_esc=y (Accessed: 26 July 2019).

Piegari, A. and Bulir, J. (2006) 'Variable narrowband transmission filters with a wide rejection band for spectrometry', *Applied Optics*, 45(16), p. 3768. doi: 10.1364/AO.45.003768.

von Pirani, M. (1907) 'Method of producing homogeneous bodies from tantalum or other highly-refractory metals.', *US Patent*. Available at: <http://www.google.com/patents/US873958>.

Plücker, M. (1858) 'XLVI. Observations on the electrical discharge through rarefied gases', *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science*, 16(109), pp. 408–418. doi: 10.1080/14786445808642591.

Pohl, R. von and Pringsheim, P. (1912) 'Über die Herstellung von Metallspiegeln durch Distillation im Vakuum', *Verhandl. Deut. Physik. Ges*, 14, p. 506.

- Poitras, D. and Dobrowolski, J. A. (2004) 'Toward perfect antireflection coatings 2 Theory', *Applied Optics*, 43(6), p. 1286. doi: 10.1364/AO.43.001286.
- Pottathara, Y. B. *et al.* (2019) 'Synthesis and Processing of Emerging Two-Dimensional Nanomaterials', in *Nanomaterials Synthesis*. Elsevier, pp. 1–25. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-815751-0.00001-8.
- Powell, R. A. and Rossnagel, S. M. (1999a) 'Chapter 2 Physics of Sputtering', in *PVD for Microelectronics Sputter Deposition Applied to Semiconductor Manufacturing*, pp. 23–49. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1079-4050\(99\)80005-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1079-4050(99)80005-2).
- Powell, R. A. and Rossnagel, S. M. (1999b) 'Chapter 4 The planar magnetron', *Thin Films*, 26(C), pp. 87–101. doi: 10.1016/S1079-4050(99)80007-6.
- Pügner, T., Knobbe, J. and Grüger, H. (2016) 'Near-Infrared Grating Spectrometer for Mobile Phone Applications', *Applied Spectroscopy*, 70(5), pp. 734–745. doi: 10.1177/0003702816638277.
- Quijada, M. A. *et al.* (2018) 'E-beam generated plasma etching for developing high-reflectance mirrors for far-ultraviolet astronomical instrument applications', in *Space Telescopes and Instrumentation 2018: Ultraviolet to Gamma*, p. 103. doi: 10.1117/12.2314391.
- Raffaella, A. and Relly, V. V. P. (2017) 'MODERN TRANSPORTATION AND PHOTOVOLTAIC ENERGY FOR URBAN ECOTOURISM', *Transylvanian Review of Administrative Sciences*, 10(41), pp. 129–145.
- Ratches, J. A. (2006) 'Current and future trends in military night vision applications', *Ferroelectrics*, 342(1), pp. 183–192. doi: 10.1080/00150190600946351.
- Reuter, D. C. *et al.* (1997) 'Hyperspectral sensing using the Linear Etalon Imaging Spectral Array', in Fujisada, H., Calamai, G., and Sweeting, M. N. (eds) *Advanced and Next-Generation Satellites II*, p. 154. doi: 10.1117/12.265427.
- Robbins, W. B. (1998) 'Roll-to-Roll Vacuum Coating', in *Handbook of Vacuum Science and Technology*. Elsevier, pp. 761–788. doi: 10.1016/B978-012352065-4/50077-8.
- Rosenberg, K. P. *et al.* (1994) 'Logarithmically variable infrared etalon filters', in Rancourt, J. D. (ed.) *Optical Thin Films IV: New Developments*, pp. 223–232. doi: 10.1117/12.185804.

- Rosnagel, S. M. *et al.* (1991) ‘Collimated magnetron sputter deposition’, *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology A: Vacuum, Surfaces, and Films*, 9(2), pp. 261–265. doi: 10.1116/1.577531.
- Rosnagel, S. M. (1994) ‘Metal ion deposition from ionized magnetron sputtering discharge’, *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology B: Microelectronics and Nanometer Structures*, 12(1), p. 449. doi: 10.1116/1.587142.
- Sargent, R. B. and O’Brien, N. A. (2003) ‘Dielectric materials for thin-film-based optical communications filters’, *MRS Bulletin*, 28(5), pp. 372–376. doi: 10.1557/mrs2003.103.
- Schenk, H. *et al.* (2000) ‘Large deflection micromechanical scanning mirrors for linear scans and pattern generation’, *IEEE Journal on Selected Topics in Quantum Electronics*, 6(5), pp. 715–722. doi: 10.1109/2944.892609.
- Scherer, M. *et al.* (1992) ‘Reactive alternating current magnetron sputtering of dielectric layers’, *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology A: Vacuum, Surfaces, and Films*, 10(4), pp. 1772–1776. doi: 10.1116/1.577745.
- Schiller, S., Heisig, U. and Goedicke, K. (1975) ‘Alternating ion plating—A method of high-rate ion vapor deposition’, *Journal of Vacuum Science and Technology*, 12(4), pp. 858–864. doi: 10.1116/1.568688.
- Schoonover Inc. (2018) *How A Polycold Or MegaCold Works In Vacuum Coating To Increase Production*. Available at: <https://schoonoverinc.com/how-a-polycold-or-megacold-works-in-vacuum-coating-to-increase-production/>.
- Seery, B. D., Cramer, D. B. and Stevens, C. (1996) ‘EO-1: NASA’s first new millennium earth orbiting mission’, *Space Sciencecraft Control and Tracking in the New Millennium*, 2810, pp. 4–10. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.255149>.
- Shon, C. H. and Lee, J. K. (2002) ‘Modeling of magnetron sputtering plasmas’, 192, pp. 258–269.
- Shorokhov, I. *et al.* (2018) ‘Novel Thin Film Transducers for Durable High-Resolution Imaging in Industry and Medicine’, in *IEEE International Ultrasonics Symposium, IUS*, pp. 5–8. doi: 10.1109/ULTSYM.2018.8580196.
- Siesler, H. W. *et al.* (2008) *Near-Infrared Spectroscopy: Principles, Instruments*,

- Applications, Near-Infrared Spectroscopy: Principles, Instruments, Applications*. Germany.
- Smakula, A. (1935) ‘Verfahren zur Erhöhung der Lichtdurchlässigkeit optischer Teile durch Erniedrigung des Brechungsindex an den Grenzflächen dieser optischen Teile’. German. Available at: <https://patents.google.com/patent/DE685767C/de>.
- Smith, D. L. (1996) *Thin-film deposition: principles and practice*, *Choice Reviews Online*. doi: 10.5860/choice.33-3347.
- Smith, J. H. R. (1959) ‘Temescal Metallurgical Corp’. United States. Available at: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US2907679A/en>.
- Soddy, F. (1907) ‘Calcium as an absorbent of gases for the production of high vacua and spectroscopic research’, *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical and Physical Character*, 78(526), pp. 429–458. doi: 10.1098/rspa.1907.0002.
- Song, S. *et al.* (2017) ‘Reactive dynamics analysis of critical Nb₂O₅ sputtering rate for drum-based metal-like deposition’, *Applied Optics*, 56(4), p. C206. doi: 10.1364/AO.56.00C206.
- Song, S. *et al.* (2019) ‘Linear variable bandpass filter for hyper-spectral imaging camera in agriculture applications’, in *Optics InfoBase Conference Papers*, pp. 9–11. doi: 10.1364/OIC.2019.ThC.6.
- Song, S. *et al.* (2020) ‘Low-cost hyper-spectral imaging system using a linear variable bandpass filter for Agriculture applications’, *Applied Optics*, 59(5), p. A167. doi: 10.1364/AO.378269.
- Song, S. *et al.* (2023) ‘Tantalum oxide and silicon oxide mixture coatings deposited using microwave plasma assisted co-sputtering for optical mirror coatings in gravitational wave detectors’, *Applied Optics*, 62(7), p. B73. doi: 10.1364/AO.477211.
- Song, S. and Placido, F. (2011) ‘In-situ investigation of spontaneous and plasma-enhanced oxidation of AlN film surfaces’, *Applied Physics Letters*, 99(12), p. 121901. doi: 10.1063/1.3640219.
- Stark, J. (1908) ‘Über die zerstäubende Wirkung der Kanalstrahlen (Emission sekundärer Atomstrahlen)’, *Zeitschrift für Elektrochemie und angewandte physikalische Chemie*, 14(46),

pp. 752–756. Available at:
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/bbpc.19080144603>.

Steidel, C. A., Jaffe, D. and Kumagai, H. Y. (1972) ‘Compositional Control of Tantalum–Aluminum Alloy Films by a dc Biased, ac Sputtering Technique’, *Journal of Vacuum Science and Technology*, 9(1), pp. 346–349. doi: 10.1116/1.1316605.

Strong, J. (1933) ‘Evaporation Technique for Aluminum’, *Physical Review*, 43(6), pp. 498–498. doi: 10.1103/PhysRev.43.498.

Strong, J. (1936) ‘On a Method of Decreasing the Reflection from Nonmetallic Substances’, *Journal of the Optical Society of America*, 26(1), p. 73. doi: 10.1364/JOSA.26.000073.

Subbaroybhat, M. (2021) *A Complete Guide to Microcontrollers, RS Components Ltd.* Available at: <https://uk.rs-online.com/web/content/discovery/ideas-and-advice/microcontrollers-guide>.

Tack, N. *et al.* (2012) ‘A compact, high-speed, and low-cost hyperspectral imager’, *Silicon Photonics VII*, 8266(0), p. 82660Q. doi: 10.1117/12.908172.

Thelen, A. and Apfel, J. H. (1965) ‘Circularly Wedged Optical Coatings I Theory’, *Applied Optics*, 4(8), p. 977. doi: 10.1364/ao.4.000977.

Thermo Secentific (2006) *Advantages of Fourier-Transform Near-Infrared Spectroscopy*. doi: 10.4324/9781315370323.

Thomas, N. C. (1991) ‘The early history of spectroscopy’, *Journal of Chemical Education*, 68(8), pp. 631–634. doi: 10.1021/ed068p631.

Thomson, J. J. (1913) ‘Rays of positive electricity and their application to chemical analyses’, *Longmans*.

Thornton, J. A. (1978) ‘Magnetron sputtering: basic physics and application to cylindrical magnetrons’, *Journal of Vacuum Science and Technology*, 15(2), pp. 171–177. doi: 10.1116/1.569448.

Tian, M. *et al.* (2018) ‘A review on the recent research progress in the compound parabolic concentrator (CPC) for solar energy applications’, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 82(June 2016), pp. 1272–1296. doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2017.09.050.

ULVAC Group (1975) 'ULVAC Group's HISTORY'. Available at: https://www.ulvac.co.jp/eng/_csr/eco/report/pdf/2015/2.pdf.

Vaughan, J. M. (2017) *The Fabry–Perot Interferometer*. Routledge. doi: 10.1201/9780203736715.

VIAVI Solutions Inc. (2023) *MicroNIR 1700ES*. Available at: <https://www.viavisolutions.com/en-us/osp/products/micronir-1700es>.

Vossen, J. L. (1980) *Thin Film Processes, Volume 2, Journal of The Electrochemical Society*.

Wang, L. *et al.* (2009) 'Structure and optical properties of ZnO:V thin films with different doping concentrations', *Thin Solid Films*, 517(13), pp. 3721–3725. doi: 10.1016/j.tsf.2008.12.043.

Wasa, K., Kanno, I. and Kotera, H. (2012) *Handbook of Sputter Deposition Technology: Fundamentals and Applications for Functional Thin Films, Nano-Materials and MEMS: Second Edition, Handbook of Sputter Deposition Technology: Fundamentals and Applications for Functional Thin Films, Nano-Materials and MEMS: Second Edition*. Elsevier. doi: 10.1016/C2010-0-67037-4.

Wehner, G. K. (1955) 'Sputtering by Ion Bombardment', in, pp. 239–298. doi: 10.1016/S0065-2539(08)60959-2.

Westwood, W. D., Glocker, D. and Shah, S. (2018) *Handbook of Thin Film Process Technology 98/1 Reactive sputtering, Handbook of Thin Film Process Technology*. Bristol, Philadelphia: Institute of Physics Publishing; CRC Press. doi: 10.1201/9781351072793.

Wiesent, B. R. *et al.* (2011) 'Linear variable filter based oil condition monitoring systems for offshore windturbines', *Instrumentation, Metrology, and Standards for Nanomanufacturing, Optics, and Semiconductors V*, 8105, p. 81050D. doi: 10.1117/12.891505.

Wiesent, B. R., Dorigo, D. G. and Koch, A. W. (2013) '3.3 - A miniaturized MID-IR-Spectrometer based on a linear variable filter and pyroelectric line array – Monitoring oil condition', in *Proceedings IRS² 2013*. AMA Service GmbH, Von-Münchhausen-Str. 49, 31515 Wunstorf, Germany, pp. 59–64. doi: 10.5162/irs2013/i3.3.

William, H. B. (2002) *Justus Von Liebig: The Chemical Gatekeeper*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Available at:

https://books.google.co.uk/books/about/Justus_Von_Liebig.html?id=VugoemP2th0C&redir_esc=y.

Xu, X., Zhang, H. and Chen, G. (2017) 'The development and latest progress of near infrared spectrometer', *Anhui Chemical Industry*, (43(4): 7–10).

Xu, Y. (2022) 'Application and Equipment of Preparation Technology of Ferroelectric Thin Film Materials in Sports Industry', *Journal of Nanomaterials*, 2022. doi: 10.1155/2022/9480475.

Yu, X., Lu, Q. and Gao, H. (2013) 'Current status and prospects of portable NIR spectrometer', *Spectroscopy and Spectral Analysis*, (33(11):2983-2988). doi: 10.3964/j.issn.1000-0593(2013)11-2983-06.

ZELTEX Inc. (2023) *ZELTEX ZX-50 IQ*, www.zeltex.com. Available at: <https://zeltex.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/zx-50iq.pdf>.

Zhang, L. *et al.* (1999) 'Miniature spectrometer based on linear variable interference filters', in Leonelli, J. and Althouse, M. L. (eds), p. 42. doi: 10.1117/12.371278.

Zhou, Cai, S. *et al.* (2021) 'Development of measurement system and analysis method for characterization of linear variable bandpass filters', *Optics Express*, 29(14), p. 21386. doi: 10.1364/oe.431571.